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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D3.3 | D11:

Synthesis report on the comparative analysis of SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in six countries: Encouraging the diversity, processes and contributions of SIE

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Executive Summary

SONNET aims to co-create a rich inter- and transdisciplinary understanding of the diversity, processes (including enabling and impeding factors) and contributions of SIE (social innovation in the energy sector). This report primarily contributes towards SONNET objective 2:

Objective 2 Identify and analyse enabling and impeding conditions for SIE processes, with a focus on socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political issues and their interrelations.

As such, it forms part of WP3, which addresses the following research questions: How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop, and institutionalise over time? How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time? What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the 'outside' institutional environment?¹ This report also contributes towards SONNET objectives 1 and 3:

Objective 1 Capture the diversity of SIE in Europe within a comprehensive SIE typology to allow for a differentiated analysis of SIE.

Objective 3 Characterise the contributions of different types of SIE in relation to making energy more secure, sustainable, competitive, and affordable for Europe's citizens.

In this way, it also contributes towards other work packages: in particular, by complementing WPs 2 and 6 and providing input for WPs 1 and 5.

In WP3, we make use of a **multiple, embedded case study approach**, using diverse units of analysis to build a better understanding of SIE-fields and the SIE-initiatives within them. The main unit of analysis is the SIE-field, while the subunits of analysis are the SIE, different SIE-field-actors (who work on the SIE) and their SIE-initiatives, and other field-actors (who enable and impede the SIE). The analysis also considers the context of wider socio-political, socio-economic and socio-cultural issues linked to these actors and the SIE-field. The case studies are presented as a series of six country reports: France, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Switzerland, and United Kingdom. Each country report presents three embedded case studies of SIE-fields within their national context. Overall, the country reports present 18 embedded case studies of SIE-fields, and 36 cases of SIE-initiatives nested within the SIE-field investigations and published in deliverable D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2020).

This deliverable D3.3 has two overall aims:

- ★ To dive into a comparative analysis of each SIE-field and their SIE-initiatives across three SONNET countries (for example, comparing framings against fossil fuel energy pathways in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland). This analysis draws on empirical

¹ See D1.2 (Wittmayer et al., 2020) and D3.1 (Hielscher et al., 2020) for more information on research questions.

phenomena surfacing in the different cases and specific concepts that help to further the understanding of SIE.

- ▲ To derive key insights into specific aspects of the diversity, processes and contributions of SIE.

The deliverable D3.3 includes:

- ▲ An introduction to the WP3 work, outlining a) key concepts and conceptual map, b) research questions, c) embedded case study approach, and d) conducting the fieldwork.
- ▲ A brief introduction into the country context in relations to SIE and past attention towards SIE.
- ▲ Deep dives into comparing each SIE-field (and their SIE-initiatives) across three SONNET countries.
 - Research design of each SIE-field comparison.
 - Deep dives into comparing each SIE-field across three SONNET countries.
 - Outline of concluding on the enabling and impeding factors for the development of SIE-fields and their SIE.
- ▲ Comparative analysis of 18 case studies
 - Methodology of case comparison.
 - Comparing SIE-fields (and their SIE-initiatives).
 - Working propositions.
- ▲ The annex includes
 - Outline of initial WP3 working propositions.
 - Table of research papers in progress.

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1 INTRODUCTION

SONNET (Social Innovation in Energy Transitions) brings diverse groups together to make sense of how social innovation can bring about a more sustainable energy sector in Europe. The project aims to co-create a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, successes, and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector (SIE).

WP3 involves studying the diversity, processes and contributions of SIE. However, the main focus is on building an understanding of processes. As outlined in deliverable D1.2 (Wittmayer et al., 2020), these are our major research questions for WP3:

- ★ How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop and institutionalise over time?
- ★ How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time?
- ★ What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the 'outside' institutional environment?

In the following sections, we introduce each of the three questions with short empirical narratives, conceptual working definitions, and a brief characterisation of the key aspects of the SIE-field that we have investigated in our case studies.

1.1 Key concepts and visual conceptual map

This section introduces the three distinct but intertwined foci that were empirically investigated in WP3: 1) Emergence, development and institutionalisation of SIE and SIE-field over time; 2) SIE-field-actors' and other field-actors' interactions with the 'outside' institutional environment; 3) Enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work. It includes descriptions and definitions of key concepts involved in each of these three foci, and concludes with an overall conceptual map that visualises the relationships between them.

1.1.1 Emergence, development and institutionalisation of SIE and SIE-field over time

WP3 includes analysing the emergence, development and institutionalisation of SIE within an SIE-field, as well as the development of SIE-initiatives, SIE-field-actors and other field-actors over time. The SIE-field includes diverse SIE-initiatives, SIE-field-actors (who work on SIE) and other field-actors (who enable and/or impede SIE). These actors take one another and their activities into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of an SIE and of their relationship to one another. Over time, SIE-field-actors' and other field-actors' patterns of activities can become more and more held in place, and practically taken for granted within a SIE-field. Actors can start to recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules. This process is conceptualised as institutionalisation.

Empirically, we identify how actors manifest around specific SIE and develop collectives and shared (but not necessarily consensual) narratives and activities over time. We also investigate what is 'socially innovative', by specifying the ideas, objects and actions these actors and collectives are working on within an SIE-field, and how these demonstrate a change in social relations and new ways of doing, organising and thinking.

This work makes use of the following conceptual definitions:

- ✦ Social innovation in the energy sector (SIE) is a combination of ideas, objects and/or actions that change social relations and involve new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy. An example: Organising under cooperative principles to generate renewable energy.
- ✦ SIE-initiative is a localised version/manifestation in time and space of a SIE. It includes SIE-field-actors, as those actors working on SIE. They can be from every sphere of society (community, market, state, third sector = SIE as multi-actor phenomena). Examples are: Ecovillage Aardehuizen and Living Lab Walldorf.
- ✦ SIE-field-actors are individuals, organisations or other collectives who are part of a certain SIE-field and actively work on SIE. They can be from every sphere of society (community, market, state, third sector = SIE as multi-actor phenomena). Examples are cooperatives, citizen initiatives, energy companies, start-ups, local governments, intermediaries and NGOs.
- ✦ Other field-actors are individuals, organisations or other collectives who are part of a certain SIE-field – these can enable and/or impede SIE. They can be from every sphere of society (community, market, state, third sector). Examples are: Local governments, national governments, professional organisations, industry actors and citizens.
- ✦ A SIE-field is an arena/space that includes a specific SIE as well as SIE-field-actors working on it and other field-actors enabling and/or impeding it. In this space these actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of a SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules. SIE-fields are often not homogenous but are composed of actors with diverse and contradictory aims and interests. An example: The United Kingdom cooperative energy field includes SIE-initiatives, SIE-field-actors (e.g. Brighton Energy Co-op, Cooperative United Kingdom, Community Energy England) and other field-actors (United Kingdom Government, City of Brighton), who have a shared understanding of an SIE, which exists as 'organising under cooperative principles to generate renewable energy'.
- ✦ Institutionalisation is a process by which a pattern of activities comes to be regulative, normatively and cultural-cognitively held in place, and practically taken for granted within a SIE-field. The degree of institutionalisation is linked to the emergence and stability of a SIE-field.

1.1.2 SIE-field-actors' and other field-actors' interactions with the 'outside' institutional environment

The SIE-field (and its actors) are nested within an 'outside' institutional environment linked to an energy system. This environment is constituted by formal and informal institutions that shape the activities of SIE-field-actors and other field-actors within the SIE-field. Although energy systems consist of a wide range of institutionalised rules, norms, and beliefs, these institutions have been subject to profound changes over the past decade. These changes can influence SIE. They may emerge because of external shocks and societal trends (for example, climate change), but may also be influenced by processes taking place as part of SIE.

WP3 includes analysing how SIE, SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment, thereby co-shaping the SIE and its SIE-field, and contributing to change or maintain the 'outside' institutional environment. We are interested in how the 'outside' institutional environment 'surrounds' and 'penetrates' the SIE-field.

Empirically, we examine how dominant institutions (regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements) within the 'outside' institutional environment influence the emergence and development of SIE (i.e. social relations and patterns of doing, organising and thinking) within an SIE-field. We also identify and examine field events and contestations, inter-field interactions of SIE-fields and external shocks and societal trends. We investigate how these events, contestations, relations, shocks and trends influence both SIE-field developments and 'outside' institutional environments as they co-shape each other over time. A particular focus is on political and policy developments.

This work makes use of the following additional conceptual definitions:

- ✦ Formal and informal institutions constitute the institutional environment. The SIE-field itself constitutes an environment (= SIE-field institutional environment) but also is nested with the larger encompassing institutional environment (= outside institutional environment). The SIE-field and its institutional environment consist of institutions and actors who interact with each other. The 'outside' institutional environment consists of institutions that can 'penetrate' (i.e. shape/influence/interact with) the SIE-field.
- ✦ Institutional change is any change in form, quality or state in an institution or arrangement of institutional elements.
- ✦ Institutions are made up of regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements. They are tacitly or explicitly agreed upon rules constraining or enabling activities of actors that provide stability and meaning to social life. These can be: 1) Regulative institutions: laws, rules, standards, policies, 2) Normative institutions: norms and value systems, and 3) Cultural-cognitive institutions: shared conceptions of reality, binding expectations, common beliefs.
- ✦ Field events are events, which might influence actors' relations and interactions within the SIE-field and can 'unsettle' the existing 'outside' institutional environment (but not necessarily change it). An example: A community energy advocacy group that was set up at a conference and started to talk to policy makers about their activities.

- ▲ Field contestations are debates among SIE-field-actors and/ or other field-actors over SIE-field structures and processes. These contestations can 'unsettle' the existing 'outside' institutional environment (but not necessarily change it). An example: Contestations over regulatory and industrial policy linked to energy infrastructure developments.
- ▲ Inter-field relations are interactions between SIE-fields (they can be nested and/ or overlapping). An example: Cooperative energy is nested within community energy in the United Kingdom.
- ▲ External shocks and societal trends are, for instance, climate change, national elections, capitalism, ageing population, and economic crises that influence SIE-fields structures. Examples: Financial crisis, weather disasters, and pandemics.

1.1.3 Enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work

The previous sub-sections introduced the ideas that processes of institutionalisation can occur within an SIE-field, and that the 'outside' institutional environment may also be changed or maintained through interactions with the SIE-field. When SIE-initiatives, other SIE-field-actors, and other field-actors engage in creating, maintaining and transforming institutions to be able to work on, enable and/ or impede SIE developments, this is conceptualised as institutional work. There might be factors that can support or hinder institutional work. For example, not all actors might be able to conduct this work, depending on their skills, capacities, intentions and resources. Some of the work conducted might have intentional or unintentional effects. Institutional changes can only occur if the work and its activities appear to be more and more legitimate over time while previously institutionalised practices become eroded.

WP3 involves studying the practices of institutional work conducted by SIE-field-actors and other field-actors. In particular, it aims to understand the factors that enable or impede the performance of these activities, and their success in creating institutional change. To do this, we examine why, how, when and where actors work at creating, maintaining and transforming institutions. This then enables us to build an understanding of: the different forms of institutional work; types of work conducted (boundary work, strategy work, etc.); actors who are engaged (or not) in this work; and enabling and impeding factors to be able to conduct this work. Drawing attention to the practices rather than purely accomplishments of institutional work allows for an investigation of intended effects but also unintended consequences: successes but also failures, winners and losers, and acts of resistance and transformation. This then enables us to study how SIE-field-actors and other field-actors potentially contribute to institutional changes and/ or maintain existing 'outside' institutional environments.

This work makes use of the following additional conceptual definition:

- ▲ Institutional work refers to the activities of SIE-field-actors and other field-actors that aim to create, maintain and transform institutions. Examples: 1) Attempts to influence policy makers and the general public through direct lobbying, research reports, positioning papers, advertising, and the setting of technical standards and 2) Attempts to influence

informal institutions, such as values, norms, binding expectations, common beliefs, habits, and routines, among the wider public (Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006; Arenas, 2017).

The relationships between these three foci are visualised in Figure 1. Within the figure, blue text and images represent SIE-fields, the SIE and actors involved; black represents the 'outside' institutional environment; and orange represents processes by which elements within these may be changed or maintained.

Figure 1: Summary of overall visual conceptual ma

1.2 Research questions

Based on the three foci outlined in the previous section, the following major and minor empirical research questions have guided the WP3 investigations:

1) How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop, and institutionalise over time?

- ★ What is 'socially innovative' about SIE-initiatives and/or SIE-field-actors? How and to what extent do which ideas, objects and/or actions demonstrate a change in social relations and new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy? How have these SIE developed over time and space?
- ★ What are relevant SIE-field-actors and other field-actors within the SIE-field, and what are their roles within the SIE-field? How have these roles changed over time?
- ★ What are relevant aims, narratives and goals that have been developed and manifested by SIE-field-actors and/ or other field-actors within the SIE-field over time? To what extent do

SIE-field-actors and/ or other field-actors hold ambitions to change the 'outside' institutional environment?

- ★ How can the interactions/relations between SIE-field-actors and/or other field-actors be characterised (e.g. cooperation, exchange, competition and conflict)? How have they changed (including power relations) over time? What types of informal and formal alliances, networks, collaborations have existed (and possibly still do)?
- ★ What have been shared narratives, activities, learnt lessons, etc. between alliances/networks/collaborations of SIE-field-actors and/or other field-actors over time? How have these narratives, activities, lessons, etc. been reproduced, adopted and replicated over time? To which extent have they been legitimised and/or contested by several actors within the SIE-field over time? How/to what extent do they refer to power issues and include ambitions to improve them?

2) How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the 'outside' institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time?

- ★ Which institutions (regulative, normative, cultural-cognitive) within the 'outside' institutional environment have shaped (including enabled/ impeded) SIE and its SIE-field (and how)?
- ★ What are the key external shocks, trends and inter-field interactions that enable/ impede the SIE and its SIE-field, and how (now and in the past)? How is the SIE and its SIE-field shaped by these events, trends and interactions (now and in the past)? How (if so) have these shocks, trends and inter-field interactions unsettled the 'outside' institutional environment?
- ★ What are important field events and field contestations² that have influenced the SIE and its SIE-field (now and in the past and why)? How (if so) have these events and contestations unsettled the 'outside' institutional environment?
- ★ What have been the most important alliances/networks/collaborations and shifts in power between SIE-field-actors and/ or other field-actors that emerged from these shocks, trends, interactions, events and contestations (when, how and for what reasons)?

3) What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the 'outside' institutional environment?

- ★ How, why, when, and where do SIE-field-actors and/or other field-actors conduct activities linked to creating and transforming institutions? What have been the most important collective (shared) activities (when, how and for what reasons)?
- ★ How and to what extent do SIE-field-actors and/or other field-actors (intended or unintended) reproduce dominant ways of doing, organising and thinking (i.e. maintaining institutions)?
- ★ What factors have enabled and/or impeded institutional work? E.g. Resources, learnt lessons and competences connected to actors/alliances/networks/collaborations.

² These can be contestations within the field and/ or linked to the 'outside' institutional environment.

- ★ Who is involved in conducting institutional work (and who is not, and why not)? Which actors benefit from this work (or not)?
- ★ What forms do these activities linked to maintaining, creating and transforming institutions take (e.g. emotional work, boundary work, strategy work, and/ or values work)?
- ★ What have been intended and unintended effects (i.e. contributions) derived from conducting institutional work? What influence have they had on SIE-field and 'outside' institutional environments?

1.3 Embedded case study approach

SONNET aims to make use of an embedded case study approach, aiming to describe SIE-fields using diverse subunits of analysis. The main unit of analysis is the SIE-field (i.e. our case), whereas the subunits of analysis are SIE-initiatives, SIE-field-actors, other field-actors and SIE (see Figure 2). The context relates to the 'outside' institutional environment linked to the SIE-field, reflecting that SIE-fields are embedded within a wider encompassing context.

Figure 2: Illustration of SONNET's embedded case study design: Showing the relations between the subunits

In SONNET, we have identified eighteen types of SIE that, together with SIE-field-actors and other field-actors, make up the SIE-fields (for more detail see D1.1 for typology of SIE (Wittmayer et al., 2020) and D1.2 (Wittmayer et al., 2020)). To be able to study the SIE-fields in-depth and compare them, we have first delineated the national context as an important factor in the development and emergence of SIE, and have included a diverse mix of country contexts (FR, DE, NL, PL, CH, UK³). We then developed an SIE-typology (see deliverable D1.1 (Wittmayer et al., 2020)), identified types of SIE, and selected six SIE-fields for further investigation.

³ In SONNET, we studied Great Britain (England, Wales and Scotland) rather than the whole of the United Kingdom. This is due to the arrangement of the electricity grid in the country, with the transmission network in Northern Ireland being largely distinct from that of Great Britain. For consistency the term 'United Kindom' is still used unless the documents or

The selection of SIE-fields was grounded in a purposive sample including the following selection criteria: 1) recognisability and prevalence of SIE-fields in each national context (i.e. SIE-fields had to be empirically recognisable in each SONNET country); 2) full coverage of interactions and manifestations identified as part of the SIE-typology (Wittmayer et al., 2020); and 3) practical considerations including synergies with other SONNET work and building upon consortium expertise. The following six SIE-fields have been selected in different national contexts:

Circle: Cooperative organisation models for renewable energy (COOP RE); Triangle: Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways (FAFF); Square: Local electricity exchange (LEE); Star: City level competition for sustainable energy (CLC); Rectangle: Participatory incubation and experimentation (PIE); Half Moon: Financing and subsidies for RE (solar and wind) (FS RE).

Figure 3: Illustration of SONNET's embedded, multiple case study approach, including national context

Table 1 lists the six SIE-fields and provides a short description of each SIE-field, and lists the SIE-initiatives and countries studied.

Table 1: SIE-field descriptions and SIE-initiatives studied

SIE-field name	Short description of SIE-field	SIE-initiatives studied	Countries studied
Cooperative organisation models for renewable energy (COOP RE)	The SIE-field is made up of organisational models through which citizens jointly own the means of and/ or participate in renewable energy production. They adhere to the cooperative principles provided by the European federation of renewable energy cooperatives and by the International Cooperative Alliance.	France: Eoliennes en Pays de Vilaine; Buxia Energies. Germany: SOLIX ENERGIE cooperative; Elektrizitätswerke Schönau (EWS). Switzerland: ADEV cooperative (Arbeitsgruppe Dezentrale Energieversorgung); Optima Solar Schweiz cooperative.	France, Germany, Switzerland

interviewees explicitly referred to 'Great Britain'. It is also possible to see an emphasis on studying England before Wales and Scotland.

SIE-field name	Short description of SIE-field	SIE-initiatives studied	Countries studied
Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways (FAFF)	The SIE-field entails the creation and development of different framings against energy pathways centred on fossil fuels. These framings contain problem descriptions and envisioned alternative futures.	<p>Netherlands: Groninger Bodem Beweging; Schaliegasvrij Nederland; Fossielvrij NL.</p> <p>Poland: The Foundation 'Development YES - Open-Pit Mines NO'; a strategic document "The Concept of Just Transition for Eastern Wielkopolska".</p> <p>United Kingdom: Campaign to Protect Pont Valley, Durham, North England; Groups in Balcombe, West Sussex, South England; Fossil Free Sussex, University of Sussex; Roseacre Awareness Group & Preston New Road Action Group, Lancashire; Frack Free Isle of Wight renamed to Don't Drill The Wight.</p>	Netherlands, Poland, United Kingdom
Local electricity exchange (LEE)	The SIE-field is defined as multi-actor collectives, experimenting with and implementing novel financial, institutional, technical (digital) and business model innovations to enable grid-connected local/regional renewable energy exchange (includes production, consumption and distribution, and sometimes even trading).	<p>France: the municipality of la Motte-Servolex; Mézière Energie of Planète Oui and Valorem.</p> <p>Switzerland: The district of Erlenmatt-Ost; Housing Cooperative Rossfeld.</p> <p>United Kingdom: Energy Local; Ripple Energy; Wadebridge Renewable Energy Network (WREN); Repowering London.</p>	France, Switzerland, United Kingdom
City level competition for sustainable energy (CLC)	The SIE-field is made up of energy competitions that happen at the city level. These are activities that aim to contribute to low-carbon energy changes within the city and/ or city administration to better address energy issues. These competitions often involve elements of ranking, gaining and/ or winning.	<p>France: Cit'ergie; the competition "Déclics"; Ville durable et innovante – VDI).</p> <p>Germany: 'Deutscher Nachhaltigkeitspreis'; the 'Climathon' competition, organised locally in Mannheim by the association 'Hackerstolz e.V.'</p> <p>Switzerland: 2000-Watt Areal; Energy Regions (Energie-Region); Spiel Energie; EnergieStadt label</p>	France, Germany, Switzerland
Participatory incubation and experimentation (PIE)	The SIE-field is made up of multi-actor collaborations, creating formats to experiment with socio-technical solutions for specific energy pathways. They often have a time-bound character and physical spaces	<p>Germany: Quartier Zukunft – Karlsruhe; Reallabor Energieavantgarde Anhalt.</p> <p>Netherlands: Buiksloterham (Amsterdam); Vve Aardehuizen (Olst).</p>	Germany, Netherlands, Poland

SIE-field name	Short description of SIE-field	SIE-initiatives studied	Countries studied
	for their experimentations and incubation.	Poland: „Osada Twórców” (The Creators' Settlement); Zgorzelec Renewable Energy Sources Development and Energy Efficiency Cluster (ZKlaster)	
Financing and subsidies for RE (solar and wind) (FS RE)	This SIE-field is defined as financing and subsidy mechanisms through which funding and/ or investment is made available to facilitate the activities of novel actor constellations related to the installation of wind and solar energy.	Netherlands: DuurzaamInvesteren ('Sustainable Investing'); Invest NL. Poland: a public subsidy programme “My Electricity”; Krakowska Elektrownia Społeczna (Krakow Social Power Plant; KES). United Kingdom: Abundance (crowdfunding platform); Leapfrog Finance.	Netherlands, Poland, United Kingdom

The next section briefly describes the fieldwork conducted for the case study work; for a more detailed description, see D3.1 (Hielscher et al., 2020).

1.4 Brief outline of conducting the fieldwork

The embedded case study approach aims to describe SIE-fields using diverse units of analysis: SIE, SIE-field, SIE-initiatives, and SIE-field-actors (who work on SIE) and other field-actors (who intentionally and/or unintentionally enable and/or impede SIEs within a SIE-field). The fieldwork consists of document reviews, in-depth interviews and participant observations. We draw on the innovation history approach to co-construct an account of the emergence and development of an SIE-field over time; specifically, case study researchers contribute to this account through the document review, and SIE-field-actors and other field-actors contribute through interviews. In addition, we take inspiration from the critical turning points approach to examine critical instances/events/processes where SIE-field-actors and other field-actors have conducted institutional work to create, maintain and/or transform institutions.

Within each SONNET country, data collection across the three embedded case studies involved conducting 24-50 interviews, analysing 40-60 documents, and carrying out 30-60 hours of participant observations. These three methods were used to enable data enrichment and triangulation. Across all 18 embedded case studies, a total of 171 interviews were conducted and analysed, around 298 documents were analysed (the overall number is larger due to the literature reviews carried out by the country teams), and 37 online events were attended as part of participant observations.

The circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic had consequences for how we could collect data. In-depth interviews were conducted over the phone or via video calls rather than face-to-face.

Participant observations took place during online rather than in-person events, or not at all. We therefore deepened the document review and increased the number of interviews. These circumstances varied between countries and rapidly changed throughout the fieldwork. A more in-depth outline of the methodology for each case study can be found in D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021).

Based on conducting the fieldwork, six country reports and 18 case study reports have been produced that make up D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021) and create the basis for conducting the comparative analysis for this deliverable. A list of reports can be found in Table 2.

Table 2: List of country reports and case study reports

Authors	Title of report	Referenced in this document
Vernay et al. 2021	Country report: Deep dives into social innovation in energy through investigating three SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in France	CR, France
Ranville et al. 2021	Research report on 'Renewable energy cooperative' in France	COOP RE, France
Vernay et al. 2021	Research report on 'Local electricity exchanges' in France	LEE, France
Vernay et al. 2021	Research report on 'City level competitions for sustainable energy' in France	CLC, France
Stadler et al. 2021	Country report: Deep dives into social innovation in energy through investigating three SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in Germany	CR, Germany
Heidary et al. 2021	Research report on 'Cooperative organisational models for renewable energy' in Germany	COOP RE, Germany
Stadler and Rogge 2021	Research report on 'Participatory incubation and experimentation' in Germany	PIE, Germany
Stadler 2021	Research report on 'City level competitions for sustainable energy' in Germany	CLC, Germany
Wittmayer et al. 2021	Country report: Deep dives into social innovation in energy through investigating three SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in the Netherlands/Belgium	CR, Netherlands
Wittmayer and Schrandt 2021	Research report on 'Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways' in the Netherlands	FAFF, Netherlands
Fraaije and Wittmayer 2020	Research report on 'Participatory incubation and experimentation' in the Netherlands and Flanders, Belgium	PIE, Netherlands
Fraaije et al. 2021	Research report on 'Financing and subsidies for RE (solar and wind)' in the Netherlands	FS RE, Netherlands
Dańkowska et al. 2021	Country report: Deep dives into social innovation in energy through investigating three SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in Poland	CR, Poland
Dańkowska 2021	Research report on 'Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways' in Poland	FAFF, Poland
Dańkowska 2021	Research report on 'Participatory experimentation and incubation' in Poland	PIE, Poland
Dembek and Stastik 2021	Research report on 'Financing and subsidies for renewable energy' in Poland	FS RE, Poland
Mueller and Musiolik 2021	Country report: Deep dives into social innovation in energy through investigating three SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in Switzerland	CR, Switzerland
Schmid and Musiolik 2020	Research report on 'Cooperative organisational models for renewable energy' in Switzerland	COOP RE, Switzerland
Musiolik and Mueller 2021	Research report on 'Local electricity exchange' in Switzerland	LEE, Switzerland

Mueller er al. 2021	Research report on 'City level competitions for sustainable energy' in Switzerland	CLC, Switzerland
Hielscher and Iskandarova 2021	Country report: Deep dives into social innovation in energy through investigating three SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in the United Kingdom	CR, United Kingdom
Hielscher 2021	Research report on 'Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways' in the United Kingdom	FAFF, United Kingdom
Iskandarova 2021	Research report on 'Local electricity in the United Kingdom	LEE, United Kingdom
Iskandarova and William 2021	Research report on 'Financing and subsidies for renewable energy' in the United Kingdom	FS RE, United Kingdom

2 BRIEF INTRODUCTION INTO COUNTRY CONTEXTS AND THEIR PAST ATTENTION ON SIE

2.1 Introduction

In this section, we briefly look across the six countries (France, Germany, the Netherlands⁴, Poland, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom) and reflect upon the 'understanding of SIE', 'policy attention towards SIE' and 'social and cultural attention towards SIE' in each country. This comparison provides first insights of the institutional environments in which SIE have emerged and developed.

2.2 Understanding of SIE

Ways of understanding social innovation in energy (SIE) vary between European countries. In Germany and Switzerland, SIE is understood as part of a wider societal energy transition. In Germany, SIE is a broad and flexible concept, including new social practices and organisational models that provide sustainable solutions for societal challenges (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung, 2021) as part of the German 'Energiewende' (a popular phrase used to describe transitions in the German energy system). The idea is that societal actors take responsibility in the sense of a new "*social contract for sustainability*" (WBGU, 2011:1). In this way, SIE contribute to increase the legitimacy of sustainability transitions. Renewable energy cooperatives (as a form of SIE) in particular gained high public acceptance rates and served as an important building block for the transformation of the German energy system.

Similarly, in Switzerland, SIE is broadly understood as activities coordinated at the national and municipal levels that contribute to the Energiestrategie 2050 (a package of measures approved via referendum). Understandings of SIE are mainly shaped through different levels of government, and similarly to Germany, the principles and activities of renewable energy cooperatives have played an important role in shaping a culture around SIE.

Meanwhile, in Poland SIE has only recently been referred to. Similarly, to Germany and Switzerland, it has been seen as a flexible concept, referring to new energy-related arrangements and initiatives which are alternative and/or additional to the dominant, centralised and state-owned energy system. Many novelties have resulted from pressures and/or inspirations drawn from European Union's policies.

By contrast, in the United Kingdom, SIE are often relatively narrowly understood, being closely linked to the idea of community energy (CE). Although energy cooperatives or energy clusters also play a role in understandings of SIE in Germany, Switzerland and Poland, the United

⁴ The case study work of WP3 began by focusing on two of the BENELUX countries and eventually zoomed in on the Netherlands. In this comparative analysis, we therefore also focus on the Netherlands.

Kingdom differs in that SIE are typically related to initiatives derived from the grassroots level with high community control, rather than government or market initiatives. Only very recently has there been a move towards multi-actor relations linked to CE. This can partly be explained by the fact that, although policy instruments such as feed-in tariffs (a subsidy for renewable electricity generation) were used to develop community energy initiatives, the United Kingdom policy generally envisages a centrally coordinated energy transition based on technological change.

In the Netherlands, explicit reference to social innovation started in about 2014. At this time it broadly referred to offering solutions for issues that do not have an immediate business case (Adviesraad voor het Wetenschaps- en Technologiebeleid, 2014). Social innovation began to be related to energy after a first (scientific) symposium on SIE was organised in 2017 at the Technical University Delft, from which an important special issue on the topic in Sustainability emerged (Hoppe and de Vries, 2018). Around that time, the term was increasingly adopted in Dutch policy circles: often referring to the manifold 'social' aspects of energy transitions, such as issues of citizen involvement.

Meanwhile, in France, understandings of SIE continue to relate more to social issues in general than to the notion of an energy transition in particular. Understandings of SIE are related to the notion of the social and solidarity economy, which involves the provision of services or goods to meet social needs not satisfied by market or policy conditions. Due to the dominance of nuclear power in the French electricity system, a wider societal energy transition has so far received relatively little attention. This is only slowly starting to change.

2.3 Policy attention towards SIE

While the EU 2030 targets on carbon reductions, energy efficiency improvements and renewables promotions are relevant for all EU Member States, national policies differ in their ambition, design and effectiveness. Because energy mix and infrastructure can vary between countries, the conditions for SIE differ across countries. Past research has shown that non-coherent and/or changing energy policy can hinder the growth of SIE over time.

In Germany, there has been an openness to SIE due to the decentralised political structure, which leaves room for local governments and grassroots initiatives to play an active role in energy transitions. In addition, Germany has a long tradition of citizen participation, mainly developed during opposition to nuclear energy in the 1970s. Policy attention has been very favourable towards SIE, in particular related to renewables; however, this attention has decreased significantly over time.

Like Germany, the political structure of Switzerland has nurtured the development and uptake of SIE. The federal system has put cities and municipalities at the heart of the energy transition, giving them powers to pursue their own initiatives and activities. However, the relatively slow rate of electricity system liberalisation may have hindered the development of community energy initiatives and SIE.

By contrast, in the Netherlands, the liberalisation of the electricity market in the 1990s has led to a decentralised and fragmented energy system controlled by private and public actors. Moreover, the 2008 financial crisis and the ensuing retreat of the central government shifted more powers to local governments. In Dutch ‘polder’ fashion, the 2013 Dutch Energy Agreement, a national agreement on energy ambitions and targets up to 2023, brought together state and local governments, employer organisations, unions, nature and environmental societies, and other societal and financial institutions. The agreement placed responsibility for the energy transition with local governments, as well as societal actors and citizens. However, it remained vague in terms of associated resources.

In countries with a high level of government and market centralisation one can observe lower levels of policy support for SIE (such as France and the UK). For example, although there has been increased policy interest in community energy activities in the United Kingdom, culminating in the Community Energy Strategy in 2014, direct incentives and support mechanisms never really materialised. Over the past few years, cuts to the feed-in tariff and other mechanisms meant that some activities gained less policy support and partly looked towards other collaborators (such as local authorities) and resources.

In Poland, there has been very limited policy support for SIE-initiatives due to a highly centralised energy system with a strong dominance of the coal sector. The great political and social impact of the mining lobby left little space for SIE until 2004, when EU energy policy began to play a key role in accelerating the energy transition towards a renewable energy mix. The entrance into the EU, together with rising costs for coal extraction has marked a milestone for a political, social and cultural shift. Similarly, in France, the energy system has been dominated and controlled by a centrally governed energy system mainly based on nuclear power. There has been a high dependence on nuclear energy until 2003, when social movements and energy cooperatives started to appear. In 2005, cities started to play an active role in local energy transitions, developing their own innovative plans and measures, making more room for SIE.

2.4 Social and cultural attention towards SIE

Over the years, increased societal attention towards environmental issues has led to rising levels of social engagement. For sure, public attitudes towards energy and energy transitions, including SIE, also depends on the social, cultural and political environment. For instance, Switzerland has a long history of public participation, and the decentralised political structure leaves more room for local governments and citizens to participate and implement their initiatives. In fact, self-organisation has been very common in Swiss society, mostly through forms of cooperatives and in times of economic hardship. The rise of anti-nuclear movements also nurtured high public interest in energy issues. Similarly, Germany has a long history of public participation originating in opposition to nuclear energy and technocratic urban planning. This has contributed to an ongoing culture of participation by citizens and civil society and is also associated with public acceptance of (at least some types of) renewable energy technologies. In Switzerland and Germany, public participation in energy transitions has further increased through the influence of the social movement Fridays for Future.

In contrast to Germany and Switzerland, a belief in progress through technological innovation and economic opportunity has generally been part of the culture of the Netherlands. However, space for SIE was created when the 2008 financial crisis was accompanied by a retreat of central government and increasing responsibility for municipal governments and citizens alongside the discourse of a 'participation society'. This has also reached the energy sector, where a sharp increase in energy cooperatives could be witnessed as well as the foundation of intermediary actors. However, these new entrants to the market face incumbent energy companies and a government that for a long time took the rather comfortable position of relying on domestic gas resources. Some incumbent actors have now been forced to stop and/or put their projects on hold as a result of local and national protests sparked by earthquakes in the extraction area, increased costs of extraction, and the increasing urgency of climate change discourses and mobilizations.

Social and cultural attention to SIE has traditionally been less strong in France and Poland due to centralised governance and dependence on nuclear or coal fired electricity generation (respectively). In France, central governance has meant that people have been largely excluded from the electricity sector. The population feels more distant from topics like renewable energy and energy transition. Cooperatives and social movements started to develop after the 2003 'négaWatt scenario' (created by French advocacy group 'Association négaWatt' to promote the phase out of fossil and nuclear energy) introduced principles of sufficiency, efficiency and renewable energy; and after cities began to play an active role in energy transitions in 2005. However, nuclear energy has remained publicly popular, which can impede the development of alternatives. Meanwhile, Poland has a long history of coal extraction, to the point where the mining lobby highly influences and controls policy making and public opinion. The situation started to change only with the emergence of initiatives such as 'Smog Alarms', spreading knowledge about the danger of polluted air. The shift to renewables is therefore harder than in a country like Germany, where opposition to nuclear energy has generated considerable social pressure for a more sustainable energy mix over a long period of time.

Finally, in the United Kingdom citizens often have low levels of trust towards the government and energy companies, which can encourage participation in community energy initiatives. The community energy sector has been growing since 2010, and has gained attention from stakeholders including energy companies, city administrations and policymakers in the hope of providing solutions to the 'social side of energy'. On the other hand, community energy initiatives are not yet seen as part of a 'new normal'. SIE-field-actors have also started to address central government directly, through groups such as Extinction Rebellion, Fridays for Future and more recently Insulate Britain (i.e. climate change movements), who protested along major roads to ask for increased energy efficiency measures in people's homes. These protest actions have also attracted national media attention.

3 DIVES INTO COMPARING SIE-FIELDS ACROSS THREE COUNTRIES

3.1 Introduction

Section 3 dives into a comparative analysis of each SIE-field across three SONNET countries (for example, comparing ‘framings against fossil fuel energy pathways’ (FAFF) in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland). To do this, it outlines key empirical phenomena surfacing in different cases and specific concepts that help to further the understanding of SIE. The comparative analysis helps to build an understanding of each SIE-field across the three countries, and of the enabling and impeding factors for SIE. The aim is to publish each SIE-field comparison as a journal article.⁵

This section begins by describing and reflecting on the research design of each SIE-field comparison (section 3.2). It then outlines key findings derived from each SIE-field comparative analysis (section 3.3). Finally, it reflects on the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field developments (section 3.3).

3.2 Research design of each SIE-field comparison

Table 3 describes the research design for each SIE-field comparison before moving into the analysis of each SIE-field in section 3.3.

Table 3: Research question(s), conceptual framing and methodology

Name of SIE-field comparison	Research question(s) or aim(s)	Conceptual framing	Methodology
Cooperative organisation models for renewable energy (COOP RE) in France, Germany and Switzerland	The aim is to understand how the role of community renewable energy (CRE) intermediaries has evolved over time. The intermediary role has emerged from the need to manage tensions resulting from supporting diverse CRE initiatives and changing policy frameworks.	The work builds on the literature examining CRE intermediaries (Hargreaves et al., 2013; Warbroek et al., 2018) and outlining the theory of paradoxes (Smith and Lewis, 2011).	Mixed-methods research design based on three methods of data collection: an extended document and literature review, participation in online events and 24 semi-structured interviews with CRE initiatives and intermediaries.

⁵ We currently have published one of the papers and for three papers, we have a complete draft. See list in the appendix.

Name of SIE-field comparison	Research question(s) or aim(s)	Conceptual framing	Methodology
Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways (FAFF) in Netherlands, Poland and United Kingdom	This paper contributes to the literature on socio-technical transitions and discontinuities by a) illustrating the ways in which processes of scaling have played a role in the social mobilisation against fossil fuels and b) identifying different scalar practices over time.	We particularly focus on the concepts of scalar practices developed in geography (e.g. (Swyngedouw, 1996)) when examining the activities against fossil fuel energy pathways.	Mixed-methods research design based on three methods of data collection. Overall, we conducted 27 in-depth interviews, were part of nine online events and reviewed around 80 documents.
Local electricity exchange (LEE) in France, Switzerland and United Kingdom	The aim of the paper is to explore and compare the development of local electricity exchange in three European countries: France, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom.	This is an empirical exploratory study on local electricity exchange models/ approaches in three European countries with a focus on the development of policy frameworks, new business models and institutionalisation of the field.	Mixed-methods research design involving three methods of data collection: an extended document and literature review; 40 original semi-structured expert interviews; observational data from seven online meetings and events.
City level competition for sustainable energy (CLC) in France, Germany and Switzerland	The aim of the study is to understand the institutionalisation of the SIE-field city level competition for sustainable energy. In particular, it focusses on social innovation initiatives and key SIE-field actors' interactions over time.	The conceptual framework is based on the notion of social innovation, institutionalisation of the SIE-field and actor networks surrounding city level competition for sustainable energy.	Mixed-methods research design involving desk-based research, literature and document analysis and 22 interviews.
Participatory incubation and experimentation (PIE) in Netherlands, Germany, Poland	The aim is to better understand the role of policy in the emergence and development of the SIE-field in the Netherlands, Germany and Poland.	This is an empirical exploratory study of participatory incubation and experimentation in three European countries with a focus on the policy strategies and debates enabling and impeding the development of the SIE-field.	Mixed-methods research design involving three methods of data collection: an extended document and literature review; 20 semi-structured interviews; observational data from seven online meetings and events.
Financing and subsidies for RE (solar and wind) (FS RE) in Netherlands, Poland and United Kingdom	The aim of the paper is to explore the development of financing and subsidies for renewable energy and compare the recent history of solar and wind energy financing in three European countries.	This is an empirical exploratory study of subsidisation and financing for wind and solar in three European countries with a focus on the development of policy frameworks and institutionalisation of the field.	Mixed-methods research design involving three methods of data collection: document analysis, 22 original expert interviews, and observational data from eight meetings and events.

3.3 Deep dives into comparing each SIE-field across three countries

This section dives into a comparative analysis of each SIE-field across three SONNET countries, outlining key insights such as empirical phenomena surfacing in different cases and specific concepts that help to further the understanding of SIE. Each in their own way, these summaries of key findings are pertinent for building an understanding of each SIE-field across three countries. Some of the SIE-field comparisons are based on an abstract and discussion/ conclusion section of articles in preparation (see Appendix 2), whilst others summarise and compare key insights from the country reports (see D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021)).

3.3.1 SIE-field: Cooperative organisation models for renewable energy

This section builds on a paper manuscript written by Adélie Ranville, Anne-Lorène Vernay, Benjamin Schmid, Jasmin Heidary and Maria Stadler.

3.3.1.1 How do community renewable energy intermediaries cope with tensions? A comparative analysis in France, Germany and Switzerland

There is an increasing awareness that technological innovation alone will not be sufficient to enable a transition to a sustainable energy system. It is expected that social innovation in the form of new social configurations and governance models also have a role to play. Community renewable energy (CRE) organisations are one example of a social innovation that scholars expect to contribute to the energy transition. CRE represent a novel form of organisation in which citizens jointly own and participate in the governance of renewable energy production. A major continuing challenge in research on CRE organisations is to understand how CRE organisations can scale up and diffuse, thereby fulfilling their potential to contribute to the energy transition.

Previous research stressed the importance of intermediaries in supporting the diffusion of CRE organisations, even when these organisations had limited access to resources and operated in an unsupportive institutional environment. According to the literature, intermediaries can be very diverse and are defined based on the activities and/or roles they fulfil. Literature identifies at least five roles: facilitating by providing knowledge, skills and confidence; creating an institutional infrastructure; framing and coordinating; brokering by creating links between CRE organisations, with private firms and/or public authorities; and configuring by supporting business model innovation. Previous studies also pinpoint the difficulties faced by CRE intermediaries in fulfilling these roles, not least because CRE organisations encompass very diverse and decentralised initiatives, partly since institutional contexts have been changing and unstable. Little research has been done to analyse how CRE intermediaries can cope with these challenges of supporting such diverse CRE organisations and provide adequate support.

This article contributes to previous research by conducting a comparative longitudinal analysis of CRE organisations and intermediaries in three European countries: France, Germany and

Switzerland. We investigate the evolving role and structure of CRE intermediaries from the moment when CRE organisations started to emerge until 2020. We observe that CRE intermediaries have to deal with three main tensions: standardisation vs innovation, local vs national, and inclusivity vs gatekeeping. We explain how CRE intermediaries cope with these tensions as CRE organisations mature and as the institutional environment evolves.

3.3.1.2 Discussion/Conclusions

The article analyses the role played by CRE intermediaries over time. It specifically focuses on intermediary organisations that have been created by CRE from the bottom up, and national organisations that decided to represent the interest of CRE. The comparative longitudinal analysis of CRE in France, Germany and Switzerland confirmed that CRE intermediaries play an important role in enabling the emergence and development of CRE organisations (Hargreaves et al., 2013; Warbroek et al., 2018). The analysis also confirmed that CRE intermediaries have to deal with a number of constraints that limit what they can achieve (Hargreaves et al., 2013). For instance, CRE intermediaries often depend on volunteers to conduct their activities. Moreover, they constantly have to deal with changing policy frameworks, which demand CRE intermediaries to evolve.

Because of these constraints, CRE intermediaries have to choose which activities to prioritise. We observed that in doing so, they also had to cope with three types of tensions. The first tension concerns standardisation vs innovation. Standardisation refers to CRE intermediaries providing knowledge and developing tools to facilitate the creation and daily operational activities of CRE organisations. Innovation instead refers to CRE intermediaries providing support for CRE to innovate by imagining new business models and/ or diversifying their activities. The second tension concerns the foci of the activities of intermediaries and whether it should be local or national. CRE intermediaries can focus on providing support to CRE locally by helping them in their daily activities. CRE intermediaries may also decide to develop actions at the national level in order to advocate for more favourable institutional frameworks. The third tension concerns how CRE intermediaries cope with the diversity behind CRE organisation. On the one hand, they may be inclusive and cherish diversity, with the risk that what constitutes a CRE becomes blurred. On the other hand, they may do some gatekeeping in order to have a clear definition of what a CRE is, with the risk of excluding initiatives that may contribute to the CRE movement.

When comparing how CRE intermediaries cope with these tensions over time in the three countries, we observed some similarities and some differences. Regarding standardisation vs innovation, we observed that CRE intermediaries in all three countries have a strong focus on standardisation. They develop tools, standard contracts and procedures to help CRE develop and to facilitate their activities at a very operational level. In both Germany and Switzerland, CRE intermediaries also provide knowledge and support to help CRE innovate and use new business models such as collective self-consumption. In France, the focus on standardisation clearly results from a policy framework that was very constraining to CRE. In Switzerland, however, the focus on standardisation results more from the fact that CRE intermediaries have to show they can be useful for CRE. This is because CRE organisations have been operating for a long time in the country, and interviews revealed that CRE organisations do not always see the need for external support derived from intermediaries.

Regarding local vs national, we observed that CRE intermediaries mainly started at the local level in France and Germany, the initial focus clearly being about helping CRE to emerge. As CRE organisations matured, CRE intermediaries in both countries decided to set up actions at the national level, because at this level that they could advocate for more enabling policy frameworks. However, we also observed some differences in how they do that. For instance, in Germany CRE intermediaries active at the national level are distinct from the ones active at a local and/or regional level; this is not the case in France, where the same intermediaries are active at both levels. In Switzerland, while some regional CRE intermediaries exist, their role seems less critical than in France and Germany. Other important intermediaries have derived from nationally established actors that represent the solar technology sector, which includes but is not limited to cooperatives. This explains why these organisations have always been organised and operating at the national level.

Regarding inclusivity vs gatekeeping, we observed that CRE intermediaries in Germany and Switzerland both adopt an inclusive approach. In both countries, the cooperative model is well institutionalised and provides clear guidelines under which CRE can operate. In France, however, it is not possible to operate a CRE under the cooperative status. CRE have to decide under which organisational model and governance principles they would like to operate. We have observed a lot of gatekeeping surrounding debates about the criteria an initiative should meet to be recognised as a CRE. This can be explained by the fact that CRE intermediaries feel the need for CRE to gain recognition from national institutions.

3.3.2 SIE-field: Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways

This section builds on a paper manuscript written by Sabine Hielscher, Julia Wittmayer and Ala Dankowska.

3.3.2.1 Social mobilisation in energy transitions: Examining scalar practices in contested fossil fuel energy pathways in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland

Pathways towards low-carbon energy transformations have become a priority in the European Union in the 21st century. The commitment to lowering carbon dioxide emissions has triggered changes to current fossil fuel-based energy systems within energy transitions alongside other changes such as the expansion of renewable electricity generation. Over the past decade, fossil fuel energy pathways have been characterised by closures of sites, continued extractions and new explorations, demonstrating processes of (dis)continuation. This paper contributes to the literature on sociotechnical transitions and discontinuities by drawing on case study work in which we trace the social mobilisation against onshore oil, gas and coal projects in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland over the past ten years. The role of social mobilisations within the (dis)continuation of fossil fuel energy pathways and scalar practices in energy transitions have remained relatively underexplored in energy transitions. Our analysis demonstrates how decision-making powers and possibilities for scrutinising fossil fuels are negotiated between local and central government, local communities and residents, grassroots movements, national NGOs, and fossil fuel industries. We conclude that all actors are involved in scalar practices, but that anti-fossil energy pathways will remain challenging if government and

industry actors keep trying to displace the politics linked to fossil fuel energy through these practices.

3.3.2.2 Discussion/Conclusions

To build an understanding of the role of social mobilisation within the (dis)continuation of fossil fuel energy pathways, we illustrate the ways in which scalar practices have played a role in the social mobilisation against fossil fuels in Europe over time.

“Such [scalar] practices include state-driven attempts to rescale governance; examples of actors using scalar discourses about the local or the global; or cases of social movement activism which deliberate over and target particular scales of action. Human actors whether individuals, social groups, or governing bodies (such as governments or state agencies) ‘produce’ and use’ scale in all manner of attempts to create some sort of advantage, to establish associations, connections, or solidarities across social divides, or to represent their interests (to be heard or seen) amidst oppressive or otherwise difficult conditions” (Fraser, 2009:332).

For example, Brown and Spiegel (2017:102) have pointed out that *“coal extraction is negotiated and contested at different scales, emphasising how regional histories and development trajectories intersect with transnational concerns to shape the contours of protest”*. Thus, we examine how scale operates as a category of practice amongst other spatial practices enacted by state institutions, social movements, etc. involved in (anti) fossil fuel energy pathways. We particularly focus on scalar practices linked to contested fossil fuel energy pathways in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland.

Our findings show that scalar practices are performed by actors and groups that are part of social mobilisations against fossil fuels, and actors who support the continuation of fossil fuel exploration and extraction projects. Actors and groups that conduct continuation activities work for national governments, fossil fuel industries, law enforcement agencies and/or journalists. They are often entangled with social mobilisations that form a direct response to these continuation activities. For example, in the United Kingdom, NGOs, local groups and grassroots networks came together as part of the Let Communities Decide campaign following the government’s 2018 proposal to allow shale gas companies to undertake exploratory drilling without local planning applications (i.e. no longer needing local approval).

Based on our research, we have found that scalar practices linked to continuation activities have: a) changed the scope for nongovernmental actors (e.g. civil society groups) to get involved in and/or intervene in policy processes; b) tried to break up contestations through giving legitimacy to protesters (or not) based on people’s geographical location (e.g. living local to extraction sites (or not)); c) tried to ‘contain’ the spatial extensions of the debates beyond the local; d) discursively broadened the assumed benefits of fossil fuel exploration and extraction projects to diverse set of actors. These scalar practices demonstrate that activities against fossil fuels remain challenging if government and industry actors do not link the impacts of projects to existing climate change goals. Nyberg (2018) has argued that *“scaling allows dominant actors to uphold contradictory positions on climate change, which contributes to explaining the current disastrous political climate impasse”* (Nyberg et al., 2018:235). For example, the United Kingdom government has set

ambitious targets in their Climate Change Act but were still hugely supportive of the shale gas industry, upholding its position for several years.

Looking across the scalar practices linked to fossil fuel continuation activities, it becomes apparent that national governments, industry actors, fossil fuel lobbies and some journalists supportive of exploration and extraction projects needed to perform several scalar practices to support, continue and expand fossil fuel projects. Scalar practices linked to continuation activities have not always achieved wished for results. As pointed out by Goodwin, Jones and Jones (2012), processes of scaling adopted to solve, manage and/ or contain the politics linked to contestations can entail unintended consequences. “*Politics returns through multiple other channels*” (Johnstone, 2014:69), by responding (directly) to scalar practices conducted by actors, who support the extraction of fossil fuels. Scalar practices linked to discontinuation activities have: a) pointed to the procedural injustices and lack of democratic accountability linked to fossil fuel projects; b) broadened contestations around fossil fuels beyond local concerns and discourses; c) provided legitimisation to actions and activities locally and nationally and empowered social mobilisations in legal, political, financial and symbolic ways; d) broadened the scale and scope of fossil fuel contestations by linking them to wider social and environmental issues and movements; e) started institutionalisation processes that make use of climate change issues and targets to stop existing and future projects through court cases and planning application processes. Looking across these scalar practices, it is possible to argue that although continuation activities have ‘controlled’ some discontinuation activities, the politics surrounding fossil fuel exploration and extraction have continued through multiple other ways (as seen in the scalar practices linked to discontinuation activities).

3.3.3 SIE-field: Local electricity exchange

This section builds on a paper manuscript written by Marfuga Iskandarova, Anne-Lorène Vernay, Jörg Musiolik, Leticia Müller and Benjamin K. Sovacool,

3.3.3.1 Tangled transitions: Exploring the emergence of local electricity exchange in three European countries

Major societal trends associated with digitisation, decentralisation, and democratisation are being heralded by many as revolutionising the future of the energy and electricity sectors. Such dynamics are often praised for their ability to empower consumers and benefit communities. But how have they been occurring in practice? In this paper, we explore the development of local electricity exchange in three European countries: France, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. We first briefly define and conceptualise local electricity exchange and peer-to-peer markets before explicating our mixed-methods research design consisting of document analysis, 40 original expert interviews across the three countries, and observational data derived from seven meetings and events. These comparative cases reveal the complexity and variation of local electricity exchange markets across our three national contexts; how such acts of decentralisation in turn (and perhaps unexpectedly) consolidate power among incumbent actors; and how local electricity exchanges are prone to significant contestation and disagreement. We conclude with future insights for both research and policy.

3.3.3.2 Discussion/Conclusions

Local electricity exchange and peer-to-peer trading have been heralded (by some) as means of community empowerment, and even social change, for their ability to involve non-traditional actors in the electricity market such as local authorities, community groups and citizens/prosumers. However, our study finds that the results of such actions are often unclear and complex, being tangled with patterns of incumbency and substantial areas of community contestation. The emergence of new (multi-actor) alliances because of increased collaboration between public, private and community actors is certainly occurring.

Although local electricity exchange, local energy markets (LEM) and peer-to-peer trading rely on multi-actor collaborations, they must work closely with incumbents. For most community actors and local authorities, partnerships with energy supply companies and distribution system operators (DSOs) would be essential for implementing local electricity exchange models.

Local electricity exchange varies across national contexts and is strongly linked with institutional frameworks (such as regulations and social norms). These frameworks can make it very difficult for projects to be financially sustainable: collective self-consumption initiatives often depend on regional subsidies to be realised, and the absence of these makes it difficult to fully experiment with and learn from operational projects. These frameworks are also unstable, with legal frameworks constantly being negotiated and challenged by different configurations of actors.

The future merits of local electricity exchange are therefore highly uncertain. Reforms in market arrangements (the development of DSOs and new flexibility markets) may create an environment more conducive to peer-to-peer solutions.

Local energy has some economic and environmental benefits that cannot be ignored, and one of the reasons for people to support local energy is arguably the benefits for the wider community as well as individuals. Nevertheless, considerable uncertainty exists concerning local electricity exchange markets of the future; their viability is yet to be proven and investments are needed for the realisation of projects. Many of these projects are being developed by community organisations which rely on volunteers and have some social goals, e.g. alleviating fuel poverty in their community; they are not purely commercial propositions, and the complexities of government policy can be a serious obstacle for them. In such contexts, the promise of local electricity exchange may be elusive.

3.3.4 SIE-field: City level competition for sustainable energy

3.3.4.1 Summary of key insights

City level energy competitions for sustainable energy (CLC) refer to diverse formats in which participants strive to rank themselves, gain or win something in order to foster sustainable energy pathways. There are different formats of competition being considered, namely, competition 'between cities' and competition 'within cities'. These formats can address changes within city administrations (e.g. in 'between city competitions') or target changes of individual behaviour (e.g. in 'within city' competitions, which take place within cities between different stakeholder

groups). Both formats apply a competitive approach to promote and mainstream sustainable energy consumption and production pathways.

CLC is socially innovative because it involves: a) new ideas, as formats are striving towards being engaging; b) changing social relations, as initiatives are actively trying to include new actor groups; c) encouraging participants to change the ways they 'do' and 'think' about energy; d) shaping local energy politics through changing how cities 'organise' sustainable energy pathways and how municipalities relate to each other. Furthermore, CLC might also include new objects such as the development of digital applications, tools or platforms that help to carry out the competition.

CLC is seen as a rather heterogeneous field with a broad scope of actors in all three countries. It includes a variety of activities carried out by different actors such as city administrations, NGOs or intermediaries like semi-public research institutes. New actor groups are getting engaged in developing games and competition formats. Civil society actors, private initiatives as well as city administrations are taking new forms of responsibility.

The SIE-field is characterised by a very specific combination of informal, formal and semi-formal relations between SIE-field-actors. There are many interactions between actors across national boundaries, given that between city competition is often framed as European challenges. The interactions/ relations between SIE-field-actors are based on 'organising' as the most important type of activity and 'competition' as the most important aspect of social relations among SIE-field-actors and other field-actors, but this can vary depending on national context. It was noted that in Germany the character of these competitions largely varies depending on the format of the competition and the actors involved. Competitions between cities can often take a more competitive character, with each city seeking recognition and funding. In contrast to competitions between cities, within-city competitions in Germany are characterised by a cooperative and playful mood rather than by competitiveness between participants. Cooperation is also a feature of CLC in Switzerland. While competition was used as an important motivating factor to participate in the Swiss EnergieStadt label (a label for cities who have achieved specific energy and climate change goals), once cities and municipalities became part of the label, they primarily relate to each other through cooperation.

The SIE-field is more institutionalised in Switzerland and less so in Germany and France. In the latter two countries the city competition formats seem to have emerged out of existing institutional structures, as the aim is to develop more flexible engagements of diverse groups. Institutional work for CLC across all three countries focusses on creating new institutions/ institutional structures and transforming institutions. This mainly involves activities of relational work, like networking and knowledge exchange. Actors contribute to creating institutions by establishing new competition formats (which serve as networking platforms, connect projects and people and inspire learning) and creating new networks between cities. Policy actors also do 'political work' for creating institutions by reconstructing the rules under which CLC-initiatives operate (e.g. in Switzerland, by embedding the EnergieStadt initiative into the larger federal Energy 2000 programme supporting energy efficiency and renewable energy sources). At the same time, institutional work also relates to maintaining institutions, which is manifested in existing responsibilities and power relations limiting changes in actor relations.

Institutional work in the SIE-field is influenced by several factors such as societal trends, urban governance structures and the availability of resources, which can create enabling and impeding conditions. For example, scarce resources can impede the participation in competition formats, but on the other hand, the prospects of financial awards can be an important motivation to participate in competitions.

3.3.5 SIE-field: Participatory incubation and experimentation

3.3.5.1 Summary of key insights

The SIE-field PIE describes novel collaborations between different types of actors with the aim of finding formats to test, experiment with and learn about diverse socio-technical solutions to address energy-related issues. These socio-technical solutions may involve new technologies and/ or new ways of thinking and organising, such as new modes of governance or business models; in either case, collaboration between different types of actors makes PIE a form of social innovation. This section discusses how policy may enable or impede the emergence and development of PIE by comparing case studies on PIE in Germany, the Netherlands and Poland. Policy has played an important role in enabling the development of the SIE-field by, for example, changing thinking, creating spaces and providing resources to support the participation of different actors in PIE. Conversely, policy can impede PIE development by resisting new ways of thinking or allocating responsibilities without appropriate resources. Here, policy refers to the mixture of policy strategies and specific instruments, as well as broader political debates, across different governance levels and policy fields (Wittmayer et al., 2020).

Policy debates, strategies and instruments at different levels of governance can enable the development of PIE by changing thinking about which energy issues are important, how they might be addressed, and which types of actors should participate in this. For example, in Poland the need to comply with EU policy has played a decisive role in changing thinking about energy, starting to move towards the diversification of energy mix and mobilising public support for renewables. Energy clusters (introduced in 2016 as units for the generation and balancing of energy from renewables or other sources within a local distribution network) can be seen as the Polish version of energy communities. In the Polish context, dominated by centralised coal fired electricity generation, this way of thinking is highly innovative. Prior to this, localised EU funded projects involving municipalities and NGOs introduced the idea that citizens and civil society can be active participants in the energy transition. However, this thinking has so far not manifested at the national level, with the development of energy clusters focussing on technological innovation and triple helix collaborations among state, business and academic actors.

Similarly, in Germany and the Netherlands international discourses such as the UN Brundtland report and Agenda 21 influenced thinking about the need for transdisciplinary research and collaboration between different types of actors to address sustainability issues. National R&D policies have played an important role in shaping how such ideas relate to PIE in energy. In the Netherlands, a long history of policy support for triple helix collaborations has contributed to strongly institutionalise thinking that state, business and academic actors are those who should participate in PIE around energy. More recently, moves towards alternative PIE formats such as living labs, which explicitly include users or citizens, have contributed to these dominant ideas

being partly contested. Energy policy in Germany has similarly focussed on technological development, but in the past years national policies in support of Reallabore ('real life laboratories') have contributed to institutionalise the idea that citizens and municipalities can also play an important role.

Beyond influencing thinking, policy can enable SIE-field development linked to PIE by creating spaces for actors to take on new roles, and providing support through appropriate regulation, funding, and access to social resources. Some roles require specific regulatory changes: for example, regulatory changes in the Netherlands and Poland have been designed to enable new types of actors to participate in locally trading electricity. Broader policy debates and strategies can also create roles and responsibilities for different kinds of actors in experimenting with energy solutions. For example, following the 2008 financial crisis the Netherlands saw a discourse around greater citizen participation alongside the decentralisation of certain responsibilities to local government. This made space for the participation of municipalities, citizens and civil society actors in this SIE-field.

Finally, providing access to financial and social resources is an important way in which policy can enable the SIE-field development. Policy can provide different types of actors with access to relevant knowledge, and networks that enable collaboration and continued learning over time, for example by sharing learning between localised, short-term projects. In the Polish case, municipality involvement can also increase SIE-initiatives' legitimacy. Meanwhile, access to funding is generally important to enable concrete actions by SIE-field-actors involved in PIE. The three country cases include only one example where PIE activities were financed by other means (crowdsourced funding for an experimental eco-village in Poland), and policies with dedicated funding streams (typically national R&D and environmental policies) tend to dominate the development of the SIE-field. As noted with regards to the German case, "*even if the SIE-field is based on bottom-up attempts, major shifts mainly occurred when large scale funding programmes picked up participatory multi-actors' formats in their research programmes and provided funding*" (PIE, Germany).

The most obvious ways in which policy may impede the development of PIE relate to unclear or incomplete regulation, and insufficient access to funding or social resources, which impede SIE-field-actors from adopting or developing their new roles. For example, in both Poland and the Netherlands regulatory changes enabled new actors to participate in electricity trading as part of experimental formats but did *not* change regulation on the grid operator to require them to cooperate; in practice, this made local electricity trading close to impossible. Other than regulatory inconsistencies, an absence of either financial or social resources can impede action by SIE-field-actors. In Poland, attention has turned to learning about which legal, organisational, and technological supports might be necessary for the energy clusters to meet their aim of energy self-sufficiency. Meanwhile, in the Netherlands regulatory changes which enabled new actors to engage in electricity trading were not accompanied by sufficient financial or social support (such as access to knowledge and networks for sharing learning).

The design of funding programmes can also impede SIE-field development. A common issue is that funding for PIE is often relatively short term, which can impede the ability of SIE-field-actors to engage with activities and particularly to carry learning forwards. In Germany, the involvement of academic actors in PIE provides a network by which learning can be transferred between

different projects, but this does raise questions about whether the learning most relevant to all SIE-field-actors is being carried forwards. Funding structures can also influence which actors are involved in PIE and the aims they pursue. For example, in Germany national funding streams have typically been awarded to only formalised institutions and actors, while in the Netherlands some funding schemes require co-funding by participants, which might inhibit the involvement of actors such as energy co-operatives with less access to finance. Furthermore, the traditional emphasis on triple helix collaborations and technological innovation may lead to civil society or municipal actors mimicking aspects of this dominant format with the aim of increasing their access to funds.

Finally, while policy can be important to influence thinking about who can collaborate in PIE and with what purpose, strongly established visions and practices of PIE within policy can also impede the development of PIE in new directions. This phenomenon is particularly emphasised within the Dutch case, since in the Netherlands triple helix models of collaboration focussing on technological innovation and economic growth are strongly established and have persisted over time. This has been associated with the early influence of large incumbent actors, such as Shell, in SIE-field development, which meant the ambition to include civil society actors in transition experiments was not realised. More recently, activities within living labs and other PIE formats have generated new ideas about who can collaborate in PIE and for what purpose; however, it is not yet clear that these will be able to compete with the dominant model. The difficulty for alternative models of PIE to attract adequate funding and other resources can also make it difficult for these SIE-field-actors to engage in institutional work in order to change this situation.

By contrast, both the Polish and German cases include examples of PIE development where policy has actively learned from developments at the local level. In Poland, two nationally funded programmes have been launched to learn about necessary conditions to support the development of energy clusters and to share knowledge across local and national levels (although this arguably represents single loop learning and does not include citizens or civil society in PIE). In Germany, the concept of Reallabore was adopted by national policy drawing on experiments that started up in one region in Germany (i.e. BaWü Labs). The move towards including citizen voices was a reaction to civil resistance to particular technologies (e.g. smart meters and onshore wind farms). Nonetheless, the Reallabore concept includes citizens in identifying relevant problems as well as solutions, and has potential to both single and double loop learning within policy practices although it has been difficult to involve policy makers directly in experimental settings to date.

To conclude, PIE by definition involves the participation of new types of actors in new roles; as such, policy plays an important role in creating cognitive, regulatory and organisational spaces for new actors to engage with energy systems in new ways, and to enable this action through funding and social resources. The SIE-field development will be impeded if policy creates rights or responsibilities without providing appropriate, coherent support, including access to longer term funding and/or social networks which enable learning to be carried forward. However, actors who attract more recognition may also attract greater policy support, which in turn enables institutional work by these actors and consolidates their position. This suggests that in addition to providing structure and support, policy should seek to actively learn from and respond to innovative PIE activities at the local level in order to enable SIE-field development to the fullest extent by including diverse actors and topics.

3.3.6 SIE-field: Financing and subsidies for renewable energy (solar and wind)⁶

This section builds on a paper manuscript written by Marfuga Iskandarova, Agata Dembek, Maria Fraaije, William Matthews, Agata Stasik, Julia M. Wittmayer and Benjamin K. Sovacool.

3.3.6.1 Who finances renewable energy in Europe? Examining temporality, authority and contestation in solar and wind subsidies in Poland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom

In this paper, we explore the development of financing and subsidies for renewable energy in three fossil-fuelled European countries: Poland, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom. Financing for renewable energy is an existing arena involving multi-actor activities and practices that develop and implement (innovative) financial instruments to facilitate investments in renewable energy. This means that the paper focuses on different financial mechanisms – such as grants, awards, subsidies, crowdfunding, community bonds, ventures, social investment, as long as these funding instruments finance sustainable energy infrastructure and activities. The extent to which this is changing social relations and comes with new ways of doing, thinking and/or organizing is an empirical topic explicitly examined in the study. We first briefly define and conceptualize financial mechanisms and subsidies before explicating our mixed methods research design consisting of scoping, document analysis, 22 original expert interviews, and observational data from eight meetings and events. We then compare the recent history of solar and wind energy financing and subsidies in our three countries. These comparative cases reveal the temporality of subsidization, indicating fundamental changes in the patterns and logics of financing over the past two decades. They reveal shifts in authority and an expansion of actors involved in financing. They lastly reveal tensions and contestations in financing, including gaps in coverage and conflicts among stakeholder groups. We conclude with future insights for renewable energy diffusion, innovation, and policy.

3.3.6.2 Discussion/Conclusions

Our comparative, mixed-methods assessment of financing and subsidies for renewable energy in three European countries yields fruitful insights concerning renewable energy, innovation, and policy.

First, the trends behind financial mechanisms for renewable energy are both complicated and fast moving. It is not only technological parameters and balance of system costs for wind and solar that are dramatically changing; the field of how such technologies are financed is complex and constituted by a number of sub-fields and institutions concerned with changing social relations in connection to financing of wind and solar that can be part of other fields, i.e.

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'municipal energy'; 'community energy'; 'investment-based crowdfunding'; 'institutional investment in green infrastructure'; 'corporate' and 'private wire' power purchase agreements (PPAs). Although some discuss how subsidies can impede innovation, in our cases subsidies represent more enabling than impeding factors. This finding also resonates strongly with global trends in renewable energy financing, where capital markets, bonds, and other financial institutions are beginning to invest in the sector (and divest from other sectors, notably fossil fuels). In simpler terms: the diversity of financing instruments and increase in financing volumes are commensurate with global goals of decarbonization and climate change mitigation.

Secondly, our analysis reveals important patterns of innovation. Our cases show not only traditional financial mechanisms employed for the new goal, that is, enabling newcomers to conduct investment in renewable energy and thus engage in energy transitions, but also entirely new, innovative, market-based financial mechanisms. Subsidies and preferential loans are used to develop and support new energy sources, and to enable new actors to get involved in energy production. Their innovativeness resides in the creation of a more dispersed and decentralized energy system. For instance, their prevalence in Poland results from a relative underdevelopment of the field (compared to NL and UK case studies), relatively low level of financial saturation and, above all, still quite restricted regulatory conditions in the Polish energy sector. Moreover, new financial mechanisms are challenging normative and cognitive institutions around renewable energy generation – their institutionalization is germinating into 'social standards' that seek to address the social dilemma of climate change mitigation. This form of institutionalization allows for legitimization of new actors participating in financing renewable energy (citizens, local authorities), making them more accepted and trusted by incumbents.

Third, determining the effectiveness of any particular set of financial mechanisms is difficult not only due to the complexity of establishing causality between a mechanism and diffusion (because the timing of many mechanisms overlaps); but also due to national variation in terms of financing over time; shifting control and ownership; and tension and contestation in financing pathways. The efficacy of financial mechanisms in this way depends on maturation and cost of technology, but also wider institutional context (e.g. market-based economy vs transition economy). It is determined partly by technology, partly by institutions, partly by policy, and partly by country context.

Fourth, and lastly, our studies offer insight for policymaking and regulation. The available forms of financial mechanisms in our three European countries are strongly dependent on state policy and specific legislation. This means that the ability for actors other than the state to create transformative change throughout the financial sphere is limited, i.e. power is more constrained and circumscribed. State planners and government bodies often have direct control over public funds and different forms of public subsidies and loans. Indirectly, policymakers influence renewable energy finance by shaping organisational aspects of renewable energy (e.g. regulating energy co-ops) or setting the rules for the financial market (e.g. around tax relief/venture capital schemes). The involvement in developing innovative financial mechanisms often demands institutional work, such as pioneering new practices, lobbying and campaigning for/against relevant policy and regulation. In this way, the institutional environment and its governance dynamics can be just as important as the specific technology being subsidized, or the particular forms of innovation being harnessed.

3.4 Concluding reflections on enabling and impeding factors for the development of SIE-fields and their SIE

These concluding reflections are based on examining the enabling and impeding factors for SIE derived from the comparative analysis of six SIE-fields⁷ presented above.

- ✦ Intermediaries have generally played a key role in supporting SIE-initiatives and therefore the development of SIE-fields. They can play diverse roles, from providing networking opportunities to advocating for policy change. Still, combining and managing all these roles has not always been straightforward. As highlighted as part of the cooperative organisation models for renewable energy (COOP RE) analysis, several tensions can emerge that intermediaries need to balance to create an enabling environment for SIE. Several impeding factors exist for intermediaries to conduct their roles, such as frequently changing policy environments within which SIE-initiatives and intermediaries try to carry out their work.
- ✦ Regarding framings against fossil fuel energy pathways (FAFF) in all three countries - the Netherlands, Poland and the United Kingdom (and particularly Poland) - EU policies have enabled SIE-initiatives to gain legitimacy and begin to institutionalise some activities to discontinue fossil fuels. In addition, FAFF has been supported by networking across country borders and different anti-fossil fuel activities; in turn, this has been linked to movements such as Fridays for Future and Extinction Rebellion. Nevertheless, national governments and industry actors have been busy trying to 'control' social mobilisations against fossil fuel based on several practices such as regulating protests and stressing the importance of fossil fuel for electricity production and energy security.
- ✦ Emerging SIE-fields such as local electricity exchange (LEE) have been constrained by existing institutional environments, in particular regulations and existing policy frameworks. The creation of experimental spaces to temporarily lift such constraints (for example, as part of incubators in the United Kingdom) has helped SIE developments, but often resources are still missing to sustain experimental projects. The future pathways of LEE are unclear, seeing that the benefits, direction and content of LEE are still emerging. Broader societal trends towards the digitalisation of energy systems have and might still support LEE developments. The main question might be who will shape and organise these developments and for whose benefit.
- ✦ The emergence and development of the SIE-field city level competition for sustainable energy (CLC) shows how important networking and learning processes have been for enabling SIE. The set up and implementation of formats have more often been framed by cooperation, rather than competition, in the aim to move towards low carbon energy futures. Cities have been able to learn from each other about formats and processes (also

⁷ SIE-fields: Cooperative organisation models for renewable energy (COOP RE); Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways (FAFF); Local electricity exchange (LEE); City level competition for sustainable energy (CLC); Participatory incubation and experimentation (PIE); Financing and subsidies for renewable energy (solar and wind) (FS RE).

through already existing networks). In particular, some EU initiatives have enabled developments in Germany and France by providing an institutional background for some of these activities. The lack of resources (such as time and money) has often impeded developments.

- ▲ As part of the SIE-field participatory incubation and experimentation (PIE), we investigated the role of policy in enabling and impeding the development of the SIE-field and its SIE. Policy has played an important role in enabling the development of the SIE-field by, for example, changing thinking, creating spaces for actors to take new roles, develop regulations that support SIE-field developments and providing resources to support the participation of different actors in PIE. Conversely, policy has impeded the development of the SIE-field PIE by resisting new ways of thinking derived from multi-actor collaborations, incomplete regulations and/or allocating responsibilities without appropriate resources, which impede SIE-field-actors from adopting or developing their new roles. The SIE-field development will be impeded if policy creates responsibilities for actors without providing appropriate, coherent support, including access to longer term funding and/or social networks which enable learning to be carried forward.
- ▲ Work on the SIE-field financing and subsidies for renewable energy (FS RE) has shown the key role of policy and legislation for SIE. They have direct impacts in the case of financial mechanisms using public funds, such as renewable energy auction mechanisms, net-metering, and different forms of public subsidies and loans. In the case of innovative forms of financing (such as crowdfunding) created by entrepreneurs and social entrepreneurs, the impact of legislation is also very strong: as the energy sector is highly regulated, regulations influence which actions and associated financial models are possible and profitable. Impediments to innovations and SIE have therefore often derived from rigid norms, beliefs and regulations.

Considering that the above points are based on a focused (rather than systematic) thematic analysis of each SIE-field, they do not represent a complete list of enabling and impeding factors for the development of SIE-fields and their SIE.

4 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF 18 CASE STUDIES

4.1 Introduction

The SONNET project makes use of an embedded case study approach to develop an understanding of the diversity, processes and contributions of SIE. This section provides key highlights from the comparative analysis of the SIE-fields (and their SIE-initiatives), based on the total of 18 embedded case studies across all six SONNET countries (i.e. 3 per country). Altogether, 36 case studies of SIE-initiatives are nested within the SIE-field investigations: on average 2 per SIE-field and 6 per country (see Table 1 for the list of country reports and case study reports). For this section, the comparative analysis of the case studies has been guided by the SONNET WP3 research questions: How do SIEs and SIE-fields emerge, develop, and institutionalise over time? How do SIE-field-actors and other field-actors interact with the ‘outside’ institutional environment and thereby co-shape the SIE-field over time? What are the enabling and impeding factors for SIE-field-actors and other field-actors to conduct institutional work and change the ‘outside’ institutional environment? While the analysis in section 3 was mainly based on inductive thematic analysis of case studies, for this section we carried out a deductive thematic analysis based on the research questions and conceptual work (see D1.2, Wittmayer et al., 2020).

This section begins by describing the methodological approach for the comparative analysis across all 18 SIE-field case studies (section 4.2). It then compares SIE-fields (section 4.3), and outlines working proposition based on the comparative analysis of SIE-fields (section 4.4).

4.2 Methodology of case comparison

This section describes the methodology for the cross-case analysis. The methodology for each individual case study is outlined in each country report and case study report (see D3.2, Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021). This section focuses on the methods used for the comparative analysis of the 18 case studies.

4.2.1 Steps of the cross-case analysis and analytical strategies

One of the key challenges for conducting and writing up the case studies was the aim of producing reports that could be used for a cross-case analysis of SIE-fields (their SIE-initiatives and SIE), i.e. creating comparable cases. As argued by Jorgensen et al. (2016:22), it is important to follow certain methodological steps and make particular choices to *“balance uniformity and attentiveness to case particularities and to ensure similarities and differences between cases can be systematically analysed”*. The following steps and analytical strategies have been followed to conduct the cross-case analysis.

4.2.1.1 Step 1: Harmonising case study approach and conduction

To be able to create comparable, embedded cases across the six country research teams, the following steps and approaches were outlined in the methodological guidelines (see D3.1, Hielscher et al., 2020):

- ▲ An overall conceptual map and narrative
- ▲ Major and minor research questions
- ▲ Selection of case studies (i.e. SIE-fields) to be studied and sampling strategy for the selection of SIE-initiatives
- ▲ Demarcation of the cases, i.e. boundaries of the SIE-fields
- ▲ Use of methods (including interview topic guide and sampling strategies)
- ▲ Outline of case study analysis (including structure of case study report and country report)

The template for the case study and country report were updated a few months into the work. In addition, a coding structure for the case analysis was provided. Although these guidelines supported the case collection and analysis, researchers had liberty to sample interviewees and documents, and explore relevant analytical themes in greater depth, among other things.

The demarcation of the SIE-fields continued after the submission of deliverable D1.3 (Hielscher et al., 2020), through several calls between SIE-field teams (each made up of researchers from three countries). Each SIE-field team conducted some initial research into the SIE-field in their own country and shared some of the findings with the rest of the team. The aim was to give an initial 'picture' of the SIE-field within each country to be able to more clearly demarcate the boundaries for each SIE-field. Then, a short description of each SIE-field and definition of the SIE was written up, including some key considerations for defining its boundaries and the period in which the historical narrative of each SIE-field was to be re-traced. Some of the SIE-field teams continued conversations throughout the fieldwork to 'check-in' whether boundaries have been followed and/or needed to be re-drawn. As part of two SIE-fields (LEE and FS RE), the boundaries were re-designed during the fieldwork to make the conduction of the case study work more manageable.

Finally, monthly WP3 working group meetings were conducted to discuss open issues as they arose whilst conducting the fieldwork. Moreover, SIE-field teams were able to hear how other teams were tracing the boundaries of the SIE-fields and conducting the embedded case studies.

4.2.1.2 Step 2: Condensing single case studies

Each country team analysed and wrote up each case study (three in total per country). This was based on developing a historical narrative of the SIE-field and its SIE-initiatives that made use of the template for the case study report. An additional case study summary was produced in the form of a country report, which synthesised findings from the three case studies and answered the major and minor research questions for WP3. These country-based summaries helped to focus the analysis of the case studies along SONNET's conceptual map. The case studies and country reports make up D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021).

4.2.1.3 Step 3: Extracting and synthesising across the 18 case studies

Most of the case study reports (including key findings, historical narrative, conclusions and methodology) are around 60-100 pages long. Finding ways to extract information that could be analysed in more depth was therefore a key step in preparing the comparative analysis. The case study summaries (included in the country report) provided a good starting point to initiate the cross-case analysis. In addition, the conceptual and empirical reflections included as boxes in each case study report were used to deepen the analysis of specific themes (such as policy developments and definition of SIE). In addition, SONNET's conceptual map (see Figure 1) and research questions provided a starting point to focus our comparative analysis.

4.2.1.4 Step 4: Analytical strategies to conduct cross-case analysis

The comparative analysis has taken inspiration from two main 'techniques': finding patterns and the critical turning point approach. We took the SONNET research questions and conceptual map (see Figure 1) as a starting point to develop deductive themes, before analysing the case studies to see what types of patterns emerged surrounding these themes. Below is a summary of the approaches:

Emergent patterns: The technique of pattern matching is a key advantage of the case study method (e.g. Collier, 1993). After the cases have been reviewed and/or coded for themes, the case study analyst looks for patterns within and across cases. As part of this process, the researchers determine whether any content of the themes differs (or not) across the case studies. Conceptual work can be used to predict and seek for patterns. In pattern matching, a single pattern can be compared to the other patterns observed in the cases, and/or mutually exclusive rival patterns can be compared with the other patterns observed in the cases (Yin, 2003).

Critical turning points approach: Rather than examining critical turning points (CTP) in the innovation journeys of social innovation initiatives as moments at which initiatives undergo or decide for change-of-course (see Pel et al., 2017), we have explored critical points or phases of institutional work. Institutional work refers to activities of SIE-field-actors and other field-actors that aim to create, maintain and transform institutions (based on Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006). These include, for example, attempts to influence policy makers and the general public through direct lobbying, research reports, position papers, advertising; the setting of technical standards; and/or attempts to influence informal institutions, such as values, norms, binding expectations, common beliefs, habits, and routines among the wider public (Arenas, 2017). Several instances and processes of institutional work were identified as part of the case study and country reports, from which it was possible to conduct a comparative analysis.

4.2.1.5 Step 5: Analytical generalisations

Generalisability in qualitative research has been a controversial topic given that interpretivist scholars have resisted the dominant role and mandate of the positivist tradition within social sciences (Polit and Beck, 2010). The aims of qualitative studies have not been to generalise, but rather to provide a rich, contextualised understanding of empirical phenomena through the in-depth study of specific cases. Qualitative methodologies that outline ways of conducting analytical generalisations are still rare (Halkier, 2011). To increase the transparency of such

generalisations, Halkier (2011:787) has outlined three methodological strategies and processes: “*ideal typologising, category zooming and positioning*”; and highlighted key critiques to generalisation that must be addressed when conducting such work. As highlighted by (Halkier, 2011:787/788):

“First, generalising on the basis of qualitative studies must necessarily be much more specific and context bound than understandings of generalisation as universalising. Second, generalising on the basis of qualitative studies must recognise and try to represent the dynamisms, ambivalences, conflicts, and complexities that constitute various overlapping contexts and the knowledge-production processes in relation to these contexts.”

Taking this guidance on board, we have taken the following analytical steps (and explorative approach) when starting to conduct analytical generalisations: 1) identifying categories based on deductive themes (e.g. institutional work); 2) tracing the relationships between identified categories (e.g. institutional work) and emerging patterns across the case studies (e.g. forms of institutional work across SIE-fields); 3) organising emerging patterns based on similarities and differences (e.g. similar and different forms of institutional work across the SIE-fields); 4) taking the emerging patterns of similarities and differences and arriving at reflections summarising key findings (see reflection boxes included within sections 4.3.1, 4.3.2, 4.3.3, 4.3.4, 4.3.5 and 4.3.6). Following this, we developed several working propositions (see section 4.4). Working propositions are tentative and preliminary statements about different aspects of SIE. They are thus tentative explanations that form possible answers to our research questions by relating concepts to one another. These working propositions will be used for the upcoming conceptual work as part of SONNET WP1. In addition, we identified one analytically promising category (i.e. policy mixes) to zoom in on within the comparative analysis. We went back to the data material and carried out a focused thematic analysis based on this promising category (see section 4.3.6). This work will be deepened as part of SONNET WP2.

4.3 Comparing SIE-fields (and their SIE-initiatives)

The decarbonisation of often highly institutionalised energy systems involves changing existing institutions, including regulations, norms, values, and belief systems that keep existing systems stable over time. Our fieldwork has shown that SIE-field-actors play a role in creating and transforming institutions, but also sometimes maintain existing ones. The SONNET team is interested in exploring the relations between existing institutions that stabilise energy systems, and SIE-fields-actors attempting to and/or playing a role in maintaining them. To analyse these dynamics, we have gone beyond understanding the emergence and development of individual SIE-initiatives, such as Brighton Energy Cooperative, as is often done in (social) innovation research. Instead, we have investigated how SIE-fields have emerged and developed (and alongside them SIE and SIE-initiatives), in addition to how institutions have shaped such developments over time. This has also led us to explore which forms of social relations in energy systems have changed and to what extent.

This section outlines the results from the comparative analysis of 18 SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives. It is structured around several core themes that derived from the empirical and

conceptual work and linked to the core research questions that have guided the WP3 work. The themes are:

- ▲ Characterisation of SIE-fields: SIE-field-actors, their activities and interactions over time – diversity
- ▲ Changes in social relations in energy systems
- ▲ Institutions shaping the SIE-fields
- ▲ SIE-initiatives (and their collaborators) conducting institutional work – contributions
- ▲ Processes of institutionalisation across SIE-fields – processes
- ▲ Towards policy mixes promoting social innovation in energy

As outlined in the themes' titles, we examine the *diversity*, *processes* and *contributions* of SIE (including the SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives). The following sub-sections provide key insights derived from the comparative analysis linked to each theme, starting with the notion of SIE-field, which includes SIE-field-actors and their activities and interactions over time.

4.3.1 Characterisation of SIE-fields: SIE-field-actors, their activities, and interactions over time – diversity

In order to understand the emergence and development of SIE within SIE-fields over time (i.e. our first empirical focus outlined under section 1.1.1.), we focus on the notion of 'SIE-fields' in this sub-section. SONNET defines an SIE-field as an “arena/space that includes a specific SIE as well as SIE-field-actors working on it and other field-actors enabling and/or impeding it” (Wittmayer et al., 2020:26). A field can be analytically approached by focusing on “increasing interactions between actors including the formation of coalitions and networks” (Wittmayer et al., 2020:25). Therefore, this section explores the diverse actors that are involved in each of the SIE-fields under study (by working, enabling or impeding SIE) and their interactions over time.

This interaction is further outlined in our definition of SIE-fields as those places where “actors take one another and their actions into account and have a shared (but not necessarily consensual) understanding of an SIE and of their relationship to other actors. They recognise (but not necessarily follow) shared norms, beliefs and rules. SIE-fields are often not homogenous but are composed of actors with diverse and contradictory aims and interests” (Wittmayer et al., 2020:26). Based on this definition, SIE-fields are formed through the ways that actors relate to one another, their understanding of SIE, their recognition of shared norms, beliefs and rules, and/or their aims.

Rather than covering all these aspects, we have analysed the 18 case studies to explore the question: What types of actors make up SIE-field-actors and what have been their activities and interactions over time? We empirically identify how actors manifest around specific SIE and develop collectives (e.g. informal and formal alliances/networks/collaborations) as well as shared (but not necessarily consensual) narratives and activities (and associated norms, beliefs and values) over time. Doing so allows us to gain important insights into how these SIE-fields empirically manifest and how they are shaped, as well as the extent to which the boundaries of an SIE-field are more or less fluid and/or recognisable.

In the following sub-section, we compare each of the SIE-fields across the three countries of study; the reflections provided in the box at the end of this sub-section are an effort to compare across SIE-fields across countries.

4.3.1.1 What types of actors make up SIE-field-actors and what have been their activities and interactions over time?

The most important actors in the SIE-field called **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy** (COOP RE) are those organisations adopting ‘cooperative organisation’ models and engaging in operating renewable plants, fostering citizen involvement and selling energy. The work of often-called renewable energy cooperatives is supported by several different networking organisations, focused on facilitating electricity exchange, organising networking, funding projects and/or representing their interests in lobbying and advocacy work. Similar tasks are taken up by regional intermediaries in Germany. Also, governments (local, regional, national, European) play an important role in enabling and/or impeding the development of cooperative organisation models, through funding and knowledge exchange (EU), regulation and support schemes (national governments) or initiating and supporting renewable energy cooperatives (local governments). A similar role to the latter is also taken up by energy and climate agencies in France.

The three SIE-fields in Switzerland, France and Germany are shaped by the very different (energy-related) political structures of the three countries. In Switzerland, the SIE-field is highly publicly accepted, and its beginnings reach back to the 1800s. More recently, there are various associations or foundations dedicated to supporting interaction between actors. These include associations for: the promotion of the cooperative idea; for solar PV for independent energy producers; or actual renewable energy cooperatives. Such intermediaries actively provide space for exchanging knowledge and networking among actors. At the other end of the spectrum, we have France with a highly centralised energy system. The French renewable energy cooperatives face constraints regarding their desired engagement along the supply chain due to government regulations. The national government plays an important role in regulating the sector and creating framework conditions, including the design and implementation of support schemes such as feed-in-tariffs. Facing such strong regulative power, the French SIE-field can be considered “*as a rather closed network of like-minded actors*” (COOP RE, France). Increasingly banks and insurance companies, in addition to local authorities and energy agencies are supportive of renewable energy communities, while the political orientation of regional and national authorities can stand in the way. Especially more experienced cooperatives started to create support structures for newcomers in France – often leading to geographically concentrated increases in the number of renewable energy cooperatives. A regional identity is important in Germany, where regional intermediaries funded by the federal government function as important enablers – their establishment led “*to an increased number of potential partners and to an expansion of social relations*” (COOP RE, Germany). Similarly, to France, the relation between renewable energy cooperatives and local authorities was considered to create a kind of “*co-dependency*” (COOP RE, Germany). Germany has two main cooperative networks engaging in networking, knowledge exchange and representing the interests of renewable energy cooperatives. Specifically, for Germany, it seemed important that individuals occupy positions in different cooperatives and thereby foster informal ties between them.

The SIE-field around **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFFF) includes individuals and residents, informal and formal groups (e.g. local initiatives, NGOs, foundations, and associations) that work locally, regionally, nationally but also internationally on this SIE. They are motivated by being connected to certain places where extraction or exploration of fossil fuels (is to) take place, and/or by broader environmental and climate change agendas. SIE-field-actors engage in different activities with the aim to 'stop' fossil fuels being extracted, explored, mined and/or invested in; these include campaigns, lobbying, strikes, petitions, deliberative meetings, creative interventions and/or the mobilisations of people. In all three countries local groups collaborate with regional and/or national level NGOs, while in the Netherlands they are also joined by businesses that (would) suffer adverse consequences from fossil fuel extraction, such as water companies. Collaboration between organisations and groups is often informal and takes place through sharing information, supporting via social media, attracting resources and networking activities; SIE-field-actors know how to find each other and collaborate in certain activities. Sometimes, regional and national network organisations are created to collect experiences and knowledge across groups (such as in the United Kingdom across local anti-coal groups). In the United Kingdom, close ties between organisations and groups arose through the affiliation of specific people to multiple groups and organisations. In Poland, it could be witnessed that the conflict with 'the outside' (i.e. fossil fuel industry) enhanced in-group solidarity. Historically, these SIE-field-actors can build on a history of environmental movements that was revived in all three countries following the Paris Agreement in 2015, as well as through the emergence of a broader decentralised organised climate movement that put climate change firmly on the agenda.

The activities of these SIE-field-actors are often targeted at fossil fuel companies, (national) governments, and institutional investors in the fossil fuel industry (often universities, banks and pension funds). Local governments have played different roles over the years and across the different sites of exploration and extraction within and across countries – including support for the shale-gas free movement by declaring themselves shale-gas free in the Netherlands, and support for continued coal extraction in Poland. The role of national governments has become more ambivalent over the years. Traditionally, they aim to secure energy supply and to this end have formulated policies that often maintain the extraction of fossil fuels. During the last years, they also have signed international and formulated national climate agreements and targets (Netherlands, United Kingdom) or been pressured by EU regulation (Poland) – which are often at odds with continued extraction and exploration of fossil fuels. Furthermore, the Dutch government's advisory bodies reassessed risks associated with gas extraction and advised the government to consider local safety above energy extraction interests. In all three countries, courts and their judgements played a major role as means through which SIE-field-actors could challenge national government strategies and decisions.

The SIE **Local electricity exchange** (LEE) concerns multi-actor collectives (including multiple non-traditional energy players) experimenting with and implementing novel financial, institutional, technical (digital) and business model innovations to enable grid-connected local/regional renewable energy exchange. This SIE – let alone the SIE-field – is at the early stages of development. In different countries and localities, different formats on how to enable the local exchange of renewable are experimented with. These include collective self-consumption (France, Switzerland), local power purchase agreements (France), and peer-to-peer electricity trading (United Kingdom). For each of these, different actors are in the driving seat – for collective self-consumption the exchange is organised by independent organisations, referred to as PMO

(Personne Morale Organisatrice; or organising legal entity) in France, and ZEV (Zusammenschluss zum Eigenverbrauch; legal term denoting pooling for self-consumption) in Switzerland. Power-purchase agreements are organised by the utility (France) – while in Switzerland the ZEV is taking over the role of the traditional utilities. National governments (including regulators) are important for defining legislation and regulations governing LEE, including exemptions from regulations to allow experimentation with such solutions. Across the United Kingdom and France, important actors include municipalities, housing cooperatives, and suppliers of renewable energy including energy cooperatives. Those actors often initiate and/or drive the development of the SIE. In Switzerland, the ZEV is often initiated by a housing cooperative, other real estate companies or pension funds. Other interested actors are real-estate firms (partly due to legal obligations for PV coverage on new developments); technology firms providing data management solutions; or intermediaries that can provide advice and support. Distribution System Operators can provide data, and various associations lobby the government for more favourable conditions. Research institutes play a role in experimental settings, while companies focused on contracting, planning, installing, metering and billing services are also required for implementation.

The SIE-field is still emerging in all three countries. In the United Kingdom, many developments are still in experimental or trial stages and no formal networking between actors could be observed. In France, collective self-consumption and power-purchase agreements are already being implemented. In Switzerland, the ZEV has become an accepted organisational form for collective self-consumption, and further experiments towards peer-to-peer trading have been started involving universities and innovative Distribution System Operators. There we also see strategic cooperation between housing cooperatives with specific service providers (e.g. metering and billing solutions), and a number of key associations that organise information exchange. The beginning of SIE-field development has seen collaboration between new market entrants (cooperatives and new firms) and established players (utilities and Distribution System Operators) testing new forms of LEE – especially in Switzerland. In France, the exchange between these groups is often facilitated by associations, intermediaries and/or interest groups. Due to the experimental nature of many collective self-consumption projects in France, they rely on support from established actors such as electricity suppliers, regional energy agencies or Distribution System Operators. Similarly, power-purchase agreements rely on formalised collaborations between renewable project developers and electricity suppliers. However, in all three countries there are still many contestations, especially between incumbents (utilities and Distribution System Operators) and new actors (cooperatives and new firms). These concern issues such as: the very existence of LEE; its role in the energy system and for energy transitions' regulation of the distribution grid (access, use, financing mechanism); or what qualifies as 'local' in electricity exchange.

Along with NGOs and associations, local administrations and authorities are driving the SIE **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC) based on an increasing recognition by several actors (from local to EU) of the important role of cities in energy transitions. Local administrations either organise competitions for their citizens (often families or school children participating in within-city competitions) or participate in competitions and/or labelling efforts with other cities (between-city competitions). The between-cities competitions and city labels are driven by regional, national or international associations, as well as national governments. City labels (i.e. formats that bring lots of actors in the city together to carry out energy projects) seem highly standardised in Switzerland and France, and are linked to the European Energy Award. In

Switzerland, the collaboration of actors involved in the main city label is enabled and funded by Federal Government and managed by a national label association. This association also connects cities that have been awarded the label, while label consultants advise cities in their process towards gaining the label. Similarly, in France, the public agency for ecological transition manages the label process. Together with a national NGO, they support and coordinate the consultants and NGOs who help cities in the application and awarding procedure.

The within-city competitions are typically coordinated and/or organised by NGOs or local administrations, and in all three countries informal collaboration rather than formal interaction is typical in this type of competition. In Switzerland, there is less formalised interaction between within-city competitions and between-city competitions, while in France, the public agency for ecological transition is an important actor for both types of competitions. This French agency has also drastically reduced its support for within-city competitions over the last years. In Switzerland, more within-city competition is emerging, while in Germany within-city competitions are *“increasingly under pressure to develop new formats that reach out to different, sometimes ‘hard to reach’ actor groups in order to mainstream issues related to sustainable energy”* (CLC, Germany). Especially between-city competitions lead to increased collaboration between city departments, mainly concerning measures and indicators, while within-city competition increases networking between citizens.

The most relevant SIE-field-actors in the SIE-field **Participatory Experimentation and Incubation** (PIE) across Germany, Netherlands and Poland are governments (local, regional, national, EU), knowledge institutes, energy businesses and increasingly civil society. They work on multi-actor, collaborative formats that aim to experiment with and/or try out novel energy solutions in specific local settings, bringing together actors from different societal spheres to work together (rather than to have a dialogue only) in a project-like setting. In the Netherlands and Germany, this SIE-field remains dominated by national governments, who fund and provide the framework conditions for the experimentation with new solutions by multiple actors. National innovation policies often focus on techno-economic innovation through triple helix collaborations including universities, companies and government. In the Netherlands, domain-specific networks draw up a research agenda to execute the mission driven innovation policy of the government. They aim to increase learning among the funded triple helix consortia. Similar structures can be found in Germany. Over the last decade, there has been some movement towards opening up to new forms of actor collaboration including local governments, civil society and citizens, with the aim of addressing broader societal agendas such as sustainability or social cohesion. These take different forms, such as living labs, city labs, regulatory sandboxes, or Reallabore ('real life laboratories'). In the Netherlands and Germany, much informal learning takes place between such labs; relationship building is considered crucial in this, but it is also highly time and resource expensive. In Germany, there are also formal networking organisations for real world laboratories – one oriented towards broader societal change (led by universities) and one oriented towards technological and economic orientated innovations (led by the Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy). Rather than by national innovation policy as in Germany and the Netherlands, in Poland, multi-actor collaborative forms were initially driven by local governments and networks of local governments, NGOs, companies and citizens, who produced and balanced energy locally, often supported through EU funding. Only later the national government formalised and certified Energy Clusters, which are linked through the national Chamber of

Energy Clusters. The latter lobbies for changes to legislation and provides possibilities for networking and exchange.

The SIE-field **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE) revolves around financial mechanisms and subsidies that allow for novel multi-actor constellations involved in renewable energy (in particular, solar PV and wind) to emerge. The SIE-field spans a heterogeneous group of actors, specifically financial (services) institutions (e.g. banks, institutional investors, crowdfunding platforms), governments (at all scales, their regulators and authorities) and citizen initiatives (energy cooperatives and energy communities). Each of these actors can provide and/or receive financial mechanisms and subsidies. Additionally, other investors, such as renewable project developers, utilities or independent power producers play a role alongside trade associations and interest groups. National governments were important in shaping the SIE-field across the three countries: on the one hand through regulating access to and finance of energy markets, and on the other, through offering, facilitating or stopping a variety of different mechanisms, including feed-in-tariffs, net-metering, tax reliefs or subsidies. Over time, local governments increasingly provided finance to renewable projects, especially in the United Kingdom. Similarly, in the Netherlands, local governments provided subsidies but soon turned towards providing investments allowing for a return. A similar move from subsidies towards investment mechanisms happened in the United Kingdom, where specific national policies tried to encourage private investment. In addition to public subsidies, sources of finance increasingly came from citizens (often via cooperatives or through crowdfunding campaigns) and from institutional investors (e.g. pension funds, insurance companies in the United Kingdom). Crowdfunding platforms started off in 2011 in the United Kingdom, and soon also started up in the Netherlands. However, Dutch crowdfunding platforms have not managed to reach the volume of those in the United Kingdom. In the United Kingdom, the different actors making up this SIE-field are connected within formalised networks, such as trade organisations (e.g. Solar Trade Association, Renewable UK, UK Crowdfunding Association, Community Energy England and Cooperatives UK); however, there are contestations in terms of competing aims and interests between those networks. In the Netherlands, through participating financially in energy systems via energy cooperatives and crowdfunding platforms, citizens increasingly became recognised as professional actors. In addition, the different crowdfunding platforms are united in a trade association to strengthen their lobbying towards the Dutch government.

REFLECTIONS ON CHARACTERISING SIE-FIELDS

- ✦ The emergence and development of an SIE-field – that is, the types of actors involved and their activities – is strongly shaped by the activities of national governments, including policies and regulations. This type of influence is stronger for some of the SIE-fields than for others, e.g. the development of different types of **LEE** are strongly shaped by such regulations, while the development of **PIE** or **CLC** is much less shaped by them.
- ✦ The SIE-fields of **COOP RE** show a high interaction between different SIE-field-actors. This is also apparent in the formation of numerous intermediaries in the form of national or regional level networks, and/or other actors such as energy agencies which take on an intermediating role. These intermediaries increase the standardisation and possibly diffusion of the SIE since they allow insights and

experiences to be shared, knowledge to be codified and contacts to be established. The SIE-fields of **FAFF** show a similar pattern of networking amongst SIE-field-actors – here we mainly see this happening between SIE-field-actors which focus on different spatial scales, e.g. a local action group with a national environmental NGO.

- ▲ Some of the SIE-fields can rely on long histories of activities related to their SIE in certain countries – what makes them innovative is then often a reframing or a refocusing of these activities. The SIE-fields of **FAFF** in the United Kingdom and the Netherlands are established in a longer line of environmental movements in those countries, and their specific focus is on ending fossil-fuel extraction and/ or exploration. Similarly, **COOP RE** in Switzerland relies on a long history of cooperative energy production across different localities but comes with a new emphasis on global challenges that goes beyond local autonomy or individual economic interests.
- ▲ Some SIE-fields, such as **COOP RE**, have an understanding of their SIE that is more or less uncontested across SIE-field-actor and other field-actors. Meanwhile, the understanding of other SIEs is much more subject to debate and experimentation – especially the SIE-field **LEE** provides an example.
- ▲ The trend towards decentralisation of the energy sector can be witnessed by zooming in on the role of local governments – in several of the SIE-fields they play crucial roles. For the SIE-field **CLC**, local government are crucial actors, both in implementing competitions within their boundaries and in competing with other cities. They are also driving or enabling some of the experimentation and incubation activities happening as part of **PIE** or **LEE**. For **FAFF**, they are important actors in relation to planning permits for fossil-fuel exploration, or in supporting protests.
- ▲ The collaboration of multiple actors is part of how some of the SIEs are defined, such as **PIE** (multi-actor collaboration formats) or **LEE** (multi-actor collectives). This often goes hand in hand with the creation of 'new' actor roles and/or new actors, such as from civil society, entering the energy system.

4.3.2 Changes in social relations in energy systems – diversity

SONNET defines social innovation as “combinations of ideas, actions and/or objects that change social relations and come with new ways of doing, thinking and/or organising energy” (Wittmayer et al., 2020:iv). At the heart of this definition is the aspect of changing social relations. In developing a typology of diverse types of social innovations in energy, we operationalised these social relations by defining them through four types of social interactions: collaboration, exchange, competition and conflict (Wittmayer et al. 2020). In this sub-section, we would like to go one step further to empirically explore which social relations are changing and to what extent. This explorative analysis is guided by two resources. Firstly, the multi-actor perspective by Avelino and Wittmayer (2016). This has been proposed as a heuristic to necessarily explicate the socio-political dimension of sustainability transitions in terms of shifting actor roles and relations. Based on this perspective, we explore the changes of social relations between actors at different levels

of aggregation (individuals, organisations and sectors); and between actors attributed to different institutional logics (state, market, community, non-profit, hybrid). Secondly, the roles perspective for sustainability transitions developed by Wittmayer *et al.*, (2017) sensitises us to how changes in social relations are indicated by changes in the roles of actors (identified through the activities they are performing and the expectations put upon them). Based on this perspective, we explore the emergence of new roles; the change and/or phasing out of existing roles; and changes in who is taking on specific roles in the energy system.

In the following, we compare each of the SIE-fields across the three countries of study as part of an explorative analysis; the reflections provided at the end of this sub-section are an effort to compare across SIE-fields across countries.

4.3.2.1 Which social relations and actor roles are changing in energy systems and how?

Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy (COOP RE). Within COOP RE, individuals and groups (institutional logic: community) come together to engage in the production (amongst other things) of renewable energy using cooperative organisational models for renewable energy (hybrid: market/community). Thus, their role in the energy system has changed. In France, this shift is expressed as *“the role of citizens which goes from passive consumers to active prosumers”* (COOP RE, France). From only consuming energy, individuals and groups are now involved or directly participating in decision-making and ownership of renewable energy facilities. Such so-called active participation of citizens in energy systems is also highlighted in Germany and Switzerland. The Swiss case describes this shift as *“from an economic point of view, citizens are moving from consumers to producers. From a political point of view, they become active co-creators of the energy system who influence not only strategic but also more operational decisions”* (COOP RE, Switzerland). Especially interesting in the Swiss context is that the cooperative organisational model as such is not innovative: it has been used to address local common good issues for centuries. What is innovative is that the new wave of cooperatives addresses broader, global challenges such as climate change. It is therefore considered that *“the central social innovation is therefore a shift of the concept of citizenship when it comes to energy policy that is a change of social relations from voters and passive consumers to prosumers who actively co-shape developments in the energy system”* (COOP RE, Switzerland).

By becoming involved in energy communities, the role of the individual goes beyond mere consumer (market), or voter (state), to political engagement in the direction of energy transitions (state). On an individual level, engagement with energy increases individuals' awareness around the resource 'energy' and changes their relations with this resource. On a collective level, new relations are being forged between individuals engaged in energy cooperatives, while on an organisational level, the relations between cooperatives are often collaborative (rather than competitive as would be expected between firms). As relatively new market entrants, energy cooperatives change the current constellations, for example by diversifying the choice that consumers have regarding what type of energy is produced, where, and by whom. This showcases new organisational models to more established energy actors.

Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways (FAFF). In this SIE-field, individuals concerned with their local environment and their safety (community) start grouping together and

collaborating with interest-based organisations and NGOs (non-profit) to engage against fossil fuel-based energy pathways. Extraction companies (market) and national governments (state) traditionally cooperate in the exploration and extraction of fossil fuels – and have been targeted by the persistent actions of individuals (community) and their interest groups (community, non-profit). State logic mechanisms (e.g. court cases, lobbying, deliberation, demonstrations) are often adopted by community and non-profit actors to reach their goals.

Generally speaking, this SIE-field targets the relation of governments and society with the fossil-fuel industry. In the Netherlands, we clearly see the relations between the government and the extraction companies changing, where the former is increasingly turning against the exploration and extraction of fossil fuels on the grounds of environmental protection, unclear profit margins and climate goals. Similar movements can be witnessed in the United Kingdom and Poland. The divestment movement is specifically targeting the relation between investors and the fossil fuel industry with the aim of ending investments in fossil fuel companies. This has been achieved by successfully mobilising those that the investors invest for – such as future pensioners for pension funds, or students for the endowments of their universities.

Local electricity exchange (LEE). While national governments (state) provide the regulatory context within which LEE can develop, a myriad of actors is driving the experimentation with or implementation of LEE. These include market actors such as housing corporations, real estate companies, pension funds, energy suppliers and utilities; LEE organising entities (such as ZEV, *Zusammenschluss zum Eigenverbrauch*; legal term denoting pooling for self-consumption) in Switzerland and PMO (*Personne Morale Organisatrice*; or organising legal entity) in France; as well as local municipalities (state) and energy cooperatives (hybrid market/community). The SIE is enabled by companies providing services including contracting, planning, installing, metering and billing services (market). Distribution Systems Operators (market) also influence the development of LEE in different ways, while many intermediaries and interest organisations (non-profit) are lobbying the government. This SIE allows numerous actors to enter the energy market and take up new roles there – this includes for example housing corporations, real-estate companies, and pension funds. In creating entities organising LEE (e.g. PMO, ZEV), such entities were adding a new role and changing the role constellations in the energy system. In Switzerland, this *“new legal entity replaces the local utility and becomes responsible for energy supply, metering, and organising a community of end-consumers”* (LEE, Switzerland). This Swiss collective self-consumption mechanism also changed the relations between real estate organisations and tenants – where the former, via the ZEV as LEE organising entity, now also sells and distributes energy to the latter. In France, peer-to-peer exchanges are considered *“to empower producers and consumers to organise electricity locally and between peers”* (LEE, France) – implying new relations based on the exchange of electricity. One can argue that through such exchanges, consumers (spanning individuals and organisations) can potentially gain more control over their energy bills, and that such localised networks allow for more autonomy. It is also argued that LEE allows *“reinventing people’s relation with electricity, creating an emotional bond with the electricity they produce”* (LEE, France). French energy suppliers play a double role – while on the one hand lobbying for policies that constrain further LEE development, on the other hand, they consider LEE as an emerging market and want to pick their share. Similarly, French Distribution System Operators were hesitant towards LEE developments at the start but now consider it as a way to increase social acceptance of smart meters and increase consumers’ digital savviness. To sum up, as part of LEE local authorities

(state), community energy/energy cooperatives (hybrid) and individuals/prosumers (community/market) increase their role in the system, while traditional actors see their roles changing (e.g. in the United Kingdom Distribution Network Operators turning into Distribution System Operators). Collaborations between state, market and community actors, and across incumbent and new market actors are characteristic for the SIE-field.

City level competitions for sustainable energy (CLC). Local governments (state), often enabled by supportive framework conditions of national governments (state), organise and/or lead within-city competitions or participate in between-city competitions. Such competitions involve novel ways of engaging in different (playful) energy competition formats – such as formats characterised by a strong sense of ‘competitiveness’ but also joyful ‘fun formats’, awards or labels. While this SIE has a strong competitive element related to activities such as ranking, comparing, and winning, these competitions seem to strengthen cooperation between and within municipalities. The backbone of between-city competitions, specifically national or international labels, are public agencies or associations (state/non-profit), NGOs (non-profit) and consultancies (market/hybrid); together, these actors form the ecosystem supporting local governments (state) in the application for and participation in the label. These *between-city* competitions seem to challenge and change: 1) the relations between different departments within local administration (state): away from an often siloed structure, since the competitions provide a common goal, foster interactions and require collaboration across departments (such as in France and Germany); 2) the relation between cities (state): competitions provide the opportunity to benchmark cities’ own activities towards sustainable energy, but also provide opportunities for cities to relate more closely to peer cities, to learn from best practices; and 3) relations between cities (state) and the national government (state): through providing recognition for their engagement in sustainable energy, CLC contributes towards cities taking up an active role in energy transitions (particularly in Switzerland). Meanwhile, *within-city* competitions are often organised by local governments (state) or local NGOs (non-profit), at times following formats developed by a combination of NGOs, associations or think tanks (hybrid, non-profit). They challenge different relations: 1) relations between citizens: citizens both compete against one another, and collaborate and learn from one another to achieve sustainable energy consumption and production (e.g. France); 2) relations between citizens (community) and their natural or material environment: providing an opportunity for raised awareness and questioning of citizens’ own energy behaviour (e.g. in France); and 3) relations of citizens with themselves: engaging in such a competition “*is above all a competition with oneself and oneself over time*” (CLC, France), thus challenging and possibly changing citizens’ own behaviour.

Participatory Experimentation and Incubation (PIE). National governments (state) are putting forth national innovation policies that provide formalised spaces for multi-actor collaboration – specifically between governments (state), businesses (market) and knowledge institutes (non-profit) – to experiment with or incubate new energy solutions. The aimed for result are techno-economic innovations. Especially in Germany and the Netherlands, such formats are well known as triple helix collaborations, and in Poland this has also become the dominant form of PIE. We see that certain trends and events and their interpretation led to contestations of this institutionalised collaboration system. This has led to the emergence of other collaborative formats, alongside (or in the case of Poland preceding) the institutionalised triple helix – such as living labs, real-world laboratories, or city labs. Other actors became involved, such as individuals, often framed as users (market) or citizen (state), associations or foundations (non-profit) or local

governments (state); they took up roles that were hitherto fulfilled by national government (e.g. municipalities or foundations funding labs) or that were newly integrated in the experimentation and incubation process (e.g. user perspective).

The extent to which these new formats challenge existing relations depends on their orientation – some are oriented towards increasing social acceptance of key technologies, while others are more bottom-up and emancipatory in their intent, focused on collaborative learning for sustainability. What they do challenge is the dominance of large companies (market) and national government (state) in defining the direction of the energy system – through involving more and diverse actors in the search for new energy solutions that fit their specific regional and local conditions and resources.

Financing and subsidies for renewable energy (FS RE). National governments (state) provide a repertoire of different financial mechanisms and subsidies for the development of RE. These subsidies are aimed at renewable project developers (market), energy companies (market), utilities (market, state), local governments (state), energy cooperatives/community energy (hybrid), households (community). During the last decade, we see three main trends in this SIE-field: 1) increased private investment (market) alongside public finance mechanisms (state) and subsidies through institutional investors; 2) increased private investment by individuals making use of the possibilities offered through crowdfunding platforms (market) or energy cooperative/community energy (hybrid); and 3) increasing role of local governments in financing renewables (state).

A first important change is that new actors took up the role of providing subsidies to or investments for renewables – not only banks or national governments, but increasingly institutional investors, municipalities and individuals. In terms of institutional logics, we thus see an increased role of the community and the private sector in comparison to the public sector. Next to this, there is also a shift within the state sector, with an increased role for local and/or regional governments in comparison to national governments. This growing access to capital, also for relatively new or small market entrants, can be considered as 'empowering' these actors in relation to other market players. It is *"slowly but steadily changing the structure of the ownership of the energy sources, and enabling the individuals and organisations previously excluded from the processes of energy production to take this new role"* (FS RE, Poland). A second important notion is that such funding opportunities, next to technological and regulatory developments, supported the emergence of the role of energy prosumers – especially important in the Polish context. *"Parties setting the regulatory framework, and offering and managing capital for investments, are creating (new) SIE-field-actors (e.g., prosumers) designing their capacities and functions through funding opportunities' offers. Those (have potential to) change the network of relations between different actors in the energy sector (e.g., energy incumbents and smaller energy producers; energy distributors and local energy communities)"* (FS RE, Poland). A third observation is that we can think of changes in social relations in at least two ways. Firstly, activities designed to encourage new social relations may be supported by funding, e.g. *"when a grant is made to fund a collaborative research project involving a novel form of collaboration"* (FS RE, United Kingdom). Secondly, the financial mechanism itself changes relations or redefines roles, e.g. *"where community share raises make local people investors in a solar farm or when contractual forms around revenue streams involve new combinations of actors"* (FS RE, United Kingdom).

REFLECTIONS ON CHANGES IN SOCIAL RELATIONS IN ENERGY SYSTEMS

Social relations in energy systems are changing on different fronts; in the following, we share some observations across the different SIE-fields.

In terms of **changes in roles and/or actors taking on roles**, we observe the following:

- ▲ Some of the SIEs are driven by and/or created by actors new to the energy system **taking on and remaking existing roles** which were previously, and often still are, fulfilled by others. This particularly concerns individuals, who start to produce and exchange energy, become co-owners of renewable installations, become members of energy cooperatives and/or invest in renewable projects, and in the process reshape what the role of energy producers or energy investors comes to mean: based on renewable energies, produced by an individual, based on private funds, etc.
- ▲ SIEs also imply **new roles in the energy system** – the role of ‘organising LEE’, for example, has not previously existed. This specific role is also taken up by relatively new actors to the energy system such as housing cooperatives, real-estate companies or pension funds.

Through ‘entering’ the energy system, these new actors and roles challenge incumbent actors to start relating to them; the above illustrated changes certainly meant a diversification and localisation of actors and changing role constellations in existing energy systems.

In terms of changes in the **institutional logics** governing the energy system, we make the following observations:

- ▲ **Institutional logics become more hybridised** in the energy system. On the one hand, this occurs through hybrid organisational forms: combining market/community or market/non-profit logics, for example, renewable energy cooperatives that strive for profit but also for the common good. On the other hand, it occurs through the collaboration of actors operating according to different institutional logics, which we see particularly for those groups driving PIE or LEE formats.
- ▲ In several different SIE-fields, the **state logic seems to gain more foothold**. This concerns the discussion around the role of ‘citizens’ in energy systems and how these roles are more political than before. We also see the roles of local governments diversifying, including investments, experimentation and incubation, or driving competitions – and thereby local governments gaining a more important status in energy systems. Finally, we see national governments releasing more climate friendly policies that also have repercussions for their relationship with the fossil fuel industry – sometimes moving away from pro-fossil fuel policies towards taking responsibility for climate change and residents local to extraction sites.

The relations between actors are thus changing through being governed under new institutional logics associated with new norms and values – with a soft push back of hardcore market logics and an opening towards community and state logics. However, the primacy of the market logic prevails as being the logic through which social innovations (such as PIE, LEE or COOP RE) should diffuse or are being taken up. This very much follows the thinking that underlies *technological* innovation uptake.

4.3.3 Institutions shaping the SIE-field - processes

This sub-section focuses on how institutions (regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive) have shaped and influenced the emergence and developments of the SIE-fields, creating enabling and impeding conditions over time. We look at differences and similarities between SIE-fields and countries, sticking to high level observations and interpretations that derived from the analysis. The following sub-sections first briefly outline our understanding and definition of institutions; then outline how regulative institutions have influenced the development of the SIE-fields; and finally turn to cultural-cognitive and normative institutions.

4.3.3.1 Understanding institutions

In SONNET, we have drawn on the ‘new institutionalism’ literature. In this literature, Scott (2001) has distinguished between three pillars of institutions, noting that institutions “*comprise regulative, normative and cultural-cognitive elements that, together with associated activities and resources, provide stability and meaning to social life... Institutions are multifaceted, durable social structures, made up of symbolic elements, social activities, and material resources*” (Scott 2014:56-57). Each of the pillars has their own basis of legitimacy and logic of compliance (Scott 2001).

We have outlined the three pillars in deliverable D1.2. (Wittmayer et al., 2020). They are also summarised in Table 4.

Table 4: Three pillars of institutions

Regulative pillar	Normative pillar	Cultural-cognitive pillar
Rules, laws, policies, standards, control and sanctions are the key elements and mechanisms of compliance that give meaning to these institutions.	“Form of rules-of-thumb, standard operating procedures, occupational standards and, educational curricula” are the key elements of the institution (Hoffman 1999). This pillar is connected to values, social norms, duties, and role expectations (Scott 2001).	The cultural-cognitive pillar relates to shared conceptions of reality, binding expectations and common beliefs with which the world is interpreted and/or meaning is given, such as symbols, discourses and cultural categories. ‘Cultural’ stands for socially constructed symbolic representation (i.e. discourses and frames) and “cognitive in that they provide vital templates for framing individual perceptions and decisions” (Scott 2010:7).
Regulative institutions guide action and perspectives by coercion or threat of legal sanction (Hoffman, 1999).	Actions and beliefs are guided forms of social obligation and professionalisation (e.g. trade associations). For example, which	Such elements are usually implicit, as they frequently become routine ways of understanding the world

Regulative pillar	Normative pillar	Cultural-cognitive pillar
Actors comply with them because they prefer not to suffer the consequences (e.g. penalties).	normative goals (such as the increased access to solar PV energy for those without adequate funding) have more legitimacy than others are highly debated between actors within the energy sector.	and create 'cognitive logics' for action.

The next section outlines how regulative institutions have influenced the emergence and development of the SIE-fields.

4.3.3.2 How have regulative institutions influenced the emergence and developments of the SIE-fields?

In the following paragraphs, we highlight some of the key differences and similarities of how regulative institutions have shaped the developments of the SIE-fields, first looking at each SIE-field in turn and then summing up by drawing attention to key differences and similarities.

Existing regulatory frameworks of the energy sector have been a key barrier for the development of **Local electricity exchange** (LEE), partly because countries are still experimenting with the implementation of LEE (and its different potential approaches/models). Most of Europe's energy market arrangements have evolved and developed around the supplier hub model, where the supplier is the nexus within the energy system, linking several processes and information between actors. In most energy systems, the supplier role is entrenched in existing regulatory frameworks, including licensing arrangements and industry codes. The supplier hub model and associated regulatory frameworks have created barriers for the emergence of LEE: for example, rules exist where energy consumers are able to contract with only one licensed supplier at any one time. To overcome some of these barriers, the **United Kingdom** government has opted for a regulatory sandbox approach to "*trial innovative ideas which are not foreseen in regulation, in a real-world environment with a small number of domestic customers during a limited amount of time, without some of the usual rules applying*" (Schneiders et al., 2020:19). In **France**, the national government has gone for an approach where regulators try to control the development of LEE through regulations due to the worry that it could endanger the existing electricity distribution and transport system (which many consider to be functioning well). Established actors in the energy systems such as finance ministry and regulatory bodies have tried to slow changes to protect the status-quo, while providing some space to enable some LEE activities. In **Switzerland**, regulatory changes opened up new entrepreneurial opportunities for SIE-field-actors within LEE. For instance, allowing private consumption communities (so called ZEV) to create an organisational model and legal entity for the self-consumption of solar power beyond building and/or property boundaries. Still, several legal limits continue to exist; for instance, blockchain technology for trading has been technically possible but its uptake has been impeded through regulations. Our findings show that the regulatory approach taken (or not) to enable the emergence of LEE often shape and define its manifestations. The characteristics of LEE and its role in future energy systems is still uncertain and is likely to look different across Europe, including as a result of regulatory developments.

FS RE and COOP RE have had a longer history than LEE. As such, regulatory approaches have emerged and changed (and sometimes have been disbanded) over the past years. For the

development of **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE), subsidies (as a key policy mechanism) have played a central role in the development of renewable energy sectors and their markets. In the **United Kingdom**, government subsidy policies for renewable energy have led to a significant increase in the deployment of renewables. After a few years, following a decrease in the costs of some renewables, subsidies were reduced and eventually cut, which was a surprise for some of the SIE-field-actors. Since then, the sector has been moving to subsidy-free renewables, diversifying who finances renewable energy (and how). Similarly, in the **Netherlands** over the last two decades renewables financing gradually shifted from state subsidisation towards relying on market mechanisms. The government's role has more generally moved towards stimulating a free market approach in financing decarbonisation and sustainability innovations, which is also signified in creating Invest-NL (i.e. private company financed with public funds, providing finances for sustainability innovations). By contrast, in **Poland** legislators have only gradually introduced policies to finance renewables (such as public subsidies, auctions and net metering), partly due to European regulations. Nevertheless, legal regulations have partly impeded the development of FS RE (e.g. regulations surrounding collective presumption are not written into legal Acts, making it difficult to develop cooperative solutions). Looking across the three countries, it becomes apparent that the available forms of financial mechanisms have been strongly dependent on state policies and linked legislations. Indirectly, policy makers through shaping renewable energy finance have influenced organisational aspects of renewable energy (e.g. regulating energy co-ops) and rules linked to its financial market (e.g. around tax relief).

Considering the interlinkages between FS RE and COOP RE, regulative institutions linked to financing renewable energy have also played a role in the development of **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy** (COOP RE). For example, in **Germany**, the provision of feed-in tariffs via the EEG (Renewable Energy Source Act, succeeding the Electricity Feed-in Act) spurred on the developments of COOP RE from the 2000s onwards; this highlights that financial policy mechanisms have also been crucial for the support of COOP RE. Alongside financing, governance structures allowing for greater decentralisation of the energy system have been key for the development of COOP RE. In **France**, the energy system has been centrally managed, seeing that a state-owned producer (i.e. EDF) has dominated the electricity sector, and this has impeded the emergence and development of COOP RE. From 2010, steps towards decentralisation have slowly changed the situation for energy cooperatives. This was particularly due to the introduction of the TECV law (Energy Transition towards Green Growth) in 2015. In comparison, the development of COOP RE in **Switzerland** was eased because of its existing federal system, where the cantons (states) and the municipalities (the lowest administrative level) have autonomy surrounding the governance of energy. Municipalities have often been key for establishing energy cooperatives and providing financial support. In all three countries, the development of COOP RE was impeded by the weakening of feed-in tariffs and overall renewable support policies (e.g. uncertainty surrounding future energy policies relevant for the SIE-field). However, even in times of weakened feed-in tariffs, federalist structures such as those in Germany and Switzerland enabled some support for energy cooperatives to be maintained through regional and local support mechanisms for COOP RE. Nonetheless, SIE-field-actors who make up COOP RE have heavily relied on legislations and subsidies to initiate and support their activities. Cuts to these subsidies meant that most SIE-initiatives had to change their financial models to make upcoming projects work. This has not been a straightforward journey and a time where projects had to be postponed and/or abandoned before being able to find alternative models.

In the case of CLC and PIE, policies have often set a context in which SIE-fields could emerge and develop. **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC) has developed due to an increasing recognition that cities can play a key role in energy transitions, setting in motion several EU and national policy plans (and linked programmes and awards) to support such developments (for example, the Leipzig Charter on Sustainable European Cities and the European Energy Award). In **Switzerland**, the Aktionsprogramm Energie 2000 (launched as part of federal energy policies) also supports the civil society initiative EnergieStadt, which provides advice for local administrations on energy issues. Over time, due to the federal support, the initiative embedded itself into federal politics, including CLC activities. The EnergieStadt label became the standard means to advance CLC in Switzerland. The process connected to the label has been formalised and standardised over the past years, making little room for alternative developments. In France and Germany, CLC is much more heterogenous. In **France**, CLC has often developed around awards and labels. Two key initiatives that aided the development of CLC have been Cit'ergie, which is part of the association European Energy Award and the label Sustainable Innovative City. Similarly, in **Germany**, awards have played a key role. They have included, for instance, the German Sustainability Award (Deutscher Nachhaltigkeitspreis), the award for climate active municipality (Klimaaktive Kommune), the European Green Capital Award, and the Transformative Action Award. These awards largely differ in their organisational structures, their degree of formalisation and stakeholders involved. In both countries, regulations have shaped the development of the SIE-field in two ways. Firstly, they can create an impetus for cities to get involved in energy and climate change issues, creating their own local policy plan that include CLC. Conversely, existing regulations and/or the lack of regulations can be seen as a hinderance for local CLC to be realised and considered to be successful. Moreover, awards (such as the European Energy Award) have created quality management and certifications systems based on standards and rules in order to determine whether city administrations can obtain them. Our findings have shown that policy strategies have often created a context in which the CLC SIE-fields could be initiated and/or develop over time. In addition to awards, quality management procedures, certifications and network structures have been set up, demonstrating a certain maturity of the SIE-fields.

In addition to CLC, over the past years, there has been an increasing recognition of the need for **participatory incubation and experimentation** (PIE) activities within the energy sector, including multiple actors (from civil society to industry actors). This enabled the emergence and development of PIE. The development of regulations can be a key aim of these endeavours. For example, PIE might involve work to identify enabling and impeding regulations for the development of sustainable energy innovations, and/or the provision of spaces in which current regulations are lifted to experiment with how existing regulations might need to change to enable sustainable energy innovations. In addition to energy policy, national and EU innovation policies have played a key role in enabling and influencing PIE, since they often come with their own funding and rules for experimentation activities. In **Poland**, the need to develop and test new social and technical innovations has recently been recognised due to increasing pressure from EU directives and the need to withdraw from coal-based energy pathways. Incubations and experimentations have been conducted within so called 'energy clusters', which have been introduced in the Polish RES Act (Act on Renewable Energy Sources) in 2016. Still, most SIE-field-actors argue that the current energy sector is overregulated, creating too many barriers for clusters to achieve their goals, whilst other aspects linked to cluster development are underregulated (such as relations between the clusters and distribution network operators). In

comparison, in **Germany** and the **Netherlands**, there has been a longer history to the SIE-field, seeing that the need for multi-actor collaborations have been recognised as key in enabling and advancing energy transitions. For example, the Dutch National Environmental Policy Plan in 2001 signified a proliferation of energy-related experiments framed as transition experiments. In Germany, the foundations for the development of the SIE-field was partly set in motion by the transdisciplinary research programme called FONA (Research for Sustainability) that started in 1999. Such policies and funding programmes have created diverse multi-actor collaboration formats (from living labs, showcases to regulatory sandboxes). However, while national policy plans and initiatives have been ambitious in their aims to transform the innovation process through integrating local civil society and municipal actors, only a small number of actors have felt empowered to conduct the transformational work. Regulations have supported the emergence and development of PIE, often in the hope that new innovations towards low carbon energy transitions could be tested and scaled. SIE-field-actors in large parts have not succeeded in transforming existing regulatory institutions away from more dominant innovation paradigms.

Whereas for CLC and PIE regulations have provided a context in which they could develop, the developments of **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF) have demonstrated how existing (and sometimes new) regulations support a ‘business as usual’ attitude towards fossil fuel exploration and experimentation projects, and in the process shape the development of SIE-fields. This happened, for example, through a) policing protests and criminalisation of anti-fossil fuel activities; b) making changes to planning regulations and acts linked to fossil fuels to ease operations for the industry; c) lack of legislated strategies to achieve climate targets; and d) setting up consultative bodies to settle societal disagreements (but with no power to influence decision-making processes). For instance, in the **Netherlands**, the government tried to deal with shale gas projects just like any other type of gas extraction and thus as falling under the existing mining law. This regulatory approach contributed to social mobilisation against shale gas. Still, SIE-field-actors have increasingly been able to make use of regulations surrounding climate change goals and targets to legitimise their actions. In the **United Kingdom**, for example, a campaigner (supported by a law firm and regional network group) won the right to a High Court challenge against a decision to grant planning permission for 20 years of oil production in the south of England. This case was significant for the whole of the United Kingdom because it determined how existing national planning rules surrounding fossil fuels fit with the United Kingdom’s net zero targets. The case was eventually lost, but could be seen as a beginning of things to come. Moreover, in the Netherlands, more recently a court case has been won against Shell to enforce a 45% emission cut by 2030 compared to 2019 emissions levels. In **Poland**, due to an unsupportive national policy towards FAFF, SIE-field actors have tended to develop their agendas in line with the EU regulatory frameworks and expertise. This has provided legitimisation to their actions and empowered their activities in legal, financial and political ways. In all three countries, the state has been able to draw on existing regulations to more or less contain and control the developments of FAFF. Still, SIE-field-actors have increasingly been able to make use of regulations surrounding climate change goals and targets to legitimise their actions.

REFLECTIONS ON REGULATIVE INSTITUTIONS ACROSS SIE-FIELDS

Our analysis has shown that the state and its regulatory actions have played a key role in the development of the six SIE-fields. Differences between how regulative institutions have influenced the development of the SIE-fields are partly due to:

- ✦ the stage of development of the SIE-field;
- ✦ the need for regulatory and policy reforms in order to institutionalise the SIE-field (i.e. how far does it 'fit' into the current energy system);
- ✦ its interlinkages with existing and future government goals and aims.

For example, FS RE and COOP RE have been recognised by policy makers to play a role in moving towards the decarbonisation of the energy sector, and regulations have been developed to support the emergence and initial development of these SIE-fields. By contrast, LEE is still emerging as an SIE-field: its characteristics and potential contributions towards the decarbonisation of the energy sector are considered to be unclear. Policy support and with it, regulatory reforms, have therefore varied between countries and are still in development. For CLC and PIE, regulative institutions in the form of policies have mainly provided a context in which the SIE-fields could develop. For example, as part of CLC, cities have developed formats to reduce energy consumption in people's households to meet local and national climate change targets. For the development of FAFF, regulative institutions have often played a role in control activities in the SIE-field. Although actors and organisation that make up FAFF have worked towards the discontinuation of fossil fuels to achieve the decarbonisation of the energy sector (linked to climate change targets written into Acts), national governments still tried to control some of the developments because they support fossil fuels and/or have yet to make concrete decisions about the speed of phasing out fossil fuels and their future role in the national energy mix.

To sum up, the creation and enactment of regulations have:

- ✦ supported the emergence and development of the SIE-field (e.g. FS RE);
- ✦ stalled developments of SIE-fields because regulations were stopped and/or have been missing (e.g. COOP RE);
- ✦ been temporarily lifted to allow for experimentations to see how regulations needed to evolve to support and/ or regulate the emergence of SIE-fields (e.g. LEE);
- ✦ restricted the emergence of SIE-fields, for example due to a lack of regulatory developments (e.g. LEE);
- ✦ provided an impetus and framework conditions to develop SIE-fields (e.g. PIE);
- ✦ controlled the developments of SIE-fields (e.g. FAFF).

Regulations have also played a role in keeping existing 'business as usual' going in the energy sector, by stabilising current ways of producing, transporting and consuming energy (e.g. LEE, FAFF).

In the next section, we outline how normative and cultural-cognitive institutions have shaped the SIE-fields. As argued by Scott (2010), regulative institutions need to be looked at in combination with normative and cultural-cognitive institutions.

4.3.3.3 How have normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influenced the emergences and developments of the SIE-fields?

This section starts to provide some insights into how normative and cultural-cognitive institutions have influenced the development of the SIE-fields. We felt that normative and cultural cognitive institutions that have influenced the developments of SIE-fields would become more transparent if they are reflected upon in relation to some of the belief systems, values and social norms that exist in current energy systems. We have therefore slightly changed the focus of the analysis in this section. Rather than comparing SIE-fields across the studied countries (as in the section on regulative institutions), we first outline existing belief systems, values and social norms in current energy systems for each country, and then reflect on how they have influenced the developments of SIE-fields in each country. We start with France and end with the United Kingdom.

France

France has relied on a highly centralised energy system. This has included creating a state-owned producer, distributor and supplier of electricity, *Électricité de France (EDF)*. Its main aim has been to create and provide access to affordable energy through the implementation of large-scale nuclear power plants. Until recently, citizens (and other actors) have not been able to shape and influence the development of the energy sector, as it was governed by *“a close network of actors including the directors of public utilities and the central administration [that] jointly determined the energy policy. These technical elite shared similar training (like Ecole des Mines), values and intellectual vision and defended a productivist approach massively based on nuclear generation of electric power”* (CR, France). From 2005, through territorial reforms, city administrations started to be recognised as playing a role in the energy transition, in particular, regaining energy governance responsibilities. Some cities embraced this new role, creating climate change and energy plans whereas others are still getting used to these new responsibilities. Dominant **belief systems, values and norms** surrounding the energy system in France can be described as having been shaped by mainly technical narratives surrounding nuclear power as a reliable, affordable and clean source of energy derived from a centralised system. Citizens are considered to be consumers of energy, who all pay the same tariff for their energy, following a guiding principle of tariff equalisation (i.e. identical pricing of electricity for all consumers) and who do not get involved in energy beyond consuming it.

Normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influencing SIE-field developments. As part of the development of **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy (COOP RE)**, SIE-field-actors needed to develop alternative narratives away from existing technical narratives surrounding nuclear power, including renewable energy and decentralisation. In addition, seeing that citizens have been considered as sole consumers of energy, SIE-field-actors needed to find ways to empower citizens to play a more active role. Narratives have also been developed to include cooperative principles, notions of localism and citizen empowerment. The manifestations of narratives have been set in motion through the formalisation of good practices, procedures and charters defining the core values of COOP RE. Developments surrounding **Local electricity**

exchange (LEE) have only recently emerged in France. SIE-field-actors have been critiqued for trying to abandon the tariff equalisation principle, and therefore contesting one of the core values of the French energy system. SIE-field-actors therefore needed to find ways of creating narratives around solidarity and collective self-consumption, and to show how their activities contribute to the decarbonisation of the energy system. Seeing that France has created a centrally organised energy system, most city administrations only recently gained more governance powers in developing their own climate change and energy plans. This process has been slow, considering that most city administrations still need to develop the expertise and working practices linked to govern energy locally and/ or regionally. Still, in comparison to COOP RE and LEE, the development of **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (LEE) and with it the role of cities in energy transitions is slightly more accepted by other field-actors (partly due to EU legislations).

Germany

In Germany, the energy transition (Energiewende) has received particular attention due to the scope and speed of its developments, in particular in its initial stages. Since the 1990s, the German energy system started to transform from a centralised, coal and nuclear focused system into a more decentralised, increasingly renewable system. The anti-nuclear movement is said to have played a crucial role in setting in motion the energy transition. Nowadays, the energy transition is shaped by an increasing decentralised energy system and a multi-level governance structure where cities and regions can partly determine their own energy futures. The governance of energy is shaped by an agenda of combatting climate change, maintaining security of supply and guaranteeing competitiveness and growth. SIE-field-actors and other field-actors have pointed out that citizens can play multiple key roles in the Energiewende, from co-owners to prosumers. Already in the 1990s, citizens started to initiate and create energy cooperatives. Although legislation was passed to end coal-fired power generation by 2038, this process has not been straightforward. Pathways towards a just transition away from coal are still highly debated in Germany. It might be possible to suggest that the dominant **belief system, values and norms** are based on the current commitment to the German Energiewende in which industrial policy is combined with active energy citizenship, emphasising the need for the energy system to be secure, environmentally friendly and economically successful. Polls still reveal that citizens support climate action and the energy transition (but details remain tricky).

Normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influencing SIE-field developments. Energy cooperatives (and the development of **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy**, COOP RE) have played a key role in the German energy transition. They are widely considered to positively contribute to transitions due to their democratic organisation, mostly local and/or regional orientation and provision of opportunities for citizen engagement. In addition, they have played a role in moving towards a more decentralised energy system. Recent regulatory changes (away from subsidies) have shifted business models towards more market-based approaches (potentially leaving behind some of the original values, e.g. democratisation of energy system). Due to the German federal political system, city administrations have played an active role in developing sustainable energy plans, demonstrating a long history of **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC). Most city administrations have stressed the importance of taking an approach that goes beyond energy issues, in particular by embedding them into climate protection agendas and activities. CLC has also meant that administrative structures and ways of working needed to change within the city administrations. Over the recent

years, they have had to a) overcome existing silos within the administration and b) find collaborators in the city to work with and explore new forms of engagement/ participation. The development of **Participatory Experimentation and Incubation** (PIE) has shown how different norms, values and belief systems exist between actors within the German energy transition, as they come together in multi-actor experimental formats. For example, different values are attached to the need to develop innovations, such as economic growth or sustainable development. Such collaborations highlight contestations surrounding which norms, values and belief system should make up the current and future energy system in Germany.

Netherlands

The energy system in the Netherlands is considered to be one of the most liberalised, as policies have been brought in to radically unbundle it. As part of the process, *“the Dutch government decided to split commercial activities regarding electricity and natural gas from network operations. Generation companies have no shares in network operators, while network operators do not hold shares of generation companies or suppliers. During this unbundling process, competition was introduced”* (Curli et al., 2020:57). Nowadays, most electricity generating companies have derived from government owned ones (in particular, municipal energy companies); still, the government has much less steering power over the energy market than before liberalisation. Historically, natural gas fields have provided cheap and reliable energy, in addition to an income to the national budget, providing a source of national pride. Due to increasing earthquakes associated with extraction activities, and the decision to phase out gas, **belief systems, values and norms** attached to the fossil fuel system have had to change. Although several policies have been introduced to support the energy transition in the Netherlands, as argued by Bosman et al. (2014:46), *“the Dutch energy transition is considerably lagging behind other EU countries... the main explaining factor for this lagging behind is a strong fossil fuel regime in which incumbents play a dominant role”*. Energy cooperatives, citizens and farmers have started to take new roles in the energy sector (some having their own supply companies). However, *“although the citizen energy movement is growing, the impact on the energy mix is small”* (Curli et al., 2020:57).

Normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influencing SIE-field developments. The development of **Participatory Experimentation and Incubation** (PIE) has not only been linked to changes in the energy sector, but also innovation and research programmes and policies, both mainly framed around economic progress and market-based mechanisms. Techno-optimism (solving societal problem with technical innovations) still seems to be the main paradigm framing most of the PIE activities. Shifts in ways of working and thinking only recently occurred due to including diverse societal actors in the experiments. Similar to PIE, **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE) has not only been shaped by the energy sector; developments in the financial sector have also played a crucial role. Neoliberal ideas have shaped the values, norms and practices within the SIE-field. Even developments that moved away from this ideology eventually adapted to existing values and belief. For example, crowdfunding originally meant supporting projects of personal importance, but nowadays these activities have been much more framed around return on investment. As part of the **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF) developments, the divestment movement has been considered as *“norm entrepreneurs”* (FAFF, Netherlands), demonstrating one of the main aims of the SIE-field, i.e. changing narratives surrounding fossil fuels, and with these the norms surrounding them.

Similarly, anti-Groningen gas frames have been able to move from reducing gas extraction to stopping it, due to turning 'private' issues into issues of public concerns (such as the impact of earthquakes due to extraction activities).

Poland

Coal mining still plays a crucial role in Poland and makes up a large part of the energy system. Political decisions around energy have been influenced by the coal lobby for years, arguing the need to maintain the coal industry to secure national energy supply. Such a belief system partly derived from the communist era in which *"the vast expansion of the energy sector was rationalised as necessary to power the energy-intensive and inefficient heavy industry, a flagship of the soviet-style economy"* (CR, Poland). Even after the turn away from communism, sustainability and environmental issues did not really play a role in government decisions, with the main focus remaining on economic growth and, with it, sustaining the coal industry. The situation changed when Poland joined the EU in 2004, which meant that policy makers had to follow EU policies by moving away from coal. This has only happened very slowly and reluctantly over the past years, with arguments that energy security and independency need to be secured, unemployment in coal regions needs to be prevented and energy prices need to be kept stable. Coal extraction still strongly influences the core **belief system, norms and values** in the Polish energy system. Vested interests in the existing coal-based energy system prevail, seeing that most coal corporations are state owned, and unions are highly involved in political decisions. Increasing air pollution and other environmental changes have set into motion a social mobilisation against coal supported by EU legislations. Still, as argued by Brauers and Oei (2020:8), *"a deep-restructuring of core beliefs, identities and values within the country is still pending"*.

Normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influencing SIE-field developments. The development of **Participatory Experimentation and Incubation** (PIE) within Poland has started to slowly change the dominant energy pathways (i.e. fossil fuel extraction) and diversify the actors involved in the energy sector (e.g. beyond national government). Such changes have been initiated by EU policies and funding opportunities. This has involved setting in motion a paradigm shift towards looking beyond technical and economic goals. Such shifts have not been straightforward in Poland due to the prevalent strong technocratic approach and lack of visions for the energy transition. EU policies have also influenced the development of **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE) and **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF) in Poland. Increasing public concerns over pollution, smog and environmental challenges have influenced attitudes towards fossil fuels and renewables. Over 80% of the public considers renewables *"as the safest energy sources among other energy sources"* (see FS RE, Poland). For instance, presumption has started to reshape social understandings towards consumption and production, allowing notions of a more decentralised energy system. Still, Polish politicians (supported by strong mining unions) are keen to sustain 'business as usual', i.e. a coal-based energy system.

Switzerland

Switzerland has a close to carbon-free electricity sector due to the dominance of nuclear and hydro generation. The energy system has been shaped based on Switzerland's federal system

and direct democracy, where cantons and municipalities have had comparably high autonomy to govern the system. Urban utility companies are expected to fulfil a public service whilst making profit for the city administration, defining the 'equitable price' for electricity and gas for the citizens. Some energy cooperatives and private companies exist, but still play a marginal role in comparison to urban utility companies. New collaborations between citizens and urban utility companies have emerged, especially surrounding renewable energy generation. In recent years, the energy system is going through a transition due to a referendum decision to phase out nuclear power. As argued by Markard et al. (2016), core **belief systems** surrounding Swiss energy policy have stayed relatively stable over the past decade. The decision to phase out nuclear did not bring about major policy and energy changes at first, but a heterogenous group of new and incumbent actors has started to support aspects of the energy transition, seeing that environmental and economic benefits are expected and that nuclear energy has lost its legitimacy.

Normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influencing SIE-field developments. In Switzerland, there is a long tradition surrounding the cooperative model, which is also embedded in Swiss society. For instance, cooperatives are frequently used as a model in the housing sector. **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy** (COOP RE) therefore developed from the 1990s onwards in Switzerland. On the one hand, the federal structure aided the development of COOP RE. On the other hand, the SIE-field has remained entrenched in local structures: energy cooperatives have only recently started to nationally organise and influence energy developments. Unlike COOP RE, **Local electricity exchange** (LEE) is still emerging in Switzerland. An organisational model that has slowly institutionalised is the ZEV (Zusammenschluss zum Eigenverbrauch, i.e. prosumption collectives) where non-binding 'standard approaches' have been developed through pilot projects. The ZEV model helped to introduce prosumption in the housing sector, in the form of distributed self-consumption beyond single homes. Still, the role of LEE in the energy transition remains unclear. The development of **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC) has been accompanied by an increasing recognition of the role of cities and city administrations in the energy transition. It helped to anchor energy issues in local administrations (that also have spread to regional developments); this has involved the creation of administrative working groups and the pursuit of networks with other local actors, such as citizens. The EnergieStadt label and associated processes and practices have widely institutionalised in city administrations in Switzerland, not necessarily allowing for other models to emerge but allowing for the emergence and establishment of energy related practices and discourses.

United Kingdom

Governments have favoured the development of large-scale energy projects (for instance nuclear) and market-based climate and renewable energy policies in the United Kingdom over the past decade. Support for renewables has been inconsistent over time and the most significant impact on decarbonisation has been due to fuel switching (from coal to gas fired power stations) that have been driven by EU Directives related to air pollution. Although there is an active community energy sector and large-scale energy providers are no longer as dominant in the energy market, the current energy transition has been characterised in terms of the "*neoliberal approach to energy*" (Devlin 2015:2) and the preference for "*working with incumbents*", rather than "*unleashing new entrants*" (Geels et al. 2016:897). The electricity

systems are still highly centralised and owned by large companies. Even in the case of renewables, large-scale projects have been preferred, for example, offshore wind installations that make up the major increase in renewable capacity over the past years. The dominant **belief system, values and norms** are characterised through a neoliberal approach to energy in the United Kingdom, giving preference to large-scale, centralised projects and market-based approaches. Although there is an active community energy sector, citizens are hardly involved in low carbon energy transitions. There are major differences in the approaches of the territories within Great Britain (i.e. Scotland, Wales, England and Northern Ireland).

Normative and cultural-cognitive institutions influencing SIE-field developments. Although moves towards a decarbonised, liberalised and renewable energy systems have supported it, the emergence of **Local electricity exchange** (LEE) is ambiguous: “*what models can be labelled LEE and what is qualified as ‘local’ electricity exchange is subject to interpretations*” (LEE, United Kingdom). Different actors (e.g. community groups and city administrations) are involved with varying norms, values and belief systems trying to shape LEE, making future developments uncertain. The involvement of non-traditional actors has also influenced the development of **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE): for instance, the increasing role for local authorities in financing renewable energy projects, institutional investors interested in opportunities associated with climate change, and small players, e.g. citizens usually investing through share offers or crowdfunding. These new actors have brought new ways of owning, working with and thinking around energy. Given that the national government recently ended subsidies, the institutionalisation of new financial mechanisms to support renewables is still in development. One of the key achievements derived from the development of **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF) in the United Kingdom is said to be raising awareness and changing public attitudes towards fossil fuels in relation to climate change. In particular, some residents local to extraction sites have described going on a political journey from disengagement to actively trying to change and shape developments in the local/national energy system, often by drawing attention to activities of the government and fossil fuel industry that are considered to keep existing power relations alive. In the process, new relations are being created between, for instance, local residents, local groups, miners and their unions, and NGOs, to find ways of working with each other and creating counter-narratives to existing energy pathways relying on fossil fuels.

REFLECTIONS ON NORMATIVE & CULTURAL-COGNITIVE INSTITUTIONS ACROSS SIE-FIELDS

Europe's energy systems have been in transition towards decarbonisation over the past decade; still, the scope and speed of these transitions has varied. Although regulative institutions have been key to facilitate these changes, belief systems, values and norms can act to stabilise actors' relations and practices within existing energy systems.

Our analysis has drawn attention to how the emergence and development of SIE-fields has given rise to **practices of creating and transforming normative and cultural-cognitive institutions**. These include:

- ✦ Creating 'spaces' where heterogenous belief systems, value and social norms can come together

The development of COOP RE, CLC, PIE and FS RE have helped more novel actors to enter energy sectors, taking up new roles and practices in energy systems (such as citizens as generators of energy). In the case of COOP RE, CLC, PIE and FS RE, more established energy actors have needed to find ways to collaborate with them (and ways of working could be co-opted). Such activities have created spaces in which different belief systems, values and norms linked to existing and future energy systems could come together, potentially developing novel practices.

- ✦ Transforming public awareness and perception linked to particular energy pathways

Increasing public awareness and engagement surrounding energy issues and climate change, and linked social mobilisations have characterised the SIE-field developments (in particular FAFF, but also others) and their possibilities to shape the institutional environment. Such developments have put social pressure on political decision-making around fossil fuels, and on the maintenance of belief systems linked to 'business as usual' within industry.

- ✦ Establishing alternative narratives and practices surrounding solidarity, cooperation, etc.

To be able to legitimise activities and establish alternative norms and values, SIE-field developments have involved countervailing narratives to existing norms and values. For example, in France, COOP RE and LEE developed narratives and practices surrounding notions of solidarity and cooperation to legitimise their work and demonstrate alternative ways of doing and thinking about energy.

- ✦ Providing visions and debates towards alternative energy systems

Most of the SIE-fields (such as LEE, COOP RE) develop visions and ideas for energy systems that look different to existing ones: for example, involving citizen ownership and

local production and consumption. This allows for debates to emerge and can reveal differences in norms and values and the need to change existing ones.

Our findings have also shown that **existing normative and cultural-cognitive institutions have influenced SIE-field developments** in some countries. In particular, they have influenced the speed and direction of transitions in the following ways:

- ✦ Entrenchment of the fossil fuel industry

The entrenchment of the fossil fuel industry within the energy sector and policy made the process of changing existing ways of working and thinking around energy a challenging journey for some SIE-field developments (see, for example, Poland, the United Kingdom and the Netherlands). As argued by Kuzemko et al. (2016:102) *“political organisations, such as government departments, may have long histories of working to maintain the supply orientation of energy systems in line with historic energy industries... Actor groups representing these industries can often mobilise considerable financial and knowledge capital behind influencing the terms of media and political debates emphasising the need to innovate in ways that will ensure their survival”*.

- ✦ Holding onto notions of centralised energy systems

SIE-field developments in more centralised energy systems seems to have taken much more time to emerge and develop, seeing that they have had to overcome several impeding conditions (see, for example, in France, Poland and the United Kingdom). For example, due to the notion of tariff equalisation that has been established in France, social benefits linked to SIE-fields are often questioned in relation to whether they will increase inequality. SIE-field developments have therefore entailed creating narratives of, for example, cooperation and solidarity to counter some of these debates and critiques.

- ✦ Not enough acknowledgements of power and political⁸ issues in multi-actor energy transitions

Although in some countries narratives of an energy transition are well-established (see, for example, Germany), the details of who is involved, how and in what ways, and what the transition and future system should look like are still widely uncertain and unclear. Techno-optimist actors still often dominate existing discussions, partly ignoring issues of power and politics linked to energy transitions.

- ✦ Need to align with policy goals and market approaches

Those SIE-fields more aligned with dominant energy transition narratives have had a more supportive institutional environment in which they could emerge and develop

⁸ Issues of power and politics have been investigated as part of the case study work, but within SONNET is written up primarily as part of WP2. For a more in-depth analysis of power issues see the deliverable D2.3.

(such as FS RE, CLC and PIE). This was partly due to the fact that some of the activities within these SIE-fields went along with prevailing narratives linked to techno-optimist solutions and market-based approaches in the energy system.

- ▲ Going beyond institutions within energy sectors

In addition to prevailing and changing normative and cultural-cognitive institutions with energy sectors, SIE-developments have been influenced by belief systems, values and social norms in, for example, research and development and financial sector (see in particular, FS RE and PIE).

In the next section, we more closely examine the different types of work being conducted by SIE-field actors and other field-actors to influences changes in the institutional environment.

4.3.4 SIE-field-actors and other field-actors conducting institutional work – contributions

This sub-section focuses on institutional changes based on SIE-field-actors conducting institutional work. We look at differences and similarities between SIE-fields and countries, sticking to high level observations and interpretations that derived from the analysis. The following sub-sections first briefly outline our understanding of institutional work; then summarise the forms of institutional work conducted within SIE-fields; and finally outline some concluding reflections.

4.3.4.1 Institutional changes based on SIE-field-actors conducting institutional work

Understanding institutional changes is key to reflect upon the relevance of SIE-field-actors and their activities. As pointed out by Scott (2001:187) *“in highly institutionalised systems, endogenous change seems almost to contradict the meaning of institution”*. Therefore, there is a need to conceptualise the ways in which institutions constrain actors’ behaviour, and how actors are able to influence and change institutions. Drawing on the work of Giddens (1979), actors are conceptualised as being knowledgeable agents who can change institutions (Leblebici et al., 1991). Still, the question of institutional change has always dealt with the ‘paradox of embedded agency’ (Holm, 1995; Battilana, 2006; Garud et al., 2007). In other words, considering that actors and their activities are embedded in institutions (regulatively, normatively and cultural-cognitively), how are they able to shape them at the same time? (Möllering, 2011). Two developments in the literature have highlighted ways to overcome the paradox of embedded agency: first, the concept of institutionalisation, which considers institutional change as being continuous; and second, the recognition of the importance of agency (Zietsma and Lawrence, 2010). The latter has been developed through the notion of institutional work, where institutional changes do not occur only through external shocks but also derive from within the SIE-field. Lawrence and Suddaby (2006) have defined institutional work as practices of individuals and/or organisations that aim to create, maintain and transform/disrupt institutions. Changes in SIE-fields can be explained by investigating how alternative practices can create legitimacy through

an institutionalisation process over time, whilst the legitimacy of previously institutionalised practices slowly becomes eroded (Leblebici et al. 1991; Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006). Lawrence and Suddaby (2006) have conceptualised practices as the connecting element between actions and institutions (Möllering, 2011; Lawrence & Suddaby, 2006). They have argued that through a focus on practices, research can focus on *“the knowledgeable, creative and practical work of individual and collective actors aimed at creating, maintaining and disrupting institutions”* (Lawrence & Suddaby, 2006:12).

Based on a literature review, Lawrence and Suddaby (2006:211) have identified several practices linked to creating institutions as part of institutional work: for example, *“overtly political work in which actors reconstruct rules, property rights and boundaries that define access to material resources”*; *“actions in which actors’ belief systems are reconfigured”*; and *“actions designed to alter abstract categorisations in which the boundaries of meaning systems are altered”*. As part of the review, they also found that little work had been conducted on practices related to maintaining and disrupting institutions. Further empirical work revealed that practices related to maintaining institutions *“primarily address the maintenance of institutions through ensuring adherence to rules systems”* and *“focus efforts to maintain institutions on reproducing existing norms and belief systems”* (Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006:230). Meanwhile, practices related to transforming institutions may involve *“disassociating the practice, rule or technology from its moral foundation”* and *“undermining core assumptions and beliefs”* that have stabilised institutions (Lawrence and Suddaby, 2006:235-237). In the next section, we identify different forms of institutional work across the SIE-fields (see also the work conducted by Rohde and Hielscher, 2021).

4.3.4.2 What forms of institutional work are practiced across the SIE-fields?

As part of the fieldwork, the SONNET researchers have identified what they considered to be the most important activities linked to creating, maintaining and transforming/disrupting institutions as part of SIE-field developments, providing examples of 2-4 activities. Looking across these activities and analysing these practices of institutional work, we have identified several forms of institutional work across the SIE-fields (as outlined in Table 5). Keeping in mind that these are what researchers have considered to be the most important activities, Table 5 does not represent all activities found in the empirical work. We still hope it represents diverse forms of institutional work carried out across the SIE-fields.

Table 5: Examples of forms of institutional work across SIE-fields

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
Intermediating	Actors create intermediary organisations that represent them to broader audiences and create internal structures (e.g.	Creating/ maintaining	COOP RE France, COOP RE Germany, PIE Germany, FS RE Netherlands,	Energy cooperatives, Real-world laboratories	Creating the ‘Energie Partagée Association’ to organise, for example, peer-to-peer exchanges.

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
	develop business models) to strengthen SIE-initiatives		COOP RE Switzerland		<p>Creating the 'Buendnis Buergerenergie e.V.' i.e. a nationwide network organisations to support energy cooperatives.</p> <p>Creating the 'Energiewende Jetzt e.V' i.e. network organisation to support energy cooperatives in 2010.</p> <p>Creating the 'Reallabore der Nachhaltigkeit' network in 2019, providing possibilities to network and create common approaches.</p> <p>Setting up a crowdfunding platform trade organisation.</p> <p>Founding of ADEV, being a pioneer in RE and part of creating cooperative federations.</p>
Lobbying	Actors attempt to influence the decisions, actions, or policies of legislators or member of regulatory agencies	Creating/ maintaining	COOP RE France, COOP RE, Germany, FS RE Netherlands, FS RE Poland, LEE United Kingdom	Energy cooperatives, banks (financial sector), network organisations, not-for-profit organisations	<p>Conducting diverse activities to gain political recognition for the 'citizen energy project' definition.</p> <p>Creating position papers (and other activities) towards influencing the changes of the EEG (German Renewable Energy Source Act) in 2021 to advocate for energy cooperatives.</p>

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
					<p>Lobbying activities from the financial sector against proposed requirement for banks to refer loan rejected entrepreneurs to alternative financier, e.g. crowdfunding platforms.</p> <p>Lobbying activities conducted by Krakowska Elektrownia Społeczna (energy cooperative) to, for example, extend the period for setting discounts for prosumers from 15 to 25 years.</p> <p>Drafting up a Local Electricity Bill and lobbying to get it through parliament. The aim of the Bill is to empower communities to sell their energy directly to local people.</p>
Displaying/ demonstrating	Actors try to demonstrate that sustainable energy is possible by making SIEs work	Creating	COOP RE, Germany, PIE Netherlands, PIE Poland, LEE Switzerland	Energy cooperatives, energy initiatives, local communities	<p>Developing social media campaigns, public information, etc. about energy cooperatives and their work.</p> <p>Experimenting with different roles and expectations through trials of local generation, storage and grid projects (see Aardehuizen), where regulatory institutions are temporarily lifted.</p> <p>Setting up what is considered to be a</p>

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
					<p>successful energy cluster, so called 'ZKlaster' (i.e. bringing together local actors).</p> <p>Conducting pilot projects to develop best practice and know-how around ZEV (collective prosumption) in LEE.</p>
Broadening/ deepening	Actors attempt to make sustainable energy relevant for all (taking it out of the niche)	Creating	CLC Germany	City administrations	Developing participation formats that are considered 'fun' so that citizens of city engage in sustainable energy.
Framing	Actors create narratives for sustainable energy futures and counter-narratives to dominant energy pathways	Creating/ maintaining	CLC Germany, FAFF Netherlands, FAFF Poland, COOP RE Switzerland	City administrations, NGO, social movements	<p>Developing narratives of how cities can play a role in combating climate change, in particular, creating new relations between administrations, citizens and energy initiatives.</p> <p>Conducting research to uncover the links between the university and fossil fuel industry to make students aware of these interlinkages and transform students' norms and values – done by EUR Fossil Free.</p> <p>Framing actions against fossil fuels beyond blocking individual investments to shifting away from fossil fuels, based on COP24 experiences.</p> <p>Framings against the nuclear</p>

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
					industry by the anti-nuclear movement, creating alternative framings and practices surrounding cooperative renewables.
Setting agendas	Actors set agendas to shape SIE-field developments	Maintaining	PIE Germany	Government ministries	Creation of the 'Reallabore' network by the ministry - supporting multi-actor formats but also making sure that agendas are being set around the goals and targets of government bodies.
Changing incumbency from within	Actors become institutional entrepreneurs, carrying out change within incumbent structures	Disrupting	FS RE Poland, LEE Switzerland	Energy initiatives, ministers, politicians	Setting up the 'My Electricity' programme (i.e. subsidy programme for PV) where minister acted as 'spiritus movens' supported by several other actors and organisations. Shaping of the Energy Act between 2013-2018, by politicians involved in LEE.
Pooling	Actors make available and/or channel resources to make SIE activities possible for diverse actors	Creating/ maintaining	FS RE Netherlands, FS RE Poland, COOP RE Switzerland, FS RE United Kingdom	Ministries, individuals, banks, national fund managers	Creation of Invest-NL (a private company financed with public funds) to provide financing for high-risk sustainable energy projects. Combining subsidies and bank loans to broaden the reach of the programme to enable renewable projects as part of the 'Clean Air' programme.

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
					Introducing subsidies for renewables (KEV), enabling energy cooperatives' business models (eventually removed).
Joining forces	Actors come together to create momentum and grow social awareness around SIE issues	Creating, maintaining	FAFF Poland, CLC Switzerland	NGOs, energy initiatives, politicians, campaigners, local groups, associations	Organising joint actions surrounding anti-coal, for example, protests against the special act 'Lex-coal' in 2019. Embedding the EnergieStadt association into the federal Action Programme 2000 and European Energy Award.
Standardising	Actors develop rules, standards, recommendations and strategies to configure SIE-field developments	Creating	LEE France, COOP RE France, PIE Poland, LEE Switzerland, LEE United Kingdom	Ministries, universities, associations linked to LEE, energy initiatives, energy cooperatives, representatives of the renewable industry, parliamentarians, NGOs	Publishing recommendations, including parameters for collective self-consumption as part of a working group created by minister. Developing, spreading and formalising definitions of what is considered a 'citizen energy project'. Developing a strategy for energy clusters based on the analysis of pilot projects, to be considered in the next amendments of the renewable act as part of the KlasterER project. Crafting and publishing a best practice report on LEE, providing guidance, know-how, tools, etc.

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
					Setting up clubs e.g. Energy Local Clubs to standardise an approach to LEE and increase ability to replicate the model.
Labelling	Actors give themselves a similar label so that they can be recognised as being part of the same phenomena, to create standards, methodologies, etc., together	Creating, maintaining	PIE Netherlands, LEE Switzerland	Living labs, prosumption collectives	<p>Building an identity by taking on board the 'living lab' term, such as Buiksloterham living lab to be able to share ideas with other labs and create a common methodology.</p> <p>Building an identity by first, using the term 'self-consumption communities' and then, Zusammenschluss zum Eigenverbrauch (ZEV). The change of terms happened because the latter term was linked with a legal status.</p>
Challenging lawfulness of policy decision	Actors set in motion a judicial review to challenge decisions	Disrupting, maintaining	FAFF Netherlands, FAFF United Kingdom	NGOs, local groups, national groups, individuals, banks (and several others)	<p>Objecting to the 2015/2016 gas extraction plan by filing an application for a judicial review.</p> <p>Objecting to the planned revisions of the National Planning Policy Framework (NPPF).</p>
Professionalising/ gaining authorisation	Actors professionalise initiatives by giving them a legal status and/or authorisation to take on board more roles	Creating	CLC Switzerland, FS RE United Kingdom	Associations, companies	<p>Establishing the association 'Traegerverein EnergieStadt' to be able to manage the energy label and take on board several new roles.</p> <p>Receiving authorisation from the Financial Conduct Authority</p>

Examples of forms of institutional work	Definition	Institutional work conducted	Examples of SIE-field/ country	Examples of the actors conducting the work	Examples of illustrative evidence
					to become crowdfunding platform for renewables.
Regulating and legislating	Actors bring in new legislations and regulations to influence developments	Creating/ maintaining	LEE France, FAFF United Kingdom	Ministers, governments, regulators	<p>Deliberating governmental changes around LEE with the CRE (French Electricity Regulatory Commission), which is reluctant to make changes that impact on the current energy system.</p> <p>Introducing the Infrastructure Act, which, for example, introduced a new definition of fracking. Although there is a referendum on fracking, because of the definition, onshore oil and gas exploration have continued.</p>
Protesting	Actors physically try to stop 'business as usual' in the energy sector	Disrupting	FAFF United Kingdom	NGOs, local groups, national groups, campaigners	Protesting at the Pont Valley opencast coalmine to stop the extension of the mine.
Mimicking	Actors look towards other actors and their activities, etc. and attempt to copy them	Creating	CLC France	Energy agency	Setting up the 'Rêve Jura Léman' project to build on the Swiss experience with the European Energy Award (EEA) and assess the possibility to develop a similar award in France.
Linking up	Actors try to link up with other more established initiatives, awards, etc. to gain legitimacy for their own activities	Creating	CLC France	Energy agency, energy initiative	Looking towards linking up 'Ville durable et innovante' label with the established 'Cit'ergie' label so that cities can get both labels awarded at the same time.

As already pointed out above, it is important to keep in mind that not all activities linked to institutional work identified in the SONNET case study work have been presented in Table 5. They represent what the SONNET WP3 researchers have considered to be the 2-4 most important activities for each SIE-field in their countries.

We now turn to reviewing important forms of institutional work involved in each of the SIEs. Different forms of institutional work linked to the development of **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy** (COOP RE) include intermediating, lobbying and displaying/demonstrating to create and maintain institutions. Over the past decade, several SIE-initiatives such as energy cooperatives have been set up and renewable projects have been realised. Initiatives have networked with each other to share experiences and learning. Based on these exchanges the need for **intermediating** between initiatives and with a wider audience (e.g. policy makers) became apparent to be able to share learning, sometimes create common approaches, and to lobby for, for example, regulatory changes. This form of institutional work was carried out in all three countries (France, Germany and Switzerland) but it took a while until it was conducted in Switzerland. Due to the federalist state, at first, SIE-initiatives emerged and developed relatively independently from each other. **Lobbying** has always played a role in COOP RE and can be carried out by SIE-initiatives and/or intermediary organisations. This form of institutional work has become particularly important over the past years, considering that subsidies for renewables have no longer been available. Lobbying has played a crucial role in making policy makers aware of the key role of COOP RE in energy transitions and their ongoing need for support. Policy makers have not been the only audience, but also the wider public that SIE-initiatives have tried to reach through, for example, social media campaigns, **displaying/demonstrating** what COOP RE is about and able to do. There is also increasingly the need to demonstrate that projects deliver on expected aims, such as democratising the energy system, to be able to gain support for future developments.

The development of **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF) has been characterised by several forms of institutional work such as framing and protesting. In addition to other activities, developing counternarratives to dominant fossil fuel ones (**framing**) and physically stopping business as usual at, for example, extraction and exploration sites (**protesting**) are core activities involved in FAFF. These forms of institutional work are about creating and disrupting institutions, i.e. creating countervailing social norms and values and disrupting what are considered 'normal' practices, e.g. extracting coal. Over the past years, **joining forces** across local, national and international anti-fossil fuel groups and organisations has also played an important role in gaining legitimacy, pooling resources and creating momentum. In particular in Poland, joining forces has made it possible to develop and emphasise counternarratives to fossil fuel energy pathways. In addition, **challenging lawfulness of decisions** through, for example, judicial review has become a way to fight policy changes, decisions and strategies. This has happened more on the grounds of arguing that ambitious climate targets cannot be achieved by continuing with fossil fuel explorations and extractions. Forms of institution work are therefore not only connected with creating and disrupting institutions, but also maintaining institutions linked to climate change. FAFF also highlights that not only SIE-field-actors conduct institutional work but also other field-actors. **Regulating and legislating** has been a way to control and contain work conducted by SIE-field-actors in order to maintain existing institutions that keep the fossil fuel industry going. The work carried out by other field-actors has been less of a focus within the case study work, but still emerged in some of the fieldwork.

Forms of institutional work linked to **Local electricity exchange** (LEE) seems to be extremely diverse: lobbying, displaying/demonstrating, changing incumbency from within, standardising, labelling and regulating/legislating. The SIE-field is still emerging in all three countries; **lobbying** work is therefore key to change existing regulations and make local electricity exchange possible in highly regulated energy systems (see e.g. the Local Electricity Bill in the United Kingdom). In addition, **standardising, labelling and displaying/demonstrating** work is important to define what the SIE-field is about (so actors can recognise it) and gain legitimacy, showing that projects can work and can create a variety of benefits. In all three countries, different forms of LEE have emerged, and it is still widely debated what LEE is, who might benefit from it, and how. Actors within the SIE-field are therefore both creating and disrupting institutions. In Switzerland, SIE-field-actors that make up LEE have been able to create and/or transform institutions by shaping the developments of the Energy Act and making it more favourable for LEE, i.e. **changing incumbency from within**. In the case of France, policy makers and regulators have conducted institutional work in the form of **regulating/legislating** to contain and control LEE activities both by maintaining existing institutions and in part impeding the emergence of the SIE-field.

Like in LEE, within the SIE-field called **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC) forms of institutional work are diverse: broadening/deepening, framing, joining forces, professionalising/gaining authorisation, mimicking and linking up. **Framing** has been one of the forms of institutional work that has been key to create a narrative around the changing role of city administrations, playing an active role in local energy and climate change issues and collaborating with several actors in these endeavours (such as citizen groups). In the process, work is conducted **broadening/deepening** networks, formats and participation to make energy 'relevant' for all citizens. It might not be surprising to see **mimicking, joining forces** and **linking up** being carried out in CLC. The participation in the European Energy Award and creation of city networks (such as Convent of Majors) have allowed cities to network and learn from each other, allowing for processes of standardisation surrounding CLC (including competition formats and impact measures) across the countries studied in SONNET. In France, there are even attempts to link up new labels with existing awards, potentially easing their legitimisation process. Development of CLC has mainly been characterised by creating institutions based on developing, for example, formats, narratives and measures, partly disrupting 'business as usual' work on energy and climate change within city administrations.

Seeing that the core activities of **Participatory Incubation and Experimentation** (PIE) are incubation and experimentation, it might be no surprise to see that one form of institutional work is about **displaying/demonstrating**, i.e. showing that sustainable energy is possible. This can entail implementing local generation, storage and grid projects in the Netherlands and Poland. In addition, **labelling** and **standardising** have been important to create common approaches, methodologies, etc. under a common label/name. For instances, in Germany, the creation of the Reallabore ('real-life laboratory') name and a network (supported by one German ministry) has been a way to create legitimacy, attract attention, and share learning and methodologies that work. The network was considered important as an **intermediary** between the labs. The effect has been to strengthen and broaden the notion of a real-life laboratory, encourage networking between members and communicate about the lab approach. The set-up of the network was supported by one of the German ministries, who was then able to contribute to **setting the agenda** of the network, shaping the development of the SIE-field. Much of the work in this SIE-field is about creating institutions.

The SIE-field **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE) has most clearly shown that SIE-field-actors are not only made up of energy initiatives and NGOs, but also policymakers and industry actors. As FS RE is still a very recent phenomena in Poland, some policymakers and politician have played a key role in **changing incumbency from within**, lobbying for policy changes to make renewable energy projects possible (e.g. setting up particular energy programmes). In addition, **lobbying** has been a core activity in Poland. For example, energy cooperatives have been able to amend energy laws based on their lobbying activities such as introducing a definition of collective presumption and making it possible to set up energy cooperatives in cities. The SIE-field has a long history in the Netherlands and in the United Kingdom, with the introduction of subsidies leading to the need to develop more market-based approaches. Lots of work has gone into lobbying against such policy changes. Work has gone into finding alternative business models, sometimes leading to work in the form of **pooling**: for example, combining financial options to finance projects (such as banks loans and subsidies) and setting up financing for high-risk projects. Due to loss of subsidies, crowdfunding has started to become a way to finance energy activities. This has meant conducting **intermediating**, lobbying and **gaining authorisation** work to organise and fully legalise these activities. For instance, in the Netherlands, there was a need to set up a crowdfunding trade organisation, while in the United Kingdom, the Financial Conduct Authority needed to authorise crowdfunding platforms for renewables. Institutional work in this SIE-field was a mix between maintaining and creating institutions.

REFLECTIONS ON INSTITUTIONAL WORK CONDUCTED WITHIN SIE-FIELDS

It is important to keep in mind that this is only a selection of forms of institutional work conducted in the SIE-fields. Our results are based on what researchers have considered to be the most important instances of diverse forms of institutional work being carried out in the SIE-field within their country.

Much of the institutional work conducted in SIE-fields is about **creating** institutions. This might not be surprising, seeing that SIEs often create alternative ways of 'doing, thinking and organising' energy for which regulative, cultural-cognitive and normative institutions still need to be developed. Some of the SIE-fields have already had a longer history and some institutions (for instance, regulations and normative institutions) have already been created and more widely adopted, which has brought about institutional work linked to **maintaining** these institutions. At the same time, maintaining institutions can be carried out by more established energy actors (such as energy producers) trying to lobby against changes that threaten their activities. Looking across Table 5, work linked with **disrupting** institutions appears to be rarer. This might be more a matter of definition. Seeing that creating institutions may undermine existing norms and beliefs within energy systems, it might be possible to suggest that creating and disrupting institutions can be interlinked. We have currently defined disrupting as a form of resistance, e.g. protesting and challenging policy decisions.

Looking across the countries and the SIE-fields, what becomes apparent is that forms of **institutional work might also co-evolve with the stages of institutionalisation of SIE-fields**. They can therefore vary between countries and SIE-fields. For example, LEE is still emerging in the studied countries, making work such as lobbying, standardising

and labelling necessary for the further development of the SIE-field. In SIE-fields with a longer history, work such as intermediating and displaying/demonstrating might become more essential. Still, it might be hard to generalise and divide forms of institutional work in accordance with the stage of institutionalisation. For example, lobbying might still be key in the emergence and development of SIE-fields (for instance, when considering that policy changes can influence the development of SIE-fields throughout institutionalisation processes). Moreover, **forms of institutional work might depend on how far the development of the SIE-fields challenges existing energy systems and/or the current direction of the energy transition.** For example, FAFF aims to challenge fossil fuel-based energy pathways and existing energy systems, requiring different forms of institutional work to PIE, which is more actively supported by a wide range of energy and innovation actors within energy transitions.

4.3.5 Processes of institutionalisation across SIE-fields – processes

In SONNET, we want to investigate the dynamic interactions between SIE and broader institutional dynamics towards transformative change (see, e.g. Haxeltine et al., 2017). Therefore, SONNET does not only analyse SIE-fields and their SIE but also dominant institutions in the energy sector (e.g. existing regulations, routines, practices, ways of thinking, social norms on how to consume and produce energy). As social innovations develop over time and space, they transform/disrupt institutions (e.g. normative beliefs around how energy is produced), while at the same time they also inevitably reproduce them (e.g. gender issues reproduced by mainly men getting involved in setting up energy cooperatives). Looking across sections 4.3.1 and 4.3.4 and drawing on the work of new institutionalism, it is possible to examine the interrelations between actors/groups, their interactions, changes in social relations, institutions shaping SIE and institutional work to be able to better understand these processes of institutionalisation of SIE-fields and their SIE. Such processes are of interest because they provide us with a way of understanding how SIE and associated regulations, social norms, values and belief systems become taken for granted (or not) over time, and in the processes change existing energy systems (or not). We have defined 'institutionalisation' as *"a process by which a pattern of activities comes to be held in place, and practically taken for granted within a field"* (Wittmayer et al., 2021:34).

4.3.5.1 Understanding processes and degrees of institutionalisation

The work of Mioerner et al., (2021) and Fuenfschilling and Truffer (2014) has pointed to the need to understand the degree of institutionalisation of socio-technical configurations (such as social innovation in energy) to be able to understand their transformative capacity. These authors consider institutionalisation to be a process. To understand this process, it is relevant to consider the agency of actors working on the SIE; the creation of SIE that 'work' and their institutionalisation process; the multiple SIEs that might co-exist alongside each other (and their relations); and the de-institutionalisation of existing energy systems and their configurations (Mioerner et al., 2021). In addition, Mioerner et al., (2021) have identified five key dimensions to

examine degrees of institutionalisation: 1) *time*, based on the assumption that SIE becomes more taken for granted and legitimate with time (i.e. increasing the degree of institutionalisation); 2) *scope of diffusion*, that can be interpreted as more institutionalised SIEs forming part of several systems (beyond energy) and/or with a broader geographical spread; 3) *vulnerability/invulnerability to intervention*, i.e. levels of resilience towards institutional changes such as changes in regulations and societal critique; 4) *starkness*, i.e. to what extent SIEs are contested and/or legitimised by multiple actors; and 5) *materialisation and translation*, i.e. to what extent the SIE is actualised in material and formal forms such as regulations, standards, or infrastructures. For a more detailed description of these dimensions see Mioerner et al., (2021).

In the next section, we aim to explore the degrees of institutionalisation of each SIE-field and their SIE. Seeing that we have not systematically conducted data collection and analysis linked to the above five dimensions of institutionalisation, this is an explorative exercise to gain first insights into this phenomenon. The next section looks at each SIE-field in turn and provides some key differences between countries.

4.3.5.2 Comparing degrees on institutionalisation in the SIE-fields - an initial exploration

Looking across the studied SIE-fields, it might be possible to argue that **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy** (COOP RE) has a higher degree of institutionalisation than some of the other SIE-fields. This is partly due to the number of realised projects and their materialisation of renewable energy installations across the studied countries. In addition, the cooperative model (and nowadays also its combination with renewable energy) builds on a long history (in particular in Germany and Switzerland), having gained increasing legitimacy even in other sectors such as housing. Based on our fieldwork, it also becomes apparent that SIE-field-actors have been able to widen and broaden the actors involved in COOP RE, demonstrating that the SIE has gained legitimacy over time. For example, banks and insurance companies have increasingly become SIE-field-actors, supporting and creating the SIE. Still, it might not be possible to talk about a high degree of institutionalisation, seeing that some of the, for example, financial models linked to COOP RE have been extremely vulnerable over the past decade due to their reliance on state policies and subsidies. Cuts to these subsidies meant that most SIE-initiatives had to change their financial models to make upcoming projects work. This has not been a straightforward journey and a time where projects had to be postponed and/or abandoned before being able to find alternative models. The resilience of these new models is yet to be seen. In addition, the key forms of institutional work conducted as part of COOP RE – intermediating, lobbying, and displaying/demonstrating – demonstrate that SIE-field-actors are still involved in creating legitimacy for the SIE and (re)developing certain components of the SIE (such as financial models) that work. Further research might need to go into how SIEs have changed over time as part of the institutionalisation process (where alternative SIE configurations have not been taken up); for example, considering whether SIE-initiatives have been able to hold onto their original aims and visions and whether transformative ambitions have been realised.

The SIE-field **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF) shows that processes of institutionalisation and deinstitutionalisation are closely interlinked with each other. The SIE-field COOP RE could emerge and develop over time because of increasing support for renewables.

COOP RE benefitted from these subsidies at the same time as broader shifts towards renewable energy occurred in Europe's energy systems. Within FAFF, these interlinkages between developing the SIE and changing the current energy mix make up the aims and activities of SIE-field-actors themselves: they create an SIE (i.e. framings against fossil fuel) whilst at the same time trying to deinstitutionalise existing socio-technical configurations within the fossil fuel industry. It is therefore questionable what is being institutionalised, and/or whether the question might be more about the deinstitutionalisation of existing socio-technical configurations (e.g. the extraction of coal). In the Netherlands and the United Kingdom, SIE-field-actors draw on a long history of social mobilisations by anti-fossil fuel and environmental movements. This means that activities linked to the SIE could evolve and establish themselves over time, such as the creation of camps as a form of protest in the United Kingdom. Materialisations in the form of camps, roadblocks, etc. are short-lived but have become more sophisticated over time. Other forms of materialisation such as how-to guides, advocacy work towards regulatory changes and documentations of activities on the internet have created more permanency.

FAFF has been able to gain support due to the increasing social legitimacy of broader social and environmental groups, such as Fridays for Future (i.e. international climate change movement); in fact, it is sometimes starting to be taken for granted as part of developments towards a more sustainable Europe. Still, the development of the SIE-field is vulnerable towards regulatory changes. Regulations have supported a 'business as usual' attitude towards fossil fuel exploration and experimentation projects. This has happened, for example, through policing protests and criminalisation of anti-fossil fuel activities. Still, the role of regulations has become more ambivalent, considering the changing policy environment for fossil fuels linked to climate change policies. For example, in the Netherlands, government support for fossil fuels has been decreasing for societal and economic reasons and climate change goals, increasingly creating an environment in which the SIE can become more institutionalised. This is not necessarily the case in Poland and the United Kingdom (although ambitious climate change goals have been legislated). FAFF has gained more legitimacy over the past decade, which might demonstrate a higher degree of institutionalisation. But seeing that processes of institutionalisation and deinstitutionalisation are highly interlinked in this SIE-field, it might be questionable to think about the transformative capacity of the SIE-field only linked to processes of institutionalisation. Future work might need to look more closely at interlinkages between institutionalisation and deinstitutionalisation processes in relation to SIEs.

Considering the emergence and development of the studied SIE-fields it becomes apparent that **Local electricity exchange** (LEE) is still at the early stages of institutionalisation. This already emerged when we tried to define the boundaries of the SIE-field before and during the fieldwork, as initial research uncovered several socio-technical configurations, making it difficult to define the SIE linked to this SIE-field. Several SIEs make up the SIE-field (such as different forms of peer-to-peer exchange), sometimes developing in collaboration and/or competition with each other. This points to discussions and contestations of what 'local electricity exchange' might actually be about. Several actors are involved in the SIE-field, often with different aims and interests in developing the SIE, which means there is support for it but also no clarity regarding what it should look like and what it should do. In France, fewer SIEs could be identified, partly due to the government actively 'controlling' the development of SIE through regulations. The SIE-field and SIEs have been highly vulnerable to regulations, seeing that regulatory changes are required to develop the SIEs. Therefore, governments and regulators have created spaces where existing

regulatory frameworks are lifted for certain periods of time to identify impeding factors and how to overcome them. Materialisations of the SIEs that make up LEE are therefore often temporary and still at the experimentation stage. In Switzerland, the organisational model surrounding the SIE has been more widely applied but standards are still not binding. Even the key forms of institutional work linked to the SIE-field remain extremely diverse, from lobbying to standardising, which might be an additional indication of a lower degree of institutionalisation, seeing that SIE-field-actors are still busy maintaining, creating and disrupting multiple institutions.

The institutionalisation of **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC) has been characterised by a supportive policy environment in which the SIE-field and its SIE could develop, and recognition of the role of cities in energy transitions. This might demonstrate that the process of institutionalisation can look different for SIEs, depending on how they 'fit' (or not) into existing changes of the energy system. 'Fit' means in how far actors need to change (or not) existing institutions to be able to institutionalise their SIE. Much of the work within CLC has gone into making the SIE 'work' (finding an SIE that works in the current 'outside' institutional environment) rather than 'fit' (creating an SIE that requires changes to the 'outside' institutional environment so that it can work). SIE-field-actors could make CLC work mainly by broadening the relevance of the SIE, developing common standards, and so on. Awards (e.g. set up by the EU) have been useful to create quality management and certifications systems based on common standards and rules to be able to determine whether city administrations can obtain them. Seeing that the EU has initiated an award across EU countries, the spread and coherence of CLC has been enabled and supported across some countries. In Switzerland, there is a longer history of CLC where the EnergieStadt label became the standard means to advance CLC. The processes connected to this label have been formalised and standardised over the past years, making little room for alternative developments. In France and Germany, CLC remains more heterogenous in terms of actors, standards, and so on. It might be possible to suggest that some degree of institutionalisation has been achieved, whilst the SIE-field is still in the process of institutionalisation.

Because **Participatory incubation and experimentation** (PIE) is based on experiments, the institutionalisation process might look slightly different than within other SIE-fields. These are often time-bound experiments, which means some of their materialisations can be rather short lived (such as a peer-to-peer energy exchange trials). Permanency is created based on developing formats, best practices, how-to guides and interlinkages between experiments that have developed over time. Similarly, the creation of institutions is a main aim derived from conducting these experimentations (i.e. developing regulations around smart energy developments), and with them the potential for future large-scale infrastructure projects. The creation of such experimental spaces has been widely legitimised in Germany and the Netherlands and more recently in Poland, seeing that diverse actors have engaged in energy transitions where such spaces are recognised as key to develop novel socio-technical configuration of possible future systems. A more recent development of widening the pool of actors (such as citizens) involved in these experiments has allowed the emergence of practices that move beyond triple helix collaborations. This has also increased the likelihood of discussions and contestations, where techno-optimistic and market-logics have nonetheless often prevailed. It seems the SIE-field is widely legitimate but that particular formats, actor constellations and roles of experiments are still in development.

Looking across the SIE-field **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FFS RE) within the three countries, it becomes apparent that several potentially competing, evolving and changing SIEs have made up the SIE-field. Several financial mechanisms and subsidies have existed alongside each other and/or replaced each other (signified by a more general move from subsidies to investments). National governments and their policies have been key in shaping the SIE-field, partly 'controlling' the scope of diffusion of certain SIE and their materialisation. Contestations and lobbying activities have often been linked to policy changes surrounding FS RE (such as the withdrawal of feed-in-tariffs). On the one hand, it is possible to argue that the SIE-field has been vulnerable to policy interventions. On the other hand, it is possible to argue that the existence of competing, evolving and changing SIEs have been key to find socio-technical configurations linked to financing renewables that work within a market oriented energy sector. Although several renewable energy projects could not be realised after subsidies were stopped, local governments and citizens began to play an increasing role in FS RE (alongside other actors such as institutional investors), broadening the idea of financing renewables. Several processes of institutionalisation of SIEs seem to be happening within FS RE, representing differing degrees of institutionalisation (with some no longer existing at all, demonstrating that deinstitutionalisation processes also play a role). The forms of institutional work (e.g. lobbying, pooling, intermediating) that have been conducted also illustrate that the SIEs are still developing.

REFLECTIONS ON PROCESSES AND DEGRESS OF INSTITUTIONALISATION

This section has been an initial exploration of the notion of processes/degrees of institutionalisation in different SIE-fields. This will be taken up in future SONNET work, in particular WPI, where the conceptual work takes place. Based on this exploration, the following initial reflections can be summarised:

- ✦ Europe's energy systems and associated institutions are in transition; SIE-fields and their SIE have therefore emerged in a changing institutional environment. This has also shaped the processes and degrees of institutionalisation of SIE. SIEs emerge in a changing energy system, which means to be able to create SIEs that work, they need to be able to adapt to the changing energy systems or actively shape it over time.
- ✦ When investigating the emergence and development of SIE-fields rather than mainly focusing on SIE-initiatives, it becomes apparent that several SIEs can evolve alongside and/or replace each other (see, for example, FS RE). Their interrelations can look different, from competition and replacement to development and evolution. In particular, policy changes have been key, because SIEs that used to work need to be developed and perhaps changed to survive in the new policy environment.
- ✦ It might be possible to differentiate between SIE that work within, try to create a fit with, and work against 'outside' institutional environments. For example, PIE is widely legitimate because the SIE is often linked to supporting existing energy pathways. COOP RE need to create a fit with the existing energy system and

policy environment, working on organisational and financial models that partly changed and fitted in existing systems. Meanwhile, FAFF explicitly opposes other aspects of existing energy systems and policy environments.

- ✦ As part of transitions, deinstitutionalisation processes play as important a role as institutionalisation processes. Sometimes, such processes are also part of the main aim of the SIE-field such as FAFF. This might not be a surprise seeing that the creation of new institutions is often linked to the disruption of existing ones. Transitions usually imply the shift of existing 'outside' institutional environments.

4.3.6 Towards policy mixes promoting social innovation in energy

In this final sub-section, we zoom in on the role of policies and policy making processes for the development of SIE-fields. For this, we analyse the case study findings through the lens of policy mixes for sustainability transitions (Rogge and Reichardt 2016; Rogge et al., 2017). In the context of our study, we define policy mixes of relevance for social innovation in the energy sector as encompassing policy mix elements (namely policy strategies and instrument mixes) at different governance levels and policy fields, which enable or impede the development of social innovation in the energy sector, and have developed incrementally over many years through policy processes. Given the nature of our analysis, we focus on the main policy mix elements and associated policy making processes at different governance levels, such as the RED II EU directive (second renewable energy directive) and its transposition into national law, or regional innovation funding for real world laboratories. These policies have been identified in our SONNET case studies on diverse SIE-fields by foregrounding policy strategies and instruments which influence the activities of SIE-actors. By following such a bottom-up approach we capture the perspective of SIE-field actors and what they would consider as the most relevant policies. Our analysis reveals that it may be useful to speak of SIE-field specific policy mixes - similarly to technology-specific policies - rather than to derive generic policy mix insights that apply across various SIE-fields. Therefore, our analysis is structured by SIE-fields. For each SIE-field we present and compare the main insights across three countries, thereby indicating patterns of similarity and difference between countries within six SIE-fields. This analysis complements our findings on the role of regulative institutions (see 4.3.3.2) and institutional work (4.3.4) by foregrounding the role of policy and politics for sustainable energy transitions in general and social innovation in energy in particular.

4.3.6.1 What is the role of policy mixes for the development of SIE?

For the SIE-field **Cooperative Organisational Models for Renewable Energy** (COOP RE) which we analysed in Germany, France and Switzerland (see Table 6), our study shows the importance of predictable national energy policy support for providing long-term investment security. While initially national energy policy instruments have provided such predictability, the national policy support for the SIE-field has declined substantially in all studied countries. However, the concrete policy design and changes to it over time differ across countries. For example, while in France the support focused on large scale projects, the German feed-in tariff model also supported small-

scale investments. When looking at the politics behind the policy mix and its changes, we find that the EU governance level has been an influential driver for national support schemes in EU member states. The decline in policy support - partly under the disguise of economic efficiency - underlines the long-term nature of resistance from incumbent actors, but has also led to the formation and organisation of SIE-field-actors in intermediary organisations trying to more effectively represent the interests of SIE-field-actors in policy making and implementation processes, even if with mixed success. We also found cross-country evidence that the local governance level is often willing, and partly able, to compensate for policy changes at the national level that impede SIE-field development.

Table 6: Synthesis of key policy mix insights for SIE-field COOP RE

	Germany	France	Switzerland
Policy mix elements	<p>SIE-field development strongly tied to policies on the national level.</p> <p>Renewable Energy Act (EEG) as most important policy (both enabling and - particularly later – also impeding).</p> <p>SIE development influenced by broader policy mix on the national level (e.g. nuclear phase-out, Mieterstromgesetz) and European level (clean energy package).</p>	<p>National policy instruments focusing on large scale projects, to the detriment of small-scale energy cooperatives.</p> <p>Strong dependency of COOP RE on regional support schemes.</p>	<p>National energy policies play key role (initially creation of protected spaces through feed-in remuneration, then decline of support).</p> <p>Gaps at national level partly compensated by enabling local policy support for COOP RE.</p>
Policy making processes	<p>Influence of the European level on national policy making.</p> <p>Policy making in reaction to market developments (reduction of technology costs led to reduction of feed-in tariffs).</p> <p>Impeding policy changes strengthens engagement of intermediaries linked to SIE in energy policy-making processes.</p>	<p>European policies pushing French governments to design policy instruments with some COOP RE support.</p> <p>Unstable policies on national level, switching from briefly enabling to again impeding COOP RE (through introducing constraints), thereby slowing down SIE-field.</p>	<p>Lately, increasing engagement of SIE-field-actors and their newly founded intermediary in national policy making processes (e.g. consultations).</p>

For the SIE-field **Framings against fossil fuel energy pathways** (FAFF), which was investigated in the Netherlands, Poland and in the United Kingdom (see Table 7), we find that a main driver for SIE-field activities is the insufficiency of national policies for meeting the Paris Agreement as the cornerstone of international climate policy. That is, the activities of SIE-field-actors across all three countries are motivated by their national governments not doing enough to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, or even attempting to or succeeding in introducing policy changes that add to the climate crisis: such as by actively pursuing new fossil fuel projects. Or put more generally: we find that inconsistent instrument mixes that are not in line with climate policy strategies are representing a main reason for protesting their governments' chosen fossil fuel pathways. When looking behind the politics of such inconsistent policy mixes, we find national

governments that are promoting the interests of fossil fuel incumbents, but are meeting resistance of SIE-field-actors. Such bottom-up resistance from social movements arises via various channels, such as by SIE-field-actors demonstrating against the nationally chosen fossil fuel pathways, by attempting to influence or cooperate with policy makers and other actors at the local level, by raising their complaints in courts, by participating in funding programs from different governance levels (e.g. EU just transition funds), or by pressuring or collaborating with the private sector and investors.

Table 7: Synthesis of key policy mix insights for SIE-field FAFF

	Netherlands	Poland	United Kingdom
Policy mix elements	<p>Significant changes in policy mix as result of SIE-field activities, including more effective climate policies but also changes in mining act.</p> <p>Policy changes on national and local governance level - divestment framing with broad impact across policies (but also on non-state actors' internal policies), whereas anti-fracking with impact on very specific policies.</p>	<p>Strong impeding role of national government regarding coal phase out (and limited possibilities of action by local authorities).</p> <p>EU policy supporting SIE, but with limited effect (e.g. Just Transition Mechanism so far only successful in one region, with private operator instead of state-owned enterprise).</p>	<p>Changes in planning framework (e.g. localism act, infrastructure act) as driver of SIE-field activities.</p> <p>SIE-field activities legitimised by United Kingdom's climate mitigation commitments under Paris Agreement and Climate Change Act</p> <p>Government commitment to coal phase out in electricity system contrasts with attempted support for shale gas.</p>
Policy making processes	<p>Important role of social movements in policy making process, particularly at local level.</p> <p>Opaque emergence, adaptation and phasing out of governing bodies.</p>	<p>Aim of the SIE-field to influence national policy making, but only very limited lobbying opportunities due to pro-fossil fuel government and lack of pro-environmental MPs.</p> <p>Polish government, under the influence of the mining lobby, has even blocked some of the EU support for just transitions in coal regions.</p> <p>Different (more indirect) forms of political pressure (e.g. through organising local referenda, writing petitions to the European Parliament, pushing finance sector to withdraw).</p>	<p>National level reducing power of local level in infrastructure decision-making, in attempt to push forward government agenda, but meeting local resistance.</p> <p>Conservative party keen on accelerating infrastructure projects, without real opposition from the Labour party.</p> <p>Scotland and Wales tend to be more climate progressive and opposed to national level policy making.</p>

For the SIE-field **Local electricity exchange** (LEE), which we studied in France, the United Kingdom and Switzerland (see Table 8), we find that national energy policies tend to impede the development of this SIE-field and that this is often done intentionally to avoid the disruptive potential of peer-to-peer electricity exchange. EU level policies are not helping the SIE-field as the lack of clear and SIE-field specific regulatory guidance contributes to regulatory uncertainty. Our

analysis of the politics behind the policy mix elements clearly shows the highly contested nature of this SIE-field in which actors have polarised perspectives. However, there are some novel policy proposals which, if adopted, would enable the further development of the SIE-field.

Table 8: Synthesis of key policy mix insights for SIE-field LEE

	France	United Kingdom	Switzerland
Policy mix elements	<p>National policies intentionally slowing down SIE development to reduce disruptive potential.</p> <p>Unstable policy frameworks with changing definitions of collective self-consumption.</p>	<p>National context is key (particularly regulatory framework) and built around "supplier hub model" which is challenged by LEE.</p> <p>Apart from electricity regulation other important policies include subsidy schemes for renewables.</p> <p>At EU level regulatory uncertainty as no specific regulation on peer-to-peer trading (but regulatory openness for it).</p>	<p>Several national policies setting rather impeding framework conditions (e.g. Energy Act, Electricity Supply Act, Tenant Law): use of the local distribution grid and selecting a supplier for end-customers currently not allowed.</p> <p>Profitability of projects partly determined by level of grid fee for self-consumption.</p>
Policy making processes	<p>Finance ministry, regulatory bodies and established actors controlling LEE emergence.</p> <p>In contrast, ministry of environment and parliamentarians supporting LEE.</p>	<p>Polarised perspectives on peer-to-peer electricity trading as contested field.</p> <p>Proposed policy changes with potential to change power balance in electricity system (e.g. Local Electricity Bill, multiple supplier proposition).</p> <p>Changing policy discourse from community energy to local energy.</p>	<p>Typical Swiss deliberative policy making process ("Vernehmlassungsverfahren"), including consultation to produce "referendum-proof" bills.</p>

For the SIE-field of **City level competitions for sustainable energy** (CLC), which we investigated in Germany, France and Switzerland (see Table 9), we find that local level policies are at the heart of developments. However, national level policies are also identified as playing a role for setting the expected direction of competitions and providing funding. Interestingly, we find that some local level policies not only implement but exceed national expectations, showcasing greater levels of climate protection or energy transition ambitions. When looking at the policy making and implementation processes, we find that learning through best-practices can stimulate more ambitious local level energy policies. We also find that policy making at the local level can be both enabled and inhibited by the national governance level.

Table 9: Synthesis of key policy mix insights for SIE-field CLC

	Germany	France	Switzerland
Policy mix elements	<p>Policy support for city-level competitions from national level (e.g. funding by ministries).</p> <p>National climate policy regulations considered as too weak, implying local policies face challenge of stimulating voluntary actions.</p>	<p>National level policies influence competition themes in CLC.</p>	<p>Some national policy strategies and instruments enabling SIE-field development (e.g. by highlighting EnergieStadt label as lighthouse project).</p> <p>Labelling primarily influences energy policies on the local level (e.g. local procurement of renewable energy in municipal buildings).</p> <p>Introduction of new local energy policies reinforce SIE-field by new cities joining labelling scheme.</p>
Policy making processes	<p>Competitions between cities enable assessment of local climate and energy policies via highlighting best-practice.</p> <p>City level competitions as search for new instruments on the local level.</p> <p>Cities lobbying for more ambitious national level energy and climate policies.</p>	<p>Local level policy change: comparisons across cities can yield reallocation of city resources to improve climate performance.</p> <p>Some SIE-initiatives aim at supporting cities in designing energy and climate policies.</p>	<p>EnergieStadt label influences energy policy making at the local level (e.g. in municipal processes, or providing direction).</p> <p>National long-term policy strategy (Energy Strategy 2050) making energy topic more relevant overall, thus increasing expectations on municipal administrations to advance local energy transitions, in turn leading to greater label uptake.</p>

For the SIE-field **Participatory incubation and experimentation** (PIE), which we studied for the Netherlands, Germany and Poland (see Table 10), we find that EU policy strategies with their climate and energy transition targets are particularly important for SIE-field activities in countries with low climate mitigation ambitions. EU funding for various forms of experimentation is also found to be an enabling policy instrument more generally. We further find that the main policy mix element enabling the SIE-field development are national policy instruments that provide funding for experimentation, whether they originate from energy, innovation, or other ministries. This supportive policy mix, however, focuses on supporting novelty creation only, while how to scale up successful experiments remains a major challenge across countries. Indeed, it is unclear whether and how learning from such experiments will lead to changes in the broader policy mix. It should also be noted that some countries (e.g. the Netherlands) are more open to the co-creative approaches utilised in many energy transition experiments, while the more top-down policy style in other countries (e.g. Poland) implies some difficulties with supporting such forms of participatory incubation and experimentation.

Table 10: Synthesis of key policy mix insights for SIE-field PIE

	Netherlands	Germany	Poland
Policy mix elements	<p>Main policy support for experimentation from innovation and environmental policy fields, with highest funding (and thus influence) from national level.</p> <p>Change of focus of experimentation policies to allow participation of new actors and activities.</p>	<p>Mainly driven by (energy) innovation policies supporting experimentation.</p> <p>Policy support from national and European level particularly relevant.</p>	<p>EU climate and renewables targets and policy support key for directing some national energy policies towards more sustainability.</p> <p>National level policy instruments of relevance for PIE include the introduction of energy clusters.</p>
Policy making processes	<p>Policy style characterised by close science-policy interface, enabling co-creation of experimentation policies.</p> <p>Unclear to which extent policy learnings from experiments are leading to changes in the policy mix.</p>	<p>Integrated policy approaches promoting social and technological innovation hampered by silo thinking of different national level ministries.</p> <p>Challenge of systematic policy learning from experimental approaches remains to be tackled.</p>	<p>Important role of European level policies as driver for implementing national policies supporting renewable energies and energy clusters.</p> <p>Policies that influence the SIE-field also contribute to bringing Polish law closer to the existing law of other Member States.</p>

Finally, for the SIE-field **Financing and subsidies for renewable energy** (FS RE), in which our analysis focused on solar PV and wind energy in the Netherlands, Poland and the United Kingdom (see Table 11), we find that national energy policies are key for the development of the SIE-field. However, recent changes mean they tend to be insufficient and at times even detrimental for SIE-field development, despite an initially enabling start. In general, EU level policies tend to drive national energy policies in EU member states to become more enabling for the SIE-field, so further policy mix changes can be expected. Looking at the politics behind the observed policy mix changes indicates the influence of lobbying by incumbents, especially when it comes to the national implementation of EU-level policies. This partly explains the deterioration of the policy mix for the SIE-field, including investment uncertainty arising from the instability of the policy mix, but also why well-intended policies may suffer from detrimental policy implementation.

Table 11: Synthesis of key policy mix insights for SIE-field FS RE

	Netherlands	Poland	United Kingdom
Policy mix elements	<p>National Energy Agreement as main policy influencing the SIE-field (formalised the importance of (financial) citizen engagement in the energy transition).</p> <p>Influential EU level policies include First Energy Directive (1996) and Treaty of Amsterdam (1997).</p>	<p>National level policies key but insufficient and contradictory (e.g. Renewables Act vs "Anti-Wind Turbine Act")</p> <p>So far, SIE-field strongly impeded by national policies (e.g. regulatory barriers)</p>	<p>National policies most important for the SIE-field (e.g. subsidies, funds, tax relief structures, regulations), but instability problematic for investor confidence (e.g. feed-in tariffs were enabling, but then cut unexpectedly).</p> <p>Overall, national policy changes after 2012/14 tended to limit the ability of</p>

	Netherlands	Poland	United Kingdom
			<p>SIE-field developments (e.g. crowdfunding platforms suffered from sudden cuts in subsidies).</p> <p>Impact of Smart Export Guarantee scheme (replace feed-in-tariff scheme) on investments in renewable technology and reductions in carbon emissions remains to be seen.</p>
Policy making processes	<p>Drafting of Energy Agreement involved deliberation with actors from many societal spheres (i.e. banks, NGOs, governments, grid operators, utilities, energy cooperatives).</p> <p>National policy has to be implemented by local and regional authorities, who are prone to lobbying due to limited time, knowledge or will for implementing energy transition.</p>	<p>EU policies (e.g. climate targets and second renewable directive) as main driver for some SIE beneficial policy change.</p> <p>Attempts from various actors to influence EU policy transposition (RED II - second renewable energy Directive) on national level to ensure better conditions for (collective) prosumers.</p> <p>Close entanglement of government and state-owned energy companies.</p>	<p>Unexpected changes and instability in national policies challenging for investors.</p>

REFLECTIONS ON POLICY MIXES RELEVANT FOR SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY

Our exploration of the role of policy mixes for social innovation in energy investigated six different SIE-fields, each in three different European countries, and enabled new insights on governing social innovation. We argue that these speak directly to the emerging debate about the need for comprehensive innovation policy targeting both technological and social innovation (Howaldt, Kopp and Schwartz, 2015). We want to highlight the following points for future engagement with policy makers on the role of policies supporting social innovation - for energy, but also beyond.

First, our analysis revealed that social innovation is such a diverse phenomenon that it is unlikely that only generic policies promoting social innovation could be recommended. While there may be some generic features of a policy mix promoting social innovation, they most likely need to be adjusted to the specific context of a given SIE-field, while at the same time paying attention to the specific country context. Indeed, similarly to the call for technology-specific instruments it may be useful to think of field-specific social innovation policies.

Second, the limited attention to social innovation in policy mixes suggests that we may be just in the emergence phase; much policy learning may still be needed to reach a stage where policy makers design policy mixes that specifically consider the

particularities of social innovation in energy. Preceding such comprehensive policy mix design would be the enhancement of policy makers' understanding of social innovation as a phenomenon, and of its interplay with technological innovation. For now, it seems rather a well-intended but not fully grasped concept that has made it into some policy circles but still requires more critical engagement and assessment of required changes in policy making. The policy mix thinking applied here may be a useful steppingstone towards this requirement.

Finally, a striking finding was the lack of social policy in our bottom-up policy mix assessment, i.e. policies not enacted by energy or innovation ministries but from the domain of social policy, such as the provision of energy-related unemployment benefits. We therefore argue it may be useful for energy and innovation policy makers to get together with social policy experts and jointly discuss the promotion of social innovation. There may also be the need for further collaboration in monitoring, evaluating and adjusting corresponding policy mixes relevant for social innovation in energy.

4.4 Working propositions

Based on our analysis across section 4, we have developed the following working propositions. Working propositions are initial statements about different aspects of SIE-fields and their SIE. They are thus preliminary explanations and provide insights into answers to our research questions. These will be further developed and help to advance the conceptual work in WPI.

Relations between actors in energy systems:

- ✦ The changing social relations of SIE manifest through a reconfiguration and/or hybridisation of institutional logics by SIE-field-actors and/or in actor constellations (such as hybrid organisational forms) – these integrate elements of state and community logics whilst often also continuing to be also rooted in market logics.
- ✦ Some SIE-field-actors take up existing roles and remake them in the process, while in other cases new roles are being created through the emergence and development of SIE.
- ✦ The entrance of new actors (in existing and new roles) in the energy system challenges existing actors' roles and actor constellations and leads to their diversification and localisation.
- ✦ Cooperation between SIE-field-actors (from differing institutional logics) is important for the emergence and development for most SIE-fields in the form of networking and sharing learning and knowledge – through dedicated networks and intermediary organisations, or informal structures and formats.

Relations between SIE-fields and/ or SIEs:

- ✦ Several forms of SIEs alongside each other within an SIE-field can complement each other but also indicate contestation of what the SIE should be about and how it should look. The emergence of SIE is therefore linked with actors' aims and interests and in how far they complement each other (or not), including issues of politics and power.

- ▲ SIE-fields vary in the extent to which they fit into the existing energy systems and their transitions (or not). Some SIE-fields and their actors therefore challenge existing institutions more than others. The speed and direction of transitions is partly determined in how far SIE-field actors are able to create and challenge/disrupt institutions and hold onto their original aims when developing the SIE.

Interrelations between actors and institutions:

- ▲ Techno-optimist approaches and market-based perspectives seem to prevail in most energy systems and their transitions; still, SIE-field-actors have created spaces in which heterogeneous social norms, values and belief systems can come together to work on energy, develop alternative energy practices and visions and transform public perceptions surrounding particular energy pathways.
- ▲ To bring about institutional change, SIE-field-actors create new institutions based on developing alternative ways of 'doing, thinking and organising' energy. Once such institutions are created, they often challenge/disrupt existing institutions and need to be maintained (seeing that creation of institutions might still be challenged by actors who want to keep in place more dominant institutions).
- ▲ Institutional work entails different types of work to be conducted by SIE-field-actors and other field-actors: emotional work, identity work, boundary work, strategy work, practice work and values work.

Relations between SIE-field (and its SIE) and the 'outside' institutional environment:

- ▲ Existing regulative institutions, and actors creating and maintaining them, play a key role since they initiate, support, allow, restrict, shape, and control the emergence and developments of SIE-fields.
- ▲ Existing normative and cultural-cognitive institutions have influenced the emergence and development of SIE-fields in some countries (such as the speed and direction of transitions). For example, the entrenchment of the fossil fuel industry and resilient notions of centralised energy systems can impede the development of some SIE-fields, while the need to align with policy goals and market approaches can influence how SIE-fields develop.

Some of these working propositions need to be developed further based on the conceptual work that will be conducted as part of WP1 in SONNET.

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6 APPENDIX 1: PUBLICATIONS STRATEGY TO DATE

The following publications have been submitted to journals or are in planning based on the SONNET WP3 work.

Table 12 List of current publications and progress so far

Author(s)	Title of publication/ working title	Progress so far
Hielscher et al.	Social mobilisation in energy transitions: Examining scalar practices in contested fossil fuel energy pathways in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands and Poland	To be submitted in 2021
Iskandarova et al.	Tangled transitions: Exploring the emergence of local electricity exchange in three European countries	To be submitted in 2021
Iskandarova et al.	Iskandarova, M. Dembek, A., Fraaije, M., Matthews, W., Stasik, A., Wittmayer, J., B.K. Sovacool. (2021) Who finances renewable energy in Europe? Examining temporality, authority and contestation in solar and wind subsidies in Poland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. <i>Energy Strategy Reviews</i> ; https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2021.100730	Accepted in October 2021 Journal: <i>Strategic Energy Review</i>
Ranville et al.	How do community renewable energy intermediaries cope with tensions? A comparative analysis in France, Germany and Switzerland	To be submitted in 2022
Rogge et al.	Policy mixes for social innovation? An exploration for case studies of social innovation in the energy sector	To be submitted in 2022 Journal: <i>Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions</i>

7 APPENDIX 2: EC SUMMARY REQUIREMENTS

Changes with respect to the DoA

The submission data of the deliverable has been changed from the 31.08.2021 to the 30.11.2021 due to COVID 19 restrictions that had an impact on the fieldwork during 2020 and 2021.

The title of the deliverable has slightly expanded by adding three words. The initial title was 'Synthesis report on the comparative analysis of SIE-initiatives in six countries: Encouraging the diversity, processes and contributions of SIE'. This has been upgraded by adding "SIE-fields and their", yielding 'Synthesis report on the comparative analysis of SIE-fields and their SIE-initiatives in six countries: Encouraging the diversity, processes and contributions of SIE'. We have made this slight adjustment to the title based on the enhancement of the case study work outlined in D3.1 (Hielscher et al., 2020). In line with our conceptual framework (see D1.2 (Wittmayer et al., 2020)), we slightly upgraded our embedded case study approach. We conducted 18 embedded case studies across all six SONNET countries (i.e. three per country). In these embedded case studies, 36 case studies of SIE-initiatives are nested within the SIE-field investigations (on average two per field, six per country).

Additional small changes to the overall WP3 work have been outlined in D3.1 (Hielscher et al., 2020) and D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021).

These changes were agreed by the project officer. There are no other changes in scope and content of the deliverable.

Dissemination and uptake

In combination with the SONNET typology (see D1.1 (Wittmayer et al., 2020)), conceptual framework (see D1.2 (Wittmayer et al., 2020)) and methodological guidelines (see D3.1 (Hielscher et al., 2020)), country and case study reports (see D3.2 (Hielscher and Wittmayer, 2021)), this deliverable has been informing publications in peer-reviewed journals (see Appendix 2), conference presentations and webinars (organised by ICLEI) that report on the SONNET case studies and their comparative analysis. In addition, this deliverable will be uploaded on the SONNET website and openly shared on the platform Zenodo.

Short Summary of results (<250 words)

In reference to the SONNET objectives, this report provides a comparative analysis on the basis of six country reports (each based on investigating three SIE-fields (and six SIE-initiatives)) as part of the case study work. The comparative analysis has developed a systematic understanding of the diversity of SIE, the processes of SIE, contributions of SIE and their local, regional and national contexts in which they evolve.

This deliverable includes: 1) an introduction to the WP3 work, outlining a) key concepts and conceptual map, b) research questions, c) embedded case study approach, d) conducting the fieldwork and e) list of country and case study reports; 2) a brief introduction into the country context in relations to SIE and past attention towards SIE; 3) deep dives into comparing each SIE-field (and their SIE-initiatives) across three countries: a) overview of dives into each SIE-field across three SONNET countries; b) summary of research questions, conceptual work, data collection, and comparative analysis approach for each SIE-field comparison and c) outline of key findings derived from each SIE-field comparative analysis across three countries and reflections on the enabling and impeding factors for SIE; 4) key highlights derived from comparative analysis of 18 case studies: a) methodological approach; b) comparing SIE-fields (and their SIE-initiatives) and c) working propositions. In the appendix, and outline of initial WP3 working propositions and a table of research papers that are in progress can be found.

Evidence of accomplishment

This deliverable and associated academic publications indicated in Appendix 2.

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